

WE'RE THE FUTURE OF WOMEN'S FOOTBALL; WE JUST DON'T KNOW IT YET!

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Abstract

Background: Although participation in women's football is continuing to increase, the number of women progressing in coaching has not followed this upward trend. With elite athletes possessing much 'capital', in that their knowledge, skills and experiences are likely to benefit them in a coaching career, a transition to coaching is common in men's football. However, this path remains less likely for women. A lack of female representation in coaching can impact all levels of the game, as well as wider perceptions of women's role in society. Therefore, this research aims to explore the journeys of elite Scottish female footballers, to investigate how their experiences may have impacted upon their career choices, and future intentions.

Methods: Framed in postmodern feminism, this research utilises a qualitative methodology to explore the lived experiences of elite Scottish female footballers. Eight semi-structured interviews were conducted with players who were currently playing in the top division in Scotland, and / or representing the Scottish national team. Interviews were conducted using Microsoft Teams and included open questions related to the players' experiences; from early introductions to the sport, through to their current semi-professional, or professional, status. Interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim, before being coded and grouped into themes using reflexive thematic analysis.

Findings: The early experiences and influences on the players' football journeys were largely similar, with many male influences. Most players had been to university, and / or had another job to subsidise the limited earnings of their professional contracts. The players all discussed their love of the game and the almost certainty that they would remain involved as long as possible. However few players saw themselves as full-time coaches at the end of their playing careers. Many reasons are posited for this including lack of role models, lack of opportunities, and past and current experiences of juggling dual-careers to subsidise the limited earnings as a player.

Conclusion: The overall conclusion is that most of the players consider coaching to be a rewarding career that they would enjoy, but many are hesitant due to the uncertain nature, and lack of earning potential. Many of these players have had (and sometimes continue to

have) dual careers and / or non-football qualifications, providing more options when their playing careers end. As governing bodies continue to provide funding and initiatives for growth, if women can focus solely on football at an earlier stage – and / or have access to more tangible role models in coaching – then the likelihood of them considering becoming high-level coaches in future is likely to be increased.

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I would also like to thank my husband for his unwavering support, from giving me the time to work, listening to my worries, offering advice, and generally being there for me. The last few years have been challenging for the whole family and I couldn't have got through it at all – never mind complete a Professional Doctorate – without his support (both physically and emotionally).

Finally, this research would not have been possible without the players who very kindly took the time to speak to me about their experiences. I thoroughly enjoyed meeting every one of them, each with their own interesting story. These young women really are an inspiration to many, and I thank them not only for their support with my research, but also for continuing to be inspirational role models, and positive advocates for women's football.

Dedication

I would like to dedicate this thesis to two people who never met but who both inspire me every day. Firstly, to my son who will never know just how much his arrival in the world brightened our lives when mum sadly had to leave it. He makes me smile every day and his positive outlook never fails to inspire me. As my number one fan he's at the heart of everything I do. Also, to my mum who I wish more than anything could be here to see this. As the hardest working, most selfless, person I've known, I strive to make her proud every day – and I know that she would be, just for being me.

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Abbreviations

FA	Football Association
FIFA	Federation Internationale de Football Associations
NCAA	National Collegiate Athletics Association
NGB	National Governing Body
SFA	Scottish Football Association
SRUC	Scotland's Rural College
SWF	Scottish Women's Football
SWPL	Scottish Women's Premier League
UEFA	Union of European Football Associations
UWS	University of the West of Scotland
WFLP	Women in Football Leadership Programme
WSL	Women's Super League

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1.0 Introduction

As women remain underrepresented in the field of coaching football, despite the growth in the women's professional game (Knoppers et al., 2021; Sawiuk, Lewis & Taylor, 2021), this research seeks to explore the experiences of current elite female players, and their intentions in relation to their post-playing career. This will make a novel addition to the current literature as it focuses on the coaching intentions of elite players – arguably one of the key demographics that could improve the coaching landscape – rather than an analysis of the journeys of those who have already chosen to embark on the career. Through exploring the experiences of women while they continue to play, it is hoped that this work will be able to contribute to new policies that seek to increase the number who then transition to coaching upon retirement, before it is too late.

Prior to the start of the 2022/23 season, in Scotland, 29% of SWPL teams were managed by women. It is not uncommon for male footballers to transition to coaching at the end of their playing career (Sleeman & Ronkainen, 2020), however this is seen far less frequently in the women's game (Knoppers et al., 2021); arguably impacting on the potential quality of coaching for younger players. Increasing the visibility of female football coaches is likely to have wide ranging positive impacts, including increased participation by girls (de Haan & Norman, 2020), more female coaches (Norman, 2015; LaVoi, 2016; Schull & Kihl, 2019; Bentzen, Dieffenback & Olusoga, 2020), and improved performances (Kerr & Banwell, 2014; Norman, 2015; Banwell, Kerr & Stirling, 2020), therefore governing bodies' policies have been developed to address the gap in this country, and across Europe. The main ones of note here – which will be discussed in section 1.6 – are the most recent SFA and UEFA women's strategies. For the first time, in 2020 and 2019 respectively, these governing bodies have produced strategies aimed specifically at the women's game, alongside their wider development plans. With a growing focus on increasing the quality and quantity of female coaches in football, this work seeks to explore the likelihood of current elite female players entering into coaching, and the factors which may have impacted upon this choice.

1.1 Aim

The aim of this research is to explore the experiences of current elite female footballers to investigate the impact of these on future coaching intentions.

1.2 Objectives

The above aim will be achieved through:

- An exploration of female players' reasons for initially taking up, and continuing to progress in football to a professional level
- An identification of the key influences on these players' careers
- An investigation into the likelihood of the players to become high-level coaches at the end of their playing careers
- An exploration into how the gender of the players' coaches throughout the years may have influenced their coaching intentions
- A discussion about the barriers and enablers to these women's progression as coaches

1.3 Research Question

How likely are elite female footballers to consider entering into coaching as a career, and what are the underlying reasons for this?

1.4 My Learning Journey

When I think of my 'journey', I see two main paths coming together that led to me embarking on this Professional Doctorate. Immediately after graduating from university in 2001 with a Leisure Studies degree – still unsure of what I wanted to do as a career, but knowing I had a passion for sport and teaching – I flew to New York to coach football. I thoroughly enjoyed this experience, although I did not want to be so far from home for the long-term, so after 18 months I moved back to Britain. I had no definite plans from here but found out that Myerscough College in Preston were in the process of starting a Girls' Football Academy and were keen to recruit a female coach. I believe I was in the right place at the right time here –

one of a few well qualified and experienced female coaches – and was offered the part-time job. A few months later the department were looking for someone to teach nutrition to the National Diploma students and I was happy to oblige, having studied this at a very basic level in my degree. I thoroughly enjoyed lecturing and as more opportunities arose, I took them, eventually being funded for my post-graduate teaching certificate, and taking on the full-time role as National Diploma Football Studies Programme Leader. This job was ideal for me as it involved lecturing between 9am-3pm, before coaching the girls' team every afternoon; allowing me to continue to develop my expertise as both a coach and a lecturer.

While working at the college I was lucky enough to be funded to do my UEFA B Licence. This qualification is expensive and challenging, so I was extremely grateful to be given the opportunity, and determined to make the most of it. The course was a lengthy one, where very high standards were expected, and – although I did not pass first time – with a lot of hard work and determination I gained the sought-after award. This put me in a very small minority as a woman at that time, and opened doors to me. I was offered a position with the Blackburn Rovers Girls' Centre of Excellence, allowing me to work with promising young players in a professional set up. This, alongside my college coaching, really allowed me to develop my skillset. This was the time that I started to notice the gender imbalance in sport, as I was one of only two women employed by Blackburn Rovers, and the only one in the sport department (not just football) at Myerscough College. I had a very good relationship with my colleagues in both roles, however I did feel that I was 'different' and was always trying to prove that I was in these positions due to my competence; not as a 'token' because of my gender. This is something I have reflected upon throughout this research; discussed further in my methodology section where I clarify my positionality and the potential impact of my own experiences on my interpretations.

My next big life event was not work related, but my husband and I decided that we wanted to move back to Scotland and that (having met in New York) we would like to travel again before we settled down. So, we left our jobs, sold our house, and flew to New Zealand for a year! There I worked as a manager in a gym and enjoyed playing football at weekends. I enjoyed the Monday-Friday, 9-5, routine that allowed me to take weekends off (something that a coaching job would not have done). Upon return from New Zealand lecturing jobs were

few and far between, so I started working as an Active Schools Coordinator. I did this job for two full years, before a part-time role at Scotland's Rural College (SRUC) came up. I was successful in my application, and my Active Schools manager was willing to allow me to work part-time in my current role, so my second spell in academia began. Although I had hoped to gain lecturing work as soon as I returned from New Zealand, in hindsight I am pleased the way things worked out as the years working with Active Schools gave me 'real life' experience of sport development that allows me to teach from experience, as well as from reading. As the department at SRUC grew a full-time position came up that I was fortunate enough to get, setting me down the path of full-time academia again.

A key moment in my most recent transition from solely lecturing to research, came when the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) took over our department in 2016, and I became a UWS employee. I still consider myself very lucky to be in the position I am now as I began my employment at SRUC with simply an honours degree, before deciding to take on a MSc in Sports Coaching in 2014, which I passed with distinction. Upon transitioning to work for UWS I realised most of my new colleagues were already doctors, and highly published. Having never considered research as part of my role I was keen to develop these skills and I worked with my MSc supervisor – who was now my colleague – to publish my dissertation. This was my first experience of writing for publication, and I really enjoyed it. I then decided I would like to work towards a PhD when the Dean of the school introduced me and the other ex-SRUC staff to the Professional Doctorate. I liked the sound of the course, with the taught element educating me about research before I had to take on a large-scale piece myself, so I enrolled.

I enjoyed some parts of the first two years more than others, but overall I found it very useful as I learned more about research methods and formed a good community of practice with my peers. I successfully passed the taught component before it was time to be given a bit more freedom to work towards my own thesis. It was not an easy decision for me to choose my final research topic and I did consider many avenues before settling on the one I did. I even did an assessment in second year that was to be based on my final topic but, although I got good feedback from my course tutor, and work colleagues who were keen to collaborate, I could not help but think it just was not right. After lots of deliberating I realised that if I was

to be successful, I had to choose something I knew I had a real passion for, that was of enough interest – professionally and in the field – to be valuable to others, and that I knew I stood a good chance of completing to a good standard. When I thought about it like this, there really was only one option: women and football coaching.

Throughout my coaching experiences I found myself in a real minority as a woman. Although it did not cross my mind at the time, I now realise that like many other female coaches I have since read about, I took on a persona to fit in with my colleagues, for example joining in the office banter. Also, upon reading others' experiences, I realise I too felt a need to overcompensate for my femininity, only really gaining the respect of male players, and some female ones, after showing competence as a player myself. Upon reflection I feel these experiences allow me to resonate with other female coaches, in some ways that I had not considered before. This feeling that I could relate to my study population was key to my choice of research question, and also to my interpretation of findings, as will be discussed in relation to positionality in the methodology section.

Having experienced coaching myself I was – and continue to be – frustrated by the lack of equity and hope that this research can make a difference to current players and coaches in the women's game. However, as my current profession – although related to coaching – is in academia I also had to make sure my Professional Doctorate would develop me as a lecturer and researcher, also making an impact upon this profession. Obviously, the act of undertaking primary research would be the main way in which I would develop professionally, gaining skills in interviewing, thematic analysis and academic writing. However, I also believe that in taking on this project that I will be able to impact general perceptions of women in sport, and perhaps other minority groups, as I continue my endeavour to use diverse examples in my teaching. Much of my teaching focuses on minority groups in sport and the first-hand knowledge I have gained throughout this process will be integral to the examples I can draw upon in class.

Although not a key responsibility of mine now, I feel that the potential for this research to have an impact upon the coaching profession cannot be underestimated. Through exploring the experiences of current players, I hope that the recommendations I make can increase the likelihood of this demographic progressing into coaching roles at all levels of the game.

Furthermore, through increasing the visibility of women as coaches in my lectures and tutorials, I hope that this impacts upon the beliefs and confidence of my own female students in relation to their future career ambitions.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

With its focus on the experiences of female footballers, and how these experiences have impacted upon their coaching intentions, it would make sense for the 'voices' of these women to form the basis of this study. For this reason, the research will be grounded in the feminist paradigm, broadly defined by Bierema and Cseh (2003, p8) as, "look[ing] at the world from a woman's perspective". The main epistemological assumption of this perspective is that individuals who have been marginalised by society have come to understand the world through the lens of the dominant group (Dewar, 1993). Although the landscape continues to evolve, football in this country – and most others – has historically been, and remains to be, dominated by white, heterosexual, non-disabled men (Matthews & Channon, 2019). This male dominance has likely led women to understand the sport through a masculine lens, impacting on their perceptions of their role as players and coaches. This in turn may have led to the continued reinforcement of the gendered stereotypes that prevail not only in football, but in sport in general, and the wider society. Examples of these stereotypes, include the perception that girls and women are physically weaker (Carlman & Hjalmarsson, 2019; Carcamo, Moreno & del Barrio, 2020), secondary to men in society (Carcamo, Moreno & del Barrio, 2020), and that their primary role is that of care giver (Ada-Lameiras & Rodriguez-Castro, 2021).

Feminism encompasses many (often contrasting) 'types', including Liberal, Radical, Socialist and Marxist (McAfee & Howard, 2009), with more contemporary feminist perspectives starting to move away from hitherto attempts to privilege women over men. Postmodern feminists, like more traditional ones, endeavour to eliminate male dominance over women but, unlike earlier advocates, they do not strive for female dominance; preferring to aim for equity that is unrelated to gender, race, ability, or any other characteristic. This framework is closely linked to the notion of intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989); described as a 'lens' for seeing how various forms of inequality interact (Crenshaw, 2020). It is important to note that both women and men in football face inequality and discrimination, therefore throughout the

research I remained cognisant of this, avoiding the assumption that experiences were simply gender related. Anstiss (2021, p1) sums up this overall strive for equity nicely as she opens her book about the rise of women's sport with the quote, "We don't want to take over, we just want to take part".

Postmodern feminism has its critics because of the historically uneasy relationship between the two paradigms. However, the perhaps slightly juxtaposed movements can work well together as, although there are some contentious points, feminism and postmodernism are "complimentary and mutually corrective" (Hekman, 2013, p225). While early feminist perspectives attempted to define an essential female nature, and to replace masculinist epistemologies with feminist ones, postmodernists argue for the rejection of the subject/object dichotomy. Postmodernists do not want to replace one hierarchy with another – their aim is to 'dissolve' these dualisms completely (Hekman, 2013).

By framing this research in the postmodern feminist perspective, I am rejecting the notion that there is one truth (neither masculine nor feminine) and accepting that there are many. In line with qualitative research in general, I understand that all knowledge is hermeneutic, and therefore have been transparent and critical about my positionality at all stages. Derrida (1997) emphasises that feminism should not aim to replace one truth with another, but that it should create multiple truths and voices. In analysing the data, I have scrutinised the language used by the players; listening carefully to each of their 'voices' and considering how their stories could be interpreted in relation to my research question.

A key influencer on early feminist perspectives, Foucault (1972), emphasised the importance of language, suggesting that knowledge and power are linked in discourse, and this emphasis on language is key to the bridging of postmodernism and feminism (Scott, 1988). Foucault's analysis also suggests that it is possible to create a discourse without the male/female hierarchy, opening up a new way of thinking about women, knowledge and power (Hekman, 2013). I aim to use this new way of thinking to encourage changing attitudes about the position of women in football, sport, and society.

One way the research may do this is by showing that women can be real assets to football, not just because they may have unique access to a niche market (i.e. other women) (Ely and

Thomas, 2001), but because they possess attitudes, ideas, and creativity of equal value (and some perhaps more) to those of men. Postmodern feminists aim to deconstruct the assumption that gender equity can only be achieved at the expense of effectiveness (Ely & Meyerson, 2000; Meyerson & Kolb, 2000). Therefore, through investigating the experiences of female footballers, this study will seek not only to discuss the impact of these experiences on the players' own future coaching intentions, but also how these experiences add value to their coaching 'toolkit'; providing support to the notion that female players may be key to improving the coaching landscape in Scotland, and perhaps worldwide.

I feel it is important at this point to clarify the terminology used throughout this thesis, as there is much discussion around the correct use of the words, woman/en and female. In creating a current glossary, Rioux and colleagues (2022) explain that 'sex' is generally accepted as a "biological feature" (p4) (although this is socially constructed), whereas 'gender' is a "social configuration" (p5), related to society's view of masculinity and femininity. In critiquing gender terminology, I agree with Rioux and colleagues (2022) when they suggest the terms male and female to describe human beings is derogatory; preferring to use woman as a noun, and female as an adjective. The only situation where this is not strictly the case is in relation to women's football as this is the widely used term for the female version of the game.

1.6 The Current Situation

Addressing the gender imbalance has recently been a key focus in women's football research (e.g Norman, Rankin-Wright & Allison, 2018; Clarkson, Cox & Thelwell, 2019; Lewis, Roberts & Andrews, 2019; Knoppers et al., 2021). Before wider literature is analysed, this section will illustrate the current coaching landscape in Scotland and England. I feel this is a good place to start as it will present an overview of the current gender balance, to allow those in decision making roles to see how and where improvements can be made. The gender of head coaches in Scotland is of interest, as this is where the current study is based. This section shows the uniqueness of the research context, as the Scottish women's game is in a period of growth. Although progress is arguably lagging behind that of England – where both top divisions are fully professional – with more teams offering contracts to players each year, current players

(therefore potential future coaches) are worthy of study. Figures from England have also been included in the section, for comparison.

Although increasing research attention has been placed upon the gender gap in coaching, it is especially difficult to find statistics from Scotland, so this section brings together relevant information from the top levels in the country for comparison and analysis. Due to the nature of football management, with its high turnover (Gonzalez-Gomez, Picazo-Tadeo & Garcia-Rubio, 2011; Bell, Brooks & Markham, 2013), this fluctuates regularly, but at the time of writing – start of season 2022/23 – there remains a clear gender gap in relation to the head coaches of women’s teams in the top divisions. The tables below (Tables 1-4) show head coach gender across the top divisions in Scotland and England.

Table 1 SWPL 1 teams and gender of head coach in 2022

Team	Head Coach	Gender
Aberdeen	Emma Hunter/Gavin Beith	F/M
Celtic	Fran Alonso	M
Glasgow City	Scott Booth	M
Hamilton	Stuart Taylor	M
Hearts	Eva Olid	F
Hibs	Dean Gibson	M
Motherwell	Paul Brownlie	M
Partick Thistle	Brian Graham	M
Rangers	Malky Thomson	M
Spartans	Debbi McCulloch	F
	Total	3F, 8M

Table 2 SWPL 2 teams and gender of head coach in 2022

Team	Head Coach	Gender
Boroughmuir Thistle	Suzy Shepherd	F
Dundee United	Graeme Hart	M
Glasgow Women	Craig Joyce	M
Kilmarnock	Jim Chapman	M
Queens Park	Barry Rodgers	M
St Johnstone	Grant Scott	M
Stirling Uni	Craig Beveridge	M
	Total	1F, 6M

Table 3 WSL 1 teams and gender of head coach in 2022

Team	Head Coach	Gender
Arsenal	Jonas Eidevall	M
Aston Villa	Carla Ward	F
Birmingham City	Darren Carter (interim)	M
Brighton	Hope Powell	F
Chelsea	Emma Hayes	F
Everton	Chris Roberts / Claire Ditchburn (interim)	M/F
Leicester	Lydia Bedford	F
Manchester City	Gareth Taylor	M
Manchester United	Marc Skinner	M
Reading	Kelly Chambers	F
Spurs	Rehanna Skinner	F
West Ham	Olli Harder	M
	Total	7F/6M

Table 4 WSL 2 teams and gender of head coach in 2022

Team	Head Coach / Manager(s)	Gender
Blackburn Rovers	Gemma Donnelly	F
Bristol City	Lauren Smith	F
Charlton	Karen Hills	F
Coventry	Jay Bradford	M
Crystal Palace	Dean Davenport	M
Durham	Lee Sanders	M
Lewes	Craig Gill	M
Liverpool	Matt Beard	M
London City	Melissa Phillips	F
Sheffield Utd	Neil Redfearn	M
Sunderland	Melanie Copeland	F
Watford	Clinton Lancaster	M
	Total	5F/7M

These tables highlight the minority that women continue to find themselves in as football coaches in Britain. In Scotland women account for less than a quarter (22%) of all of head coaches of women's teams, while in England the figure is slightly higher, but still below half (48%). It should also be noted that for the first time since the Scottish Football Association (SFA) took over responsibility for the women's team in 1998, the national team is currently managed by a man; Pedro Martinez Losa, appointed in 2021. Conversely, after being managed by men since 2013, England appointed Sarina Wiegman, a Dutch woman, in 2021.

On a wider scale, looking at international teams, during the 2022 UEFA Women's European Championships, ten countries were managed by men (62.5%), compared with six managed by women (37.5%). These figures relate only to women's football – in the men's game there are no female head coaches in Scotland or England's fully professional leagues, nor of national men's teams.

These figures are useful in providing an overview of the current gender gap, but it is worth adding here about some of the work that is being done to address this. Recent research by the Observatory for Sport in Scotland (Brown & Murray, 2021) highlights the gender gap in sports leadership in Scotland, finding that 27% of all sports coaches are women. Perhaps more worrying is that this number has fallen by four per cent over the last five years. Brown and Murray's findings are interesting considering many governing bodies list increasing female representation as a key priority, again reinforcing the need for further research that can explore the potential reasons for this limited success.

In England, one policy that had a real impact on National Governing Bodies (NGBs) was the Code for Sports Governance. This tasked any bodies receiving funding from the government or the National Lottery with ensuring a minimum of 30% of each gender on their board. From many bodies having no women at all on their boards, after the introduction of the code in 2019, 72% had met the 30% target (Farrer & Co., 2019). This shows the power of money, as the same research found that although NGBs had embraced diversity, professional clubs (for whom the code did not relate) had not done the same. Only one Premier League football club met the 30% target in 2019, with the average representation being 10%, and 11 of the 20 clubs (55%) with no women at all on their boards (Farrer & Co., 2019). More recent figures show a slight improvement, with the Fairgame report (Fairgame, 2022) showing 40% of Premier League clubs remaining all-male. The funders explain that this 30% target is simply that – a target, rather than a quota – and support is provided to aid organisations as they make “an ongoing public commitment” to diversifying their workforces (Farrer & Co., 2016).

In 2019 the European governing body for football (UEFA) produced its first Women's Football Strategy; Time for Action. In addition to its ambitious aim of doubling the number of female players by 2024, it also identified addressing the gender imbalance at leadership level as a key priority, aiming to double female representation on all UEFA bodies (UEFA, 2019a).

Perhaps more encouragingly – in that it does not further divide the men and women’s game – the generic strategy (Together for the Future of Football) (UEFA, 2019b) cites women’s football as the first of its strategic priorities, again stating the aim of doubling the number of female players in the continent. Furthermore, one of the policy’s objectives is to “ensure football in Europe is accessible and available to all” (UEFA, 2019b, p17). This objective shows that not only is the aim for parity across genders, but also across all characteristics that have in the past impacted participation (addressing ‘intersectionality’ (Crenshaw, 1989), discussed further below).

Resulting from the Time for Action strategy (UEFA, 2019b), came the UEFA Coach Development Programme for Women (UEFA, 2021), which offers financial scholarships to female coaches for UEFA diploma courses. In addition, a working group was formed to ensure that women’s football content is included in all coach education courses, and a mentoring programme was introduced (UEFA, 2021). This mentoring programme will allocate a personal mentor – one who is an experienced coach – to a group of developing female coaches who already hold their UEFA Pro diplomas. These initiatives address some of the key barriers identified below in the literature review, including cost of education, frustration about the masculine nature of courses, and lack of support. Finally, the UEFA Academy runs the UEFA Women in Football Leadership Programme (WFLP); a training week that seeks to support women to have more influence over the game throughout their careers (UEFA, 2021).

In Britain, just last year the Football Association (FA) launched a Coaching Excellence initiative (The FA, 2021a). This initiative is not exclusively for women, but is for coaches working in the elite women’s game. Through individual and group workshops, and peer mentoring support, the initiative seeks to focus on the needs that are specific to women’s football in the country. This addresses a key finding of Norman, Rankin-Wright and Allison’s (2018) study that found rather than just qualifications, female coaches desired more visible pathways for progression, with adequate support at each stage; both vertical (from educators and experienced coaches), and horizontal (from peers) in nature.

Similarly, the Scottish Football Association (SFA) also recently produced a strategy for girls’ and women’s football – Accelerate Our Game (SFA, 2020a) – which aims to empower female leaders at all levels. And, produced in conjunction with UEFA, this strategy sits alongside the

generic strategy, *The Power of Football* (SFA, 2020b), which also highlights the growth of girls' and women's football as a key priority. The introduction to *Accelerate Our Game* highlights women's football as the largest area of growth, suggesting its "potential [is] limitless" (SFA, 2020a, p1). The strategy aims to be a "catalyst" (ibid) to continued growth and improvement at all levels, through six strategic pillars: inspire and support lifelong participation; take elite competitions and clubs to the next level; deliver successful national teams and a world class performance system; improve visibility and change perceptions; increase commercial revenues; optimise organisation and governance structures (SFA, 2020b).

Not related specifically to gender, the Premier League Coach Index (The FA, 2021b) was launched in 2021 to increase opportunities in coaching among all underrepresented groups. This Index aims to increase the opportunities available, and visible, to minority group coaches, by alerting them to relevant coaching opportunities and training. Coaches with a minimum Level 2 coaching award can sign up for these alerts in the hope that they will continue to develop and progress in the game, addressing the lack of diversity throughout the country. Clubs will also receive support from the FA as they strive to increase the diversity of their workforces (The FA, 2021b).

These policies show that reducing the gender gap throughout football is a priority of national and international bodies. However, with these policies in place, and the gender gap showing little signs of reducing, I would argue this novel piece of research is key to gaining a deeper understanding of the reasons that many female players fail to progress as coaches. Through understanding what is really limiting progress related to the number of female players choosing to transition to coaching, perhaps policies can be better tailored to individual needs.

2.0 Literature Review

In this section a range of literature will be reviewed to further analyse the theoretical framework, before providing an overview of the historical and current role of women in sport and society, barriers faced as they aim to progress, and the qualities that they can bring to the workforce.

2.1 Postmodern Feminism

Postmodern feminism was chosen as the framework for this research as it strives to reduce the inequality that prevails in so many aspects of society. This is not only related to gender, but also race, disability, class, sexual orientation, etc. (Bierema & Cseh, 2003). There are many demographics that face discrimination in football (Kassimeres, 2021), and although this study focuses mainly on gender, it is expected that findings may be related to some other minority groups – such as non-white individuals, people with disabilities and the LGBTQ+ community – and in some cases, individuals who possess characteristics from more than one. This recognition that one's gender is often not the only one that influences equality issues was the basis of 'intersectional feminism' (Crenshaw, 1989). In a recent interview Crenshaw (2020) explained how various forms of inequality can act together, exacerbating the inequality faced by some individuals.

Intersectionality is defined by Weldon (2008, p193) as "a concept that describes the interaction between systems of oppression". These 'systems of oppression' include – among others – race, gender, class, disability, nationality, sexual orientation and age (Burnham, 2001). Shields (2008) further discusses how categories of one's social identity – such as gender, or social class – take their meaning in relation to other categories, thus challenging assumptions such as psychology's homogenisation of gender (Shields, 2008). This is important to note as the following study aims to understand experiences of female footballers, however their gender is only one aspect of their character. This makes it likely that although they are all female, other categories of their identity will mean that they live different experiences in relation to their individual characteristics, and the interaction of these.

Morris and Bunjun (2007, p1) agree that “women are not one group of people who think the same way, have the same experiences, or live the same life”, and this is key to postmodern feminism. Feminists have long challenged the dichotomy of male and female, and masculinity and femininity, therefore this paradigm can help make sense of the stereotypical roles that are incongruous with sport, and more specifically, football. This notion of stereotypical gender-based characteristics can be seen in the coaching literature where findings suggest female coaches often feel obliged to take on traditionally masculine traits to succeed (Smith et al., 2019; Chapman et al., 2020; Sawiuk, Lewis and Taylor, 2021). Rather than being defined by one’s gender, feminists would argue that individuals fall on a spectrum of masculinity and femininity (Lorber, 1994; Miller, 2010).

Historically, sporting success has been associated with traits such as aggression, power, and competitiveness (Lines, 2003; Roper and Polasek, 2014); traditionally male characteristics (Lafontaine & Kamphoff, 2016). Feminine traits, however, are often understood as emotionally needy, weak and passive (Norman, 2010); unlikely to bring success in a sporting arena (Messner, 1992; Anderson, 2008). Although through sport women are increasingly showing that they can be strong, competitive, and successful (Dashper, 2018; McGannon et al., 2019) – and men are more frequently showing more traditionally feminine traits (such as vulnerability and caring) (Lavega et al., 2017; Piedra, 2017) – success in sport continues to be largely promoted through the achievements, and associated visibility, of young (often white, heterosexual, non-disabled) males; reinforcing these dominant ideologies.

With visibility a key influencer on perceptions, the media play a huge part in promoting hegemonic masculinity as the dominant ideology in sport (Trujillo, 1991). Hegemonic masculinity was a concept first developed by Connell in 1987, related to the social construction of gender in society (Grindstaff, 2011). The main driver of Connell’s (1987) original work was her critique of role theory, namely its static nature that provided no room for resistance and social change (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005). Connell (1987) therefore talked about ‘masculinities’ rather than the singular, ‘masculine’, defining these as “configurations of practice that are accomplished in social action and, therefore, can differ according to the gender relations in a particular social setting” (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005; p836).

Hegemonic masculinity, according to Connell (2005), is at the top of the hierarchy of masculinities, leading to the dominant position of men, and the subordination of women in society. This hegemonic masculinity draws on Gramsci's (1971) notion of cultural hegemony, used to explain the interaction of culture and power in capitalist societies. Lears (1985) discusses the lack of one precise definition of this concept, but emphasises that consent and force exist together, although one will always dominate. This also relates to Foucault's notion of 'discursive practice'; the available vocabulary limiting the clarification of social alternatives (Lears, 1985). This concept will be a recurring theme throughout this thesis as sport has historically been, and – to a lesser extent – continues to be “one of the most masculine (and sex-segregated) of institutions ... largely organized by and for men” (Grindstaff, 2011, p861).

Feminist research spans many fields and the lack of visibility of successful women is not only apparent in sport. In her study of the role of postmodern feminism in education, Wallin (1999) found that women are often excluded from subject matter, leading students to miss valuable insight, and to believe that women are incapable of knowledge production. Furthermore, this exclusion reinforces invisibility and devalues women in the field (Martin, 1994). Wallins' (1990) study draws real parallels to those conducted in sport, as the paucity of female coaches means valuable insight (i.e. coaching skills) can be missed, and the perception that women are incapable is reinforced, devaluing further their presence.

As postmodern feminism suggests, there is no one solution to all situations, but all stakeholders must play a role in developing alternatives (Wallin, 1999). Feminist research aligns well with qualitative, interpretative studies where participants are viewed as collaborators in knowledge production, rather than objects to be manipulated (Bierema & Cseh, 2003). Worrell (1996, p476) suggests that feminist research, “challenges traditional scientific inquiry, focuses on the experiences and lives of women, considers asymmetrical power arrangements, recognises gender as an essential category of analysis, attends to language and power to “name”, promotes social activism and societal change”. This societal change is a key aim of this paper. However, in line with postmodern feminism, this change is not aimed solely at women. As Wallin (1999, p26) explains, postmodern feminist theory should promote “reciprocal trust, knowledge sharing, open structures, consultation and good communication for morally responsible policy making”. This means the intention is not to

exclude men from this process, but to ensure both genders are included, and tasked equally with contributing to good practice.

In their paper which critiques traditional feminist frameworks, Shaw and Frisby (2006) criticise previous attempts at gender equity, such as 'fix the women', 'value the feminine' and 'create equal opportunities'. These previous 'frames' "accommodate existing systems" (Ely & Meyerson, 2000, p112), rather than challenge the sources of power that reproduce hegemonic masculinity. This can be seen in Crocket's (2017) review of literature in which she concludes that, across sports, female coaches rarely created alternative discourses; rather 'problematise' the current one in which men are superior. Postmodern feminists understand the importance of striving for equity, rather than equal opportunities, to ensure no one gender, or other demographic, is devalued (Bierema & Cseh, 2003).

In adding a fourth frame, Ely and Meyerson (2000) discuss three processes that marginalise women in society. These processes – 'informal practices', 'symbols of success', and 'the public face of organisations' – are visible in football, both in the men's and women's game. Examples of informal practices include timings of meetings that may be more difficult for women who have caring responsibilities to attend (Meyerson & Fletcher, 2000), and 'old boys' networks' (Brass, 1985; Aicher & Sagas, 2009). Symbols of success refers to the way in which success is acknowledged, often related to traditionally masculine practices such as competition and control (Knights & McCabe, 2001). The public face of the organisation suggests that the dominant demographic tend to hold positions of authority and are more visible (Ely & Thomas, 2001), reinforcing this as the norm. Throughout the remainder of this literature review, and in the findings section, examples of these processes will be discussed.

In relation to visibility, through highlighting the achievements of male athletes, the media serves to reinforce hegemonic masculinity as the epitome of success and athleticism. This happens not only through the back pages, but as much sports coverage sits within the "news media", it is often associated with "objectivity and balance"; regarded "a truthful reflection of society" Anstiss (2020, p62). Where female athletes do gain media attention, previous research shows that this coverage tends to focus more on their personal lives and appearance, rather than their achievements.

A good example of this is highlighted in Anstiss' (2021) book, *The Unstoppable Rise of Women's Sport*. Anstiss discusses a post-match interview at the 2015 Australian Open (tennis) where, following her second-round victory – rather than asking about Eugenie Bouchard's performance – the male journalist chose to ask her to 'give us a twirl' to show off her outfit. Similarly, upon receiving the first Women's Ballon d'Or in 2018 (an award that is widely accepted to be given to the world's best player, one which has been contested by male players since 1956) Ada Hegerberg of Lyon and Croatia was asked by the host DJ to 'twerk' (dance provocatively) (Aarons, 2018).

This type of coverage downplays the importance of female athletes' athleticism, and further reinforces gendered stereotypes of femininity (Gardner, 2015; Dashper, 2018). Blatant sexism seems less prevalent now, evidenced in part by Dashper's (2018) study of media representation of female athletes at the 2016 Olympic games. This study showed that obvious sexualisation was less apparent than previously reported, however it was noted that the coverage remained "ambivalent" (p17), seemingly hesitant in presenting athletic achievements, and continuing to focus more on athletes' personal lives.

More recent figures from a BBC survey of elite female athletes from a range of sports echo Dashper's (2018) findings, in relation to the improving – yet still unbalanced – media coverage. Results from the survey show that although 85% of respondents felt that the media did not do enough to promote women's sport, and 86% felt that they reported differently on men's and women's sport, 93% of respondents believed that media coverage had improved over the previous five years (BBC, 2020).

This focus of the media on non-athletic traits, coupled with the sheer lack of coverage at all (Cohen, 2013; Cooky, Messner & Hextrum, 2013; Cooky, Messner & Musto, 2015), does little to challenge the dominant discourse of sport as a masculine domain. Although recent years have seen increases in live broadcast of women's football in Scotland, it accounts for only two percent of mainstream media coverage (SFA, 2020a). Messner, Dunbar and Hunt (2000) highlight the media's role in pressuring males to conform to traditional masculine standards, through their promotion of strong aggressive men as superior to those showing a more passive and sensitive side. With the sporting environment identified as a real site for the reproduction of hegemonic masculinity (Messner, 1992; Connell, 2005; Connell &

Messerschmidt, 2005; Grindstaff, 2011), and the media's role in promoting sport, it is understandable that feminists find this a real barrier to their strive for parity.

Shaw and Frisby (2016) add to their fourth frame with a focus on intersectionality of gender with other aspects of diversity, highlighting the need to deconstruct current discourses that suggest that gender equity is incongruent with organisational effectiveness. To the contrary, Terjesen, Sealy and Singh (2009) suggest that board diversity is key to optimal decision making and financial success in organisations. These additions will form part of the feminist critique throughout this work, which will strive for equity rather than dominance of one demographic (Hemmings, 2011), and the move away from the notion of a dichotomy, towards more fluidity in relation to masculinity and femininity; postmodern feminism being the "ultimate acceptor of diversity, multiple truths, roles and realities" (Uche, 2017, p31).

In summary, the main tenets of postmodern feminism are the strive for equity, rather than a replacement of any historical and / or current hierarchies. Through addressing intersectionality, and dissolving hierarchies and dualisms, it is hoped that women's football (and men's football) will improve as a result of the increased diversity within governing organisations, teams, and the individuals within them.

2.2 The Gender Gap

It is widely reported that women and girls are largely underrepresented in sports participation across the globe (World Health Organisation (WHO), 2021). Specific to Scotland, Brown & Murray (2021) highlight a 10% gender gap from age 11, continuing through the life cycle. Although the gap remains evident today, some research does show that the number of women taking part in sport has been steadily increasing (Farrer & Co., 2019; De Haan & Knoppers, 2020; Anstiss, 2021). This increase is particularly evident in women's football which, according to Sleeman and Ronkainen (2020, p2), is in a period of "unprecedented growth". In Scotland, the most recent SFA figures show that there are now over 17,000 registered female players in this country, an increase of 17% from the 2019 World Cup (the first time Scotland had qualified) (SFA, 2020a). However, although this increase in participation, which can be seen throughout the world (Hall & Oglesby, 2016; Clarkson, Cox & Thelwell, 2019; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019), is encouraging, it is not yet reflected in

the coaching workforce (Lapchick, 2018; Lewis et al., 2018; Fasting, Sand and Nordstrand, 2019; Darvin & Lubke, 2021; Knoppers et al., 2021).

A major development in football in Britain was the inception of the Women's Super League (WSL) in England in 2011, and subsequent transition to a full-time professional league in 2018 (Garry, 2018). This development has improved the quality and reputation of the women's game (UEFA, 2019a), and has allowed women from around the world to become full-time footballers. These increased opportunities, and improved reputation, is likely to lead to further increases in participation as young players can now see an opportunity to have a career that hitherto was not possible in Britain. Although not fully professionalised in Scotland, recent figures show over 70 players on professional contracts – although not all of these are full-time – in the Scottish Women's Professional League (SWPL), with a target of an increase of ten percent annually (SFA, 2020a). This number is growing, with Kilmarnock FC, a SWPL 2 club, announcing that six players had signed professional contracts, and another six amateur contracts for the forthcoming season (Kilmarnock FC, 2022). The professionalisation of women's football has in turn opened up more opportunities for coaching within the women's game (Woodward, 2017), however this has not necessarily helped – perhaps even hindered – the gender gap, as men are now more likely to apply for these (now higher profile) positions (Ronkainen, Sleeman & Richardson, 2020).

Although female football coaches remain in a minority, the statistics presented above (Tables 1-4) are more promising than those in Lewis and colleagues' (2018) study, which showed only two female managers across the two WSL divisions, perhaps a sign that the situation is improving. The gender gap increases with level of performance, recent figures showing that throughout Europe less than twenty per cent of coaches of women's national teams were female (UEFA, 2018). Furthermore at elite club level, since the start of the UEFA Women's Champions' League until 2018, there had been only 23 female head coaches, compared to 147 men (Filho and Rettig, 2018). More recent figures provide some interesting information. Knoppers and colleagues' (2021) highlight that between 2000 and 2019, with one exception, all coaches of major competition winners in the women's game (i.e. Olympics, World Cup, European Championships) have been female. This could suggest that, although they make up

a minority of the coaching workforce, female coaches have statistically been more successful on the national stage.

Regarding participation, it appears that in this country, and many others, football (even at elite level in some cases) remains a hobby, rather than a career choice for women. This may be one reason for the gender gap that seems to widen in relation to coaching, and other leadership positions in the game. Gledhill and Harwood (2015) found that unlike many young men who are likely to identify completely as footballers (Mills et al., 2014), most young female players construct multiple identities throughout adolescence, likely due to the hitherto lack of career opportunities. In their study of high-level youth players in England, Sleeman and Ronkainen (2020) found that where boys saw football as an achievable and rewarding career path, girls continued to view it as a hobby. The authors did find, however, that some Academy coaches were applying increasing pressure on the girls to focus solely on the sport, more in line with what has traditionally been seen in the male game (Mills et al., 2014). For this reason it is not unlikely that this 'identity foreclosure' (the commitment to an ideological position without full exploration of other options (Marcia, 1996)) will become more common in the women's game in future.

In the wider context, female sports coaches are greatly outnumbered by male coaches (Lapchick, 2018; Banwell, Kerr & Stirling, 2019; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019; De Haan & Knoppers, 2020; Brown & Murray, 2021), and this disparity is particularly evident at higher performance levels (LaFontaine and Kamphoff, 2016; MacInnes, 2017; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019), and in male dominated sports (LaFontaine and Kamphoff, 2016; Sanderson and Gramlich, 2016; MacInnes, 2017; Darvin & Lubke, 2021). Recent research in Scotland (Brown & Murray, 2021) shows that since 2016 the number of female sport coaches has fallen by nearly four per cent; this demographic representing just over a quarter of coaches across all sports. Across Europe, a recent study showed that less than a third of sport coaches were female (Moustakas, Petry & Lara-Bercial, 2021). These data are limited as the authors admit more than half of the clubs they investigated were unable to report their gender balance. This is perhaps a concern in itself, in that these clubs may not have increasing diversity as a priority if they do not know their current status. Although the sporting landscape is very different in America, in relation to funding and commercialisation, it is

interesting to note that in the National Collegiate Athletics Association (NCAA) men hold 60% of head coach roles in women's sport, and 98% of head coach roles in men's sport (Darven & Lubke, 2020), mirroring findings across Europe.

The gender gap in sport coaching has not gone unnoticed, and one explanation provided for the large drop in female coaches in women's college sport in America, may also be relevant here in Britain. In America Title IX was introduced in 1998 (Acosta and Carpenter, 2014) to reduce gender discrimination in college athletics. The law made it illegal to discriminate between genders, and thus led to increased finance for women's sport (where until then it had received little backing). This increased finance led women's sport to achieve a higher status, a positive step for female athletes. However, where this law brought increased opportunities for female athletes, it seems to have had the opposite effect on women's coaching opportunities. Before the inception of Title IX, 90% of women's college teams were coached by women, before dropping to 43% in 2014. With the increased profile and monetary rewards now available in women's sport, Acosta and Carpenter (2014) argue that this has enticed more men to enter the arena.

Although not directly comparable to Britain – where money involved in sport, especially at college / university level, is far less – as more money becomes available through the professionalisation of the WSL, and increasing profile of the top leagues in Scotland, it is likely that men are now more likely to find coaching in the women's game more appealing than in the past. Ronkainen, Sleeman and Richardson (2020) offer another possible reason that men are increasingly gaining employment as coaches of women's teams. Through their interviews with ten elite female coaches in England, they found that these women felt that men were increasingly attracted to coaching in the women's game, seeing it as a quicker route to higher levels of competition, impacting on the opportunities for women to work in this environment.

Related to sport in general, a recent large-scale study of coaching in Britain shows far less of a gender gap than many previously. However, upon analysis, this is likely a result of the broad definition of coaching used. The survey, by UK Coaching, found that, in 2019, 43% of the coaching workforce was female, a decrease of 3% from 2017 (Thompson, Whitaker & Bunyan, 2020). However, upon delving deeper into these figures some interesting findings appear.

The study uses a wide definition of coaching, including roles such as community activators, teachers, and fitness instructors.

While this report provides useful and interesting data for many purposes, it is not reflective of sport coaching per se, especially at more elite levels. Although the survey found a relatively small gender gap overall, it was apparent that significantly less women had a formal coaching qualification, with men almost twice as likely to coach in clubs, academies, and sports institutes. As the level of qualification increased, the gender gap widened. This can also be seen in football, where a recent study conducted in England found that of the 390 individuals who held the UEFA Pro Licence (the highest coaching award), only seven (1.8%) were women (Sawiuk, Lewis & Taylor, 2021). In Scotland the proportion is almost identical (1.8%), with only three women among the 164 pro licence holders (Lange, 2020).

The UK Coaching survey highlighted a discrepancy in the types of activity coached between genders, with almost twice as many men coaching invasion games, and almost four times as many women coaching dance, thus fitting in with traditional gender stereotypes. Male coaches were also significantly more likely to say they had a better understanding of high-level athletes, and to refer to themselves as a 'coach' (Thompson, Whitaker & Bunyan, 2020). In addition to the disparity in relation to level of qualification, this may suggest two things that are common across the literature: 1. that many of the women identified as active coaches were perhaps teachers, fitness instructors, or acting in a more supporting role (LaFountaine & Kamphoff, 2016), and 2. that women were less confident in their ability, preferring to downplay their qualities (Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019).

As well as providing some interesting statistics, this section also shows the importance of critiquing language, highlighting how the interpretation of the word 'coach', and the specific characteristics of the study sample, can affect findings. This influence of language and context was key to the current study that explores the experiences of a very specific group. This demographic grew up, and continue to exist, in an environment where women's football is only starting to see signs of professionalisation. Scotland could be said to be ahead of some nations, with some players on professional contracts, but still behind others, for example England where the top division is fully professional. Therefore, by investigating the coaching intentions of these players, considering how their past experiences have impacted,

recommendations will be made to improve gender equity in sport, here, and perhaps in other nations both more and less advanced in relation to the status of the women's game.

2.3 Barriers Faced by Women

Much of the previous literature about female sport coaches has highlighted several barriers that seem to be stopping them entering and progressing in the role. Thompson, Whitaker and Bunyan's (2020) study, discussed above, involved surveying over 50,000 adults and 2,000 children (of both genders) to explore their experiences of coaching, and of being coached. The study found the most common barrier to women's' participation in coaching was the cost of training. This is an interesting finding as the cost of coaching courses is the same for men and women, however an interview with Rachel Yankey – a former England international footballer and coach – may provide one explanation. Speaking to MacInnes (2017) Yankey explained that the lack of jobs available to women upon qualification was off-putting, as the number and quality of opportunities failed to justify the cost of attending the courses.

This feeling of limited opportunities upon qualification was echoed by participants in Norman, Rankin-Wright and Allison's (2018) study of English female coach educators, who felt they had limited opportunities for progression and paid employment in their field. Further studies in Europe have presented similar findings, with women sharing the belief that female coaches tend to only be appointed to women's teams (LaFontaine & Kamphoff, 2016; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019; Knoppers et al., 2021), restricting their opportunities at the highest level. Furthermore, paid employment in women's teams is becoming increasingly difficult as more men begin to coach in the women's game (Ronkainen, Sleeman & Richardson, 2020; Knoppers et al., 2021).

Lack of opportunity in men's football can hinder qualified women's earning potential, making it difficult for them to see coaching as a sole career. This is because women's teams generally receive less funding than men's (FIFPro, 2017; LaVoi, Wasend & Baeth, 2019), limiting the feasibility of women becoming full-time coaches. Without the reward of a valuable role upon completion, it is understandable that many women cannot justify spending large sums of money on coaching qualifications. Further to this lack of potential future earning, Knoppers and colleagues (2021) also found that men were more likely to be sponsored by a Football

Association to allow them to coach at national level, where women more often had to pay for courses themselves. This barrier prevented at least one coach from Knoppers and colleagues' (2021) study from gaining the licence she needed to coach initially, and another believed men were given priority for entry into the limited capacity courses.

Another barrier that rated highly in Thompson, Whitaker and Bunyan's (2020) study was difficulty in finding a work-life balance as a coach; however in this study the barrier was more likely to be faced by men than women. This finding is in contrast to many previous ones which tend to associate the juggle of coaching and family life with women (e.g. *Women in Sport*, 2015; Carson, McCormack & Walsh, 2018; Smith et al, 2019). This conflict may again be linked to the wide definition of coaching used by UK Coaching – where teachers and instructors are more likely to be paid professions – and the fact that the men in this study tended to be coaching at a higher level, where time commitment is generally higher than at recreational level. Related to the 'informal practices' identified by Ely and Meyerson (2000), the amount of travelling required, and irregular hours involved in coaching, could be seen as an indirect barrier to women, who tend to be more likely to have to combine the role with family commitments, and often another career outside of sport (Burton & LaVoi, 2016).

In discussing the time investment required to be a high-level sport coach, Ronkainen, Sleeman and Richardson (2020, p322) refer to the role as a "life project", with the commitment often coming at the expense of other responsibilities and interests. Although this commitment is not specific to women, there is evidence that they find the 'trade-off' particularly difficult. In studies of established female coaches, it is common to hear of feelings of guilt where they have had to take time away from their families to fulfil their coaching role (Leberman and Palmer, 2009; Norman, 2014). These feelings of guilt are likely to stem from 'emphasised femininity' (Connell, 1987), the historical confirmation of women to accommodating men's interests and desires. As women are traditionally viewed as care givers there remains a view by many that their place very much remains in the home (Stick, 2017).

This view that a woman's place is in the home comes from gendered stereotypes that continue to prevail across society, where there remains incongruence between the qualities deemed as necessary for successful leadership, and those generally attributed to women (Heilman, 2012; Leitch & Stead, 2016; Marvin & Grandy, 2016). Once piece of research that

begins to show the flaws in these stereotypes is the Harvard Business Review study which found that women scored higher than men in 17 of the 19 'key leadership capabilities' (Zenger & Folkman, 2019).

A commonly cited reason for the continuance of these gendered stereotypes is that, through fear of losing power and privileges, dominant groups continue to enforce their stereotypes on non-dominant groups (De Haan & Norman, 2020). As football has long been considered a masculine activity (Siegele, Smith & Hardin, 2019), it could be posited that the dominant group (in this case, men) are unwilling to break down these stereotypes in case it loses them the power that they are accustomed to. There is some evidence that stereotypical gender roles are becoming blurred – due in part to the postmodern feminist movement, and other theories suggesting a move away from the gender binary – however the continuing imbalance in leadership roles suggests work remains to be done.

This male dominance in football has been acknowledged by those in positions of power, and policies have been created to address it (e.g. Accelerate Our Game (SFA, 2020a), Time for Action (UEFA, 2019a)), however targets set by these organisations vary in their specificity and likely impact. For example, where UEFA state they will double female representation on all UEFA bodies by 2024 (UEFA, 2019a) – an ambitious measurable target – the SFA more cautiously state that they will “empower female leadership across all levels of the game” (SFA, 2020a), with no specific target, or timescale, set.

Until equity is achieved – therefore changing the public face of the organisation (Ely & Meyerson, 2000) – it is difficult to see these stereotypes abating. This is especially true as research shows that the organisations charged with creating inclusive policies are serving to reinforce stereotypes through the gender balance of their own workforces, and more specifically in the roles in which they employ women. For example, in the FA National Centre, although women are visible employees, they are vastly outnumbered by men in leadership positions (Sawiuk, Lewis & Taylor, 2021). Similarly, although one third of US collegiate athletic department employees are women (Lapchick, 2018), the majority are employed in service or administrative roles; very few holding coaching or leadership positions.

A general lack of jobs available to women has been highlighted as a key barrier in many studies of female sport coaches (Walker & Bopp, 2011; Fasting, Sand & Knorre, 2013; Norman, 2013; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019). Women have reported lack of opportunities both in initially entering the profession, and as they attempt to progress to higher levels, with those who do embark on a coaching career often 'shunted' into less important roles (Walker and Bopp, 2011; Clarkson, Cox & Thelwell, 2019). In their interviews with female grassroots coaches, Murray, Lord and Lorimer (2020) identified disparities in the types of position and level of performance squad that the women had access to, regardless of their level of qualification.

It is apparent that, especially in high performance sport, women are often seen as outsiders, resulting in them being overlooked during recruitment and promotion (LaFontaine and Kamphoff, 2016; Norman, Rankin-Wright, & Allison, 2018), with recruitment strategies often consisting of informal invitations and assumed leadership (Ronkainen, Sleeman & Richardson, 2020). Fasting, Sand and Nordstrand's (2019) study highlighted the commonality of headhunting through male dominated networks, limiting the opportunities for women at elite levels in football. Darwin, Taylor and Wells (2019) also found that this was the case with recruitment of assistant coaches in the NCAA, therefore limiting the number of women who would be in a position to step up to head coach in the future.

A recent study of elite football in England investigated the recruitment strategies employed by clubs, through semi-structured interviews with 25 Sporting Directors, across the top two divisions (Parnell et al., 2021). These interviews provide evidence of Sporting Directors hiring people they already know, and those like themselves, limiting opportunities for 'outsiders'. In conclusion they suggest "trust and knowing people" (p13) are at the forefront in recruitment decision making, which may explain some of the inequalities that impact the game (such as gender and race). Although their study did not investigate the consequences of this, the authors suggest there are likely negative consequences both on and off the field. Parnell and colleagues' (2021) study focused on the men's game, but it is likely the findings are relevant to the women's game also, and worthy of further study as we strive to encourage more female players to consider coaching as a career.

It is not only in sport that lack of opportunity for women prevails. Research in various fields has found evidence of this ‘homologous reproduction’ (Kanter, 1977), where people in positions of power tend to hire others similar to themselves (Stangl and Kane, 1991; Lovett and Lowry, 1994; Schlesinger and Weigelt-Schlesinger, 2012). Kanter introduced this concept in 1977, explaining how a dominant group in society strive to guard power and privilege through reproducing themselves in their own image. A recent study by Darvin and Lubke (2021) found less evidence of homologous reproduction in the hiring of assistant coaches in the NCAA than in the past, but there did remain a real gender disparity. Interestingly, they found that female head coaches were more likely than men to engage in the practice.

This finding conflicts with postmodern feminist values, where equity is the aim rather than female dominance (Bierema & Cseh, 2003; McAfee & Howard, 2009). Darvin and Lubke’s (2021) findings differ from many others across Europe however, where the majority of sporting directors are men (Graham et al., 2013; Fielding-Lloyd & Mean, 2016; Sanderson & Gramlich, 2016), and homologous reproduction of hegemonic masculinity continues. Anstiss (2021) makes an interesting point about this as she references FIFA, where at surface level great progress seems to have been made. Quotas have been introduced to address the gender imbalance, but Moya Dodd – a former FIFA Council member – questioned whether this had led to women’s voices being truly heard. She explained that although women were being appointed, they were being appointed by the same people who voted for “all the men”. Dodd explained that had women been asked, they were likely to have made different selections, “but they’re not asked” (Dodd, cited in Anstiss, 2021, p 177).

An earlier report by Women in Sport (2015, p12) also criticised quotas, suggesting that, although they may increase representation at board level, the “trickle down” effects such as executive representation remained unaddressed. Interviewees in this study echoed concerns of Welford (2011) in response to being ‘tokens’, rather than positioned on merit. This ‘tokenism’ has been discussed in further studies (e.g. Larsen, 2016; Clarkson, Cox & Thelwell, 2019; Drury et al, 2021) with women feeling under pressure to ‘overperform’ to justify their position.

As highlighted earlier, women are more likely to be employed in the women’s game and this brings with it additional challenges in relation to the opportunities available for a full-time

career in the field, even at national level. With limited professionalisation of the women's game, Norman (2013) found it was not uncommon for female coaches to take on additional roles, such as administration and preparation of kit; a result of the lack of prestige given to their sport. This difference in status remained evident in Knoppers and colleagues (2021) study where a national level football coach explained how coaching the women's national 'A' team did not count as a high enough standard for entry to a licenced course, instead she had to gain experience with a young men's team.

Lack of opportunities in male teams has generally been a key influencer in the overall prospects for women in coaching, however it is becoming apparent that the increased stature of the women's game may now be indirectly reducing opportunities for female coaches to coach at the highest level, in the arena where they hitherto found it easier to access. In football a key 'symbol of success' (Ely & Meyerson, 2000) for a coach is working with players at the highest level. As the women's game has become fully professional in England, it is now more desirable as a career for both genders.

In exploring the experiences of football coaches in England, Ronkainen, Sleeman and Richardson (2020) found that both women and men considered opportunities to work with elite players to be better in the women's game. The authors suggest ambitious young men were now more frequently entering the elite women's game, as they saw it as a 'fast track' to higher levels. In doing this, opportunities for women are further limited, mirroring what happened in America with the passing of Title IX. Described above, evidence shows that men became more likely to coach female college teams upon the introduction of this law, which made the roles more financially rewarding – and thus higher status (Acosta & Carpenter, 2014). However, as Burton (2015) reiterates, although across the globe it is now more common for males to coach female teams, it remains very rare for the reverse to happen.

Related to this, it could be argued that the biggest barrier to women in sport coaching, is the male dominated environment in which it exists (Keats, 2016; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019; Murray, Lord & Lorimer, 2020; Sisjord, Fasting & Sand, 2021). It is widely understood that sport has historically been a masculine activity (Hargreaves, 1994; Birrell, 2000; Coakley, 2004; Norman, 2014), and elite football is a prime example of one in which traditional hierarchies, and overly competitive cultures, continue to dominate (Ronkiainen, Sleeman &

Richardson, 2020). This competitive culture is often aligned with masculinity although, through their sporting endeavours, female athletes are now showing that this genderisation is inappropriate.

In a recent study of women attending a football coaching course in England, Sawiuk, Lewis and Taylor (2021) concluded that masculinity in football continued to be reinforced through the male 'voices' by which the courses were delivered. Female candidates highlighted references to 'the game' as being related specifically to the male game, and coaching sessions deemed successful by coach educators as characterised by traditional masculine traits. This masculine influence throughout the course led to a conflict between the women's inherent characters, and what they felt was required to pass the course. This conflict has been highlighted in previous research into women's experiences of coach education (e.g. Welford, 2011, Chapman et al., 2020), with women in agreement that they feel under pressure to adopt a masculine style to be accepted and / or to be successful.

Through the dominance of traditional masculinity, the football environment has previously been described as "harsh and hostile" (Norman, 2010, p512); one where language, policies and practices create an unequal order of gender relations (Shaw and Slack, 2002). This environment is one where 'hegemonic masculinity' (Kessler et al., 1982; Connell, 2005) prevails (Siegele, Smith & Hardin, 2019; Murray, Lord & Lorimer, 2020). Although it is possible for women to challenge this male dominance, Sawiuk, Lewis and Taylor (2021) found that there was a general reluctance among candidates on coaching courses to do this, for fear that their views would be dismissed and / or that they would be portrayed as troublemakers.

Women may also choose not to challenge this male culture through lack of confidence in their leadership abilities (Norman, 2014; Women in Sport, 2016; Anstiss, 2021), or belief that masculine traits are required for successful leadership (Koenig et al., 2011). Furthermore, where most literature focuses on the more direct impacts of male hegemony, Murray, Lord and Lorimer (2020) add that it can also bring about forms of competitiveness among women as they strive to advance their careers. Leberman and Burton (2017) refer to this as the 'queen bee syndrome' where females in leadership roles fail to nurture those who would benefit from their mentorship. This is a more indirect effect, but one which equally may limit the quality and quantity of female coaches progressing in the game.

Another barrier – which appears less prevalent in women’s football than men’s, but an issue nonetheless – is that of homophobia. An early study by Griffin (1992) discussed negative attitudes towards lesbianism in football, stressing that the barrier was not only an issue for lesbians, as “all women in sport are victimized by the use of the lesbian label to intimidate and control” (p258). This finding is supported by more recent studies by Gledhill and Harwood (2015) and Magrath (2016) who iterate that the label of lesbian – often in a derogatory manner – is widespread in women’s sport. Norman’s (2014) study of female football coaches in the UK discussed negative stereotypes and homophobia encountered by national team coaches, with these women explaining how they, and female athletes, often felt pressured to demonstrate overt signs of femininity to compensate for their athletic ability. This study followed an earlier one by Norman (2013) in which she found that lesbian coaches generally felt undervalued, and some even believed that parents considered them to be sexual predators; assumptions that were not made about their heterosexual male coach counterparts (Norman, 2013).

Where quantitative data has been gathered, instances of homophobia have been identified throughout Europe; a recent statistic provided by the professional players’ union (FIFPro) showed that 63% of female players in Europe had experienced homophobia on match days (FIFPro, 2017). Another – albeit more dated – study by sportscotland found that gender stereotypes, and ingrained perceptions of masculinity and femininity found in sport served to promote homophobia in Scotland (Brackenridge et al., 2008). Anstiss (2021) discusses homophobia as a barrier to coaching. She suggests it appears to be less obviously an issue for women in Europe, although perhaps it is more of an “unspoken barrier” (p214). She does, however, provide some stories about indirect and direct discrimination of gay female coaches in America, clearly limiting women’s progression in the role.

In addition to the external barriers discussed above, research has highlighted a number of internal barriers that may be impacting upon women’s entry and progression in sport coaching. A recurring theme is that of confidence among female coaches (Norman, 2013; Norman, 2014; Clarkson, Cox & Thelwell, 2019; Fasting, Sand and Nordstrand, 2019; Kentta et al, 2020). In the most recent UK Coaching study this lack of confidence was apparent; with 78% of the male coaches feeling confident delivering activities, compared to 67% of female

coaches (Thompson, Whitaker and Bunyan, 2020). It is important to note these figures refer to those who are currently coaching, therefore they do not provide detail about the women whose lack of self-confidence has led them to fail to enter, or to leave the coaching workforce. Burton and LaVoi (2016) also reported that female sport coaches were likely to have lower confidence than their male counterparts, their evidence suggesting this disparity is a result of gendered stereotypes within their sport.

Findings of LaVoi and Dutove's (2012) review of literature show that it is common for female coaches to feel underqualified for high level coaching positions, even when their 'coaching capital' suggested otherwise. For the purposes of this research, capital refers to the assets one possesses, i.e. qualifications, technical and tactical knowledge, and prior experiences as athletes and coaches. This is in line with Bourdieu's (1986) definition which describes capital as a form of power. Tomlinson (2004) suggests the degree of capital one has available will impact the amount of control they have over themselves and others. This coaching capital can also be related to Putnam's (2004) notion of bonding and bridging forms. Through gathering qualifications and experiences, women will reap the benefits of bonding capital that strengthen their mutual relations, while bridging capital may allow them to become part of wider coaching circles.

Fasting, Sand and Nordstrand (2019) undertook a large-scale study, interviewing forty elite female football coaches, although results of only five were published due to journal restrictions. These interviews found that the female coaches all agreed that self-confidence was an issue within their field. One of the coaches illustrated the point when she said that it was common for men to think, "I can manage 10% of this, so therefore I can do it," whereas a woman is more likely to think, "I can only manage 90% of this, so therefore I can't do it" (p9). This supports earlier studies (Kamphoff, Armentrout & Driska, 2010; Norman, 2010; Blom et al., 2011) that also report female coaches feeling the need to be accomplished athletes and / or coaches in order to be respected.

This inclination of women to downplay their abilities has been reported in many studies of female sport coaches' experiences and perceptions (e.g. Walker & Bopp, 2011; Fielding-Lloyd & Mean, 2016; Clarkson, Cox & Thelwell, 2019), however it is important to note that, as discussed above with postmodern feminism, men and women should not be divided into two

distinct groups. Not all men are over-confident, and there are women who have high self-esteem in the coaching environment, evidence that one's assigned gender does not specify how they behave, and the characteristics they develop through socialisation. Nevertheless, the nature of football in this country limits the visibility of such personas, a challenge to both feminists, and those promoting inclusive masculinity (e.g. Anderson & McCormack, 2016).

Inclusive masculinity Theory (IMT) was introduced by Anderson in 2009 to understand the changing relationship between young men and their masculinities (Anderson & McCormack, 2016). The theory was an inductive one, developing through ethnographic research that found a changing social and cultural landscape brought about more inclusive – namely, less homophobic – forms of masculinity (Anderson, 2009). Anderson (2009, p7) referred to “homophobia”, that is, “the fear of being homosexualised”, and how decreasing instances of this allowed men to develop “softer, more expressive and tactile forms of masculinity” (O'Neill, 2015). This theory will be discussed further in the following section. More recently, Anstiss (2021) supports the importance of a move away from hegemonic masculinity in sport, not only for women. She notes that a move towards more inclusive masculinities (and femininities) would also benefit boys' and men's mental health as, through the promotion of strong women, they may feel less pressure to always be the 'leader'.

2.4 Inclusive / Multiple Masculinities

In proposing his theory of 'inclusive masculinity' Anderson (2009) suggests that in modern society men are more able to show traditional feminine traits, findings later echoed by Roberts (2013) in his interviews with young men in England. Although football is widely considered the epitome of masculinity (Magrath, 2016; Goldblatt, 2014) there are growing instances of male footballers showing less traditionally masculine traits, something Magrath (2016; p ix) deems “metrosexuality”, or the “softening” of masculinity. This is in line with the theory of 'multiple masculinities', a term introduced by Carrigan, Connell, and Lee (1985) in their critique of the 'multiple hierarchies' identified in Kessler and colleagues' (1982) study of social inequality in Australian high schools.

There is increasing evidence that traditional gendered stereotypes are outdated, with studies finding multiple masculinities and femininities apparent in society (Ashe, 2007; Murray &

White, 2017; Pettersson, 2018; Fernandez-Lasa et al., 2020). In critiquing hegemonic masculinity, Connell and Messerschmidt (2005, p832) point out that male dominance should not always be assumed to be “normal” (i.e. seen in the majority in all situations), but that it is certainly “normative”, as seems to be the case in football.

Although this move away from the dichotomies of male and female, and masculinity and femininity, is apparent in recent literature, there remains some evidence that, in practice, it is not always the case, with ‘sissiness’ (the display of traditional feminine attributes (Poole, 2014)) often resulting in teasing at school (Messerschmidt 2000; Kimmel & Mahler 2003), and any non ‘macho’ behaviour in sport leading to homophobic abuse (Magrath, 2016). Recent evidence suggests a greater acceptance of feminine traits in men (Anderson & McCormack, 2016), however these authors do suggest it is not yet the ‘norm’ to be so accepting. It is likely that this linking of sport with traditional masculine traits will continue to inhibit men’s display of ‘non-macho’ characteristics, doing little to challenge the male hegemonic nature, especially in those sports traditionally considered to be more masculine. Furthermore, although it seems to be becoming more acceptable for men to ‘blur the lines’ of femininity and masculinity (Anderson, 2009), there does not appear to be the same freedom for women who are considered a ‘tomboy’ or even a ‘bitch’ when they show more traditional masculine characteristics in their coaching (Smith et al, 2019).

This concept of multiple masculinities (Ricciardelli, Clow & White, 2010; Atkinson, 2011) can be related to many feminist theories in that characteristics are not specifically linked to a particular gender or orientation (e.g. liberal feminism proposes that differences between men and women are a result of socialisation and opportunities, and poststructuralist feminism infers that all experiences are constructed by society in line with the dominant discourse). Magrath (2016) discusses masculinity as being context specific and this is perhaps more appropriate than the matching of a trait to a gender. Similarly, Ely and Meyerson (2000, p114) explain how one should view gender as “neither static nor universal; its meaning and consequences are socially constructed”.

In their critique of masculinity Connell and Messerschmidt (2005, p836) agree that the problem of framing of masculinity within a “heteronormative conception” of gender does not account for ‘within-gender’ differences. As sport is highlighted as an arena where

heteronormativity is reinforced (Connell, 2005; Goldblatt, 2014; Magrath, 2016) this may be key to women's progression in coaching, as they feel a requirement to contest the notion of emphasised femininity (i.e. fragility, care giver, etc.) if they are to be successful (Murray, Lord & Lorimer, 2020). Instead, they are required to show physical strength, toughness, competitiveness and rationality (Schwalbe, 2015); key constructs of masculinity. These traits, however, are arguably key characteristics of any athlete – male or female – again adding backing to the push for contextualisation of characteristics above genderisation.

2.5 Experiences of Female Coaches

Where studies have sought to explore the experiences of female sports coaches, they have generally focused on the minority who have had a successful career (e.g. Fasting, Sand and Nordstrand, 2019; Knoppers et al., 2021), perhaps leading to 'survivorship bias' (Smith, 2014). Survivorship bias is a term used to describe sampling errors that can occur in research, where those who have not 'made it' are omitted, thus skewing results. The term was first used by Wald, a scholar who was tasked with researching damage to fighter aircraft. Wald pointed out that there was little to be gained from reinforcing the planes that had survived, as those that had been shot down would provide more useful data (Powell, Ingram & Broughton, 2016).

Looking at the general coaching landscape, it has been widely reported that women tend to coach less prestigious, and more 'feminine', sports (Reade, Rogers & Norman, 2009; Fasting, Sand & Knorre, 2013; Thompson, Whitaker & Bunyan, 2020), usually holding positions of little authority (Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2017). Where female football coaches have been studied specifically, they generally report largely negative experiences, especially at the earlier stages of their careers, with key reasons including lack of respect (Walker & Bopp, 2011; LaFontaine and Kamphoff, 2016; Norman, Rankin-Wright & Allison, 2018), cultural disapproval / hostility (Norman, 2014), a demeaning environment (Kerr & Banwell, 2014), tokenism (Kamphoff, Armentrout & Driska, 2010; Women in Sport, 2015), isolation (Murray, Lord & Lorimer, 2020), and lack of support (Norman, 2014; Clarkson, Cox & Thelwell, 2019).

Many of these issues are very much in line with those presented earlier as barriers to female sport coaches, showing that these do not disappear; rather that some women choose to, and

/ or are able to, overcome them. Furthermore, these coaches who have succeeded in overcoming barriers to progress to high-level coaching, reported having a “longer journey” than that of their male counterparts (Sisjord, Fasting & Sand, 2021). Sisjord, Fasting and Sand relate this journey to a “labyrinth” (Eagly & Carli, 2007, p1) that women must navigate, relating it to the androcentric principle (Bourdieu, 2001), where masculine domination is legitimised, activities are distributed according to gender, and women are considered outsiders. Furthermore, Norman (2008) introduced the ‘bottleneck’ metaphor, illustrating the flawed pathways and limited opportunities that exclude more and more women from positions of power as they advance in their sport. Through interviews with elite coaches in the UK, Norman (2008, p455) found that “the higher the women climb, the more constricted the pathways and opportunities become”, allowing only a few to ‘pass through’ and make it to the top of their profession.

In their critique, Burton and LaVoi (2016) add to the disapproval of traditional feminist theories which suggest a need to ‘fix the women’ to reduce inequality, rather than striving for a more equitable society. Anstiss (2021) also criticises this fix the women narrative, arguing that as long as they can continue to question the women in a system, men do not need to question the system itself, thus neglecting to consider that they may in fact be part of the problem. This further explains how gender stereotypes continue to promote men as the public face of the sporting system, marginalising women and impacting upon their ability to enter and progress in elite football.

Where women have successfully negotiated the coaching ladder to work at an elite level, it is apparent from their perceptions that they are not respected as highly as male coaches (Manley et al., 2010; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019). It is noteworthy that this feeling is not only in relation to coaching male athletes. For example, Knoppers and colleagues (2021) back up previous studies by Harris (2005) and Kristiansen, Broch and Pedersen (2014), who found that professional female footballers also showed a preference for a male coach. Interestingly therefore, Siegele, Smith and Hardin (2019) found male athletes’ perceptions of their female coach were not impacted by her gender, rather by accomplishments and leadership qualities. This shows a lack of direct discrimination, but it could be argued that these leadership qualities rated by the male athletes are those often attributed to men,

perhaps making it more difficult for women to portray them without fitting in with the fix the women ideology.

It seems Siegele, Smith and Hardin (2019) may agree with this critique, as they felt that despite the athletes generally dismissing stereotypes – stating that they did not believe that masculine qualities were required by a head coach – incidences of marginalisation and discrimination were visible. Furthermore, where women did show more traditional masculine qualities, perhaps in an effort to fit in, there were signs that the male athletes looked negatively upon them.

This negative assumption of the coach's character is an example of how a mismatch between traditional leadership qualities and stereotypical female traits can make it difficult for women to achieve acceptance. A need to comply with the dominant discourse is discussed in other similar studies (e.g. Smith et al, 2019; Knoppers et al, 2021). There is some evidence that women may be starting to show more confidence in challenging the norm, however. For example, in Knoppers and colleagues' (2021) study, some female football coaches explained that, although a level of compliance was required to gain employment at the highest level, they did go on to create an "alternative discourse" (p14) that celebrates, rather than ignores, women's football.

Although women have reported negative experiences as sport coaches, there are some studies that show more positive ones, again the majority of these focusing on established coaches. Supporting earlier research by Blom and colleagues (2011), LaFontaine and Kamphoff's (2016) study of female coaches of male athletes provides interesting results. From their interviews it was apparent that most coaches felt that they were supported by their athletic directors, parents and peers. However, it must be noted that for many it took some time to develop the respect, supporting the labyrinth (Burton & LaVoi, 2016) metaphor discussed previously. Furthermore, some women felt that the level of respect their position deserved was never truly achieved.

The coaches in LaFontaine and Kamphoff's (2016) study were all highly qualified, and working in male sport, meaning they were likely to have proved themselves to be competent coaches, perhaps making them unrepresentative of the many women who struggle to enter

/ progress in football (again resulting in arguably 'survivorship biased' results). Another recent study (Murray, Lord & Lorimer, 2020) investigated a slightly different demographic, but found similar results, in that grassroots coaches in England struggled to gain the respect they deserved. Like those discussed above, these coaches discussed how they felt they had to exhibit masculine characteristics to gain the respect of their athletes.

In line with LaFountaine and Kamphoff's (2016) findings, others have reported positive experiences of sport coaches who are working at higher performance levels (Norman, 2014; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019), suggesting that as female coaches 'prove' themselves, they experience less direct discrimination. However, the high-level coaches included in these studies explain that although they feel respected in their current positions, they have generally had to overcome barriers to get to this point, which may begin to explain why many women fail to progress to higher levels from early coaching experiences.

Overall, there is a general consensus that female sport coaches see their environment as dominated by men and masculine practices, and that this has led to a longer, more difficult journey, to high levels (e.g Lewis, Roberts & Andrews, 2018; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019). Fasting, Sand and Nordstrand (2019) found female coaches considered the men who dominated the sport to overvalue their capital, whilst the women undervalued theirs. This need to overcompensate for being a woman has been highlighted before in interviews with female coaches (Walker and Bopp, 2011; Fielding-Lloyd and Mean, 2016; Clarkson, Cox and Thelwell, 2019). Moreover, in an online sport news column, a previous manager of Manchester United Women stated that when attending coaching courses, she has to "spend the week earning respect, whereas a man gets it automatically" (Stoney, 2019).

Related to the theoretical framework, Foucault's work can help to explain these experiences. Foucault discusses the relationship between power and knowledge, and how those in positions of power decide what knowledge is, and claim to be most knowledgeable, therefore continuing to hold positions of power (Foucault, 1983). The experiences described above suggest that women who coach feel secondary, and less knowledgeable, than their male counterparts; likely a result of the male dominated environment in which they work. Similarly, in his work about 'madness and civilization', in which he discusses how 'normality' is defined, Foucault (1965) explains how one defines normal through the abnormal. He

suggests that although society excludes the abnormal, it incessantly studies them, and this is what leads to the power relations in a society. To relate this to the current situation in football, once normality has been established (the masculine nature of the game) it is those who exhibit normality who have the power over the 'abnormal' (i.e. the women).

This section shows how deep-rooted stereotypical beliefs continue to impact women's experiences, even where they are equally, or even more, qualified and experienced than their male counterparts. With this in mind, the current research will seek to explore where these stereotypes have already impacted upon current players' experiences, and how these women perceive they can be addressed to promote more equal opportunities in future.

2.6 Coach Education

To progress in coaching, one must work through a number of coach education courses, however some research suggests that the nature of these courses could be enough to put some women off working beyond grassroots levels. In studying female coaches taking part in the UEFA A-licence course – required to work at the highest level – in England, Sawiuk, Lewis and Taylor (2021) found that educators showed a lack of knowledge about, and gave little merit to, the women's game. Elite coaches in Knoppers and colleagues' (2021) study discussed how it was always men who were employed as coach educators, and videos that were used as examples to support content only included men's teams. Knoppers and colleagues' (2021) study investigated the experiences of national team managers from across the globe, showing that these issues are widespread. Although UEFA (2019) figures show an increasing number of women gaining qualifications, the gender gap remains, and female coaches continue to be in a minority, increasingly so as they progress beyond grassroots (UEFA, 2019a). This minority status can lead women to feel that they do not belong, especially as they progress to higher levels (Lewis, Roberts and Andrews, 2018; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019; Sawiuk, Lewis & Taylor, 2021).

One reason posited for this feeling of isolation is the sexist and bigoted cultures in which high-level coach education courses reside (Lewis, Roberts and Andrews, 2018; Norman, Rankin-Wright & Allison, 2018; Clarkson, Cox & Thelwell, 2019; Sawiuk, Lewis & Taylor 2021). Sawiuk, Lewis and Taylor (2021, p15) suggest that the UEFA A licence is "delivered by men for the

consumption of men and reproduced by men". This hegemonic reproduction results in a "society of normalisation" (Foucault, 1980; p107) in which the term football seems to refer only to the male game. This androcentric environment is often created through the use of language, such as male nouns, swearing and derogatory female categorisation (Sawuik, Lewis & Taylor, 2021). This is key to understanding the phenomenon from a postmodern feminist viewpoint, as Hansen (2006) explains, the narratives constructed by a group provide a valuable insight into their thoughts and actions.

These feelings of isolation and exclusion lead some women to drop out of the profession, where others find coping mechanisms – such as displaying masculine qualities – to gain acceptance (Fielding-Lloyd and Mean, 2008). Sawuik, Lewis and Taylor's (2021) research explored the experiences of women who had recently undertaken the UEFA A licence, suggesting that the way coaching is "conceptualised, debated and defined" by coach educators serves to reinforce the hegemonic nature of football. This was backed up by Knoppers and colleagues (2021) in their study of elite national team coaches. Examples of practices that – perhaps indirectly – marginalised women included using only male players to demonstrate / practice sessions with, linking tasks specifically to the male game, and providing uniforms that are made for the male physique which were often unsuitable for the female coaches.

As discussed above, it is common for female football coaches to feel they need to work much harder, and perform at a higher level, than their male peers, just to be accepted (Walker and Bopp, 2011; Schlesinger and Weigelt-Schlesinger, 2012). As well as in the job itself, Lewis, Roberts and Andrews (2018) found that this was common in coach education in England. Through interviewing ten elite coaches the authors found that abusive, derogatory and sexist language was common on FA courses, and the coaches discussed the emphasis placed by educators on traditional male characteristics such as aggression and dominance. This, again, is evidence of indirect discrimination where the nature of the assessment is often in conflict with (what society tends to judge as) a woman's nature, and not necessarily conducive to good practice, as will be discussed below.

Similar findings have been published by Welford (2011) and Chapman and colleagues (2020), with female coaches discussing the pressure they felt to adopt a masculine way of coaching

to pass the course. In critiquing this evidence however, it could be argued that this is not necessarily discriminatory against women per se, as the postmodern feminist would argue that aggression and dominance should not only be attributed to men; some women showing these traits, while not all men necessarily do (as discussed in section 2.4 – Inclusive / Multiple Masculinities).

In addition to the practices identified above, Sawiuk, Lewis and Taylor (2021, p7) also highlighted the impact of language on women's experiences of coach education; telling us that "its use and misuse, intent and effect, is difficult to overstate". Several of the coaches explained that they felt verbally under attack, forced to answer questions in a particular way, to justify their inclusion on the course. Furthermore, in addition to the masculine nature of communication of the course content itself, sexist language further prevailed during downtime. One coach described her embarrassment and awkwardness during a rare visit to the bar where men were discussing sexual encounters. This experience led to her avoiding these situations in future, thus becoming increasingly isolated (Sawiuk, Lewis & Taylor, 2021). Other coaches discussed similar awkwardness, explaining there were two ways to deal with it: try to join in (thus reinforcing the behaviour), or stay away (and secure the bar as a male space, again reinforcing gender stereotypes).

Although male dominance in football coach education has been found to be restrictive to women, it is likely caused, at least partially, by the shortage of available female coach educators. Recent figures show that only three per cent of coaches who are qualified to the standard required to become educators are women (UEFA, 2017). Norman, Rankin-Wright and Allison (2018) also highlighted the problem of a lack of appropriately qualified female coaches, especially at higher levels. Their data show that the number of female coach educators in England progressing through the pathway dropped from 40 qualified to educate at level one, through to one qualified to educate at level four (UEFA A-licence).

With reference to the postmodern feminists' focus on intersectionality, all of the coaches in Norman, Rankin-Wright and Allison's (2018) study acknowledged the lack of diversity – not just related to gender – in the coach educators they encountered. Some of the coaches in Sawiuk, Lewis and Taylor's (2021) study felt that the complete ignoring of the women's game was demotivating. Although they did not necessarily want a female specific course, they felt

that there should be a better balance on gender-neutral courses, as the UEFA A Licence is a prerequisite for coaching at a high level in either gender (therefore it should prepare candidates for both environments). These coaches stated that there was no reference at all to the women's game, with all examples based around male elite football; unlikely to fully transfer to the women's game in which these female coaches were likely aspiring to work in, and which some men may inadvertently end up working in as a route to higher level competition.

In addition to including the women's game in generic UEFA courses, it has been suggested that it may be beneficial to continue to offer female-only courses. One of the coaches in Sawiuk, Lewis and Taylor's (2021) study, who had attended one of these, highlighted the impact of having a tutor that she was able to talk to, giving her the support that many others (with male tutors) did not have. This finding was mirrored in Sisjord, Fasting and Sand's (2021, p13) study where many of the female coaches highlighted the "women-only community" as a positive learning environment where they were able to fully participate. A common feeling can be summed up with the following statement from one coach, "when you are a lone woman in a group of 30 men, and even if you are better than them, you tend to hold back, often, unless you have lots of self-confidence".

There are some criticisms of these female-only courses, however. Due to the dearth in suitably qualified women, it is common for these courses – including my own experience of this – to be led by male tutors. Also, although some women have shown a preference for female-only courses (Fielding-Lloyd & Mean, 2016; Lewis, Roberts & Andrews, 2018; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019) others argue that they actually reinforce the stereotype that women must be treated differently (Fielding-Lloyd & Mean, 2008; Lewis, Roberts & Andrews, 2018; Norman, Rankin-Wright & Allison, 2018), against the postmodern feminist move away from the male / female dichotomy.

2.7 Implications of Increasing Female Representation in Coaching

Research is consistent in the reporting of a lack of female voice in sports coaching (e.g. Norman, 2012; Burton, 2015). Burton (2015) discusses the paucity of female representation resulting in the structural bias and discrimination that can serve as a limiter to women's

progression. Furthermore, Norman (2012) explains how male dominance at the top levels in elite sport has wide implications on all levels of participation and leadership. With men in key decision-making roles, sport provision continues to be influenced by masculine views, meaning the impact is noticeable not only at higher levels, but even in its ability to engage inactive females in the first place (Shlesinger & Weigelt-Shlesinger, 2012).

As well as being a voice for other women, considering their needs in policy making and practice, female athletes serve as role models to younger generations, leading more girls to take up the sport, and remain involved in it (Whisenant, 2008; Lyle, 2013). Among researchers and sports professionals there appears a general understanding that with female coaches visible as role models, future generations of girls and women may be encouraged to take part in sport and sustain their participation (Meier, 2015; Dunn, 2016; Ronkainen, Ryba & Selanne, 2019). This is important for general health as well as for the advancement of the sport.

Female role models in sport have historically been sparse and, despite women breaking down barriers in their participation and achievements, media coverage continues to lag behind that of males (Cooky, Messner & Hextrum, 2013; Bruce & Hardin, 2014; Hall & Oglesby, 2016), doing little to change the perception of sport as a male institute. Through increasing female representation at the highest level, the perception of sport as a safe and acceptable domain for women and girls may be created (Marshall, Demers & Sharp, 2010; Moran-Miller & Flores, 2011; Kidd, 2013). Although the benefits of role models, in relation to participation, are widely documented, the lack of these role models has been highlighted in many studies as a key barrier to women progressing as sport coaches (Avery, Tonidandel & Phillips, 2008; Burton & LaVoi, 2016; Taylor & Hardin, 2016; Sisjord, Fasting & Sand, 2021).

Through challenging the masculine perception of football – or the public face of the organisation (Ely & Meyerson, 2000) – with increasing female representation in leadership positions, girls' general self-esteem can be increased (Kerr, Banwell & Stirling, 2021). As discussed above self-esteem has been identified as a barrier to women in coaching, therefore by increasing the number of female coaches in the game, other prospective coaches may feel more confident in taking on the role themselves. In addition, Norman's (2013) study highlighted the importance of promoting female coaches to show that the profession is

“valued, worthwhile and accessible” for women, explaining that through increasing the visibility of female national team coaches, others may be inspired to follow suit.

Where other male-dominated fields have been studied (e.g. airline pilots, (Germain, Herzog & Hamilton, 2012)), same-sex role models have been shown to have a positive influence on women’s decisions to work in these professions (Greene & Stitt-Gohdes, 1997; Lockwood, 2006). Sport studies have also found a positive relationship between female athletes’ exposure to female coaches, and their interest and aspirations in the coaching profession (Lirgg, Dibrezzo & Smith, 1994, Everhart & Chelladurai, 1998; Demers & Audet, 2007; LaVoi, 2016). The phrase, “if you can’t see it, you can’t be it” (Murray, 2017; Anstiss, 2021) is being increasingly heard from those who seek to challenge hegemony in all its forms (not just the male domination of football). In her book about female football coaches around the world, LaVoi (2016) proposes that through seeing women in coaching positions, other young women will be more inclined to think of the role as a worthwhile, feasible, career.

This proposition supports that by Demers and Audet (2007) who found that novice female coaches cited the significant impact of their own female coaches upon their decision to coach. More recent studies into the effects of a female role model for aspiring coaches are sparse, however one which used both qualitative and quantitative methods with a large group of female sport students discovered that 86% who were coached by a woman had future coaching intentions, compared with 69% of those coached by a man. Furthermore, those who had the strongest intention (90%) had also gained coaching experience while being coached by a woman, perhaps suggesting that experienced coaches could act as mentors for those who are still competing (Fasting, Sand & Knorre, 2013).

The wider effects of this lack of role models have been studied in a range of environments. In line with much of the sporting literature, Pettersson (2018, p109) found that inflexible work hours, and “men supporting men”, were key factors inhibiting the progression of female physicists. Similarly, Germain, Herzog and Hamilton (2012) found that misogynistic behaviours were common in the airline industry, and a lack of role models contributed to a sense of isolation in trainee pilots. An interesting article by Ward (2008) – where an investigation into law, engineering and medicine drew many parallels with women’s football – identified a presumption of less competence, societal views, lack of respect, and the ‘glass

ceiling' effect (Williams, 1992) in limiting the progression of females in their respective professions. These findings provide further evidence of the wider benefits to society in using female role models to break down the gendered stereotypes that exist, not only in relation to football.

The Head of the Women's Game at the FA pondered, "If we can change attitudes to women and girls playing football, I wonder if we can change people's attitudes to women in business, I wonder if we can change people's attitudes to the way they are in families, I wonder if we can change attitudes towards what's possible?" (Campbell, cited in Anstiss, 2021, p11).

Although the paucity of female coaches implicates upon sport in many ways, including general participation rates, and performances at national level, wider literature shows how a lack of visible female coaches may also reinforce the longstanding gendered perceptions of women's inferior status in society (Norman, 2014). Related to this, research has shown that improving the gender balance in coaching can lead to wider structural, cultural and social change in sport as a whole (Kerr & Marshall, 2007; LaVoi & Dutove, 2012), which may then further impact other areas of society. Research suggests that the marginalisation of female leaders in sport is likely to be aiding the reproduction of wider social exclusions (Anderson, 2008; Saavedra, 2009). However, due to its popularity and widespread coverage, sport has been identified as a key site for challenging norms (Sage, 1990; Machida and Feltz, 2013; Anstiss, 2021), and could therefore be a place where some of these stereotypes are broken down for future generations.

Siegele, Smith and Hardin (2019) concluded that exposing young women to women in authoritative roles from an early age is likely to reduce the chance of them developing the prejudices that those without such exposure may hold. They recommend that youth athletes of both genders should be exposed to both male and female coaches from grassroots levels, to avoid gendered stereotypes developing as they progress throughout their career. Fink, LaVoi and Newhall (2016) also consider the importance of men being introduced to proficient female leaders to increase the respect they grant them. For this to happen there needs to be visible, competent leaders, and Helper and Feltz (2008) suggest that it is through showing proficiency in male-dominated fields that women can challenge the perception that they are incapable.

This notion has more recently been explored by LaFontaine and Kamphoff (2016), and Hancock, Darvin and Walker (2018), who found that aside from improving as athletes, through being coached by a woman, male athletes also learned to respect female leaders in general. This challenging of gendered stereotypes – through permeating the dominant ideologies of masculinity in sport – has also been suggested as having the potential to benefit other minority groups who have become marginalised in society (Norman, 2012), key to postmodern feminist thought.

2.8 Women as Coaches

As discussed above, numerous benefits of increasing female representation in coaching have been proposed. A key strength that women can bring to football is their ability to build positive group dynamics, to show fairness, and to effectively resolve conflict (Kerr & Marshall, 2007). The coach-athlete relationship has been cited as key to success in sport (Jowett & Cockerill, 2002; Jowett, 2003; Stewart, 2016); a positive relationship having the potential to increase an athlete's motivation, focus, concentration span and ability to cope with stress (Gearity & Murray, 2011; Appleton & Duda, 2016; Fry & Moore, 2019).

In coaching literature that explores experiences of female athletes, various studies have shown that although they share many attributes with their male counterparts, female athletes do need to be coached differently (Longshore & Sachs, 2015; Norman, 2016; Stewart, 2016; Walach-Bista, 2019; De Haan & Knoppers, 2020). While there is a perception that women lack the attributes required to coach sports (Manley et al., 2010; Norman, 2010; Norman, 2014; LaFontaine and Kamphoff, 2016), there is some evidence to suggest that some traditional female traits are preferred by both male and female athletes (Fasting & Pfister, 2000; Pensgaard and Roberts, 2002; Siegele, Smith & Hardin, 2019).

Male athletes in Siegele, Smith and Hardin's (2019) study did not have a preference when it came to the gender of their coach, stating that they valued both stereotypically masculine and feminine qualities; technical knowledge (masculine), communication and nurturing (feminine). As discussed before however, the aim of postmodern feminism, and Carrigan, Connell and Lee's (2005) theory of multiple masculinities, is to move away from these outdated stereotypes, judging one's ability on merit and not related to their given sex. The

athletes, in Siegele, Smith and Hardin's (2019) study, also commented on the ability of the female coaches to bring teams together, with one athlete going as far as to say that he did not think a male coach would be able to bring about the same level of cohesion, key to optimal team performance (Carron, 2012; Benson et al., 2016). Furthermore, many athletes – both male and female – have shown a preference for a coach who creates a caring and accepting climate (Fasting & Pfister, 2000; Pensgaard & Roberts, 2002; Newton et al., 2007), one which is generally associated with femininity (Merchant, 2012).

When asked, more female coaches than male cited the creation of a warm and welcoming environment as important, where men were more likely to mention getting good results (Thompson, Whitaker & Bunyon, 2020). Newton and colleagues (2007) defined this caring climate in sport as one in which an individual feels valued, leading to a positive environment for learning and performing. Anstiss (2021, p212) also highlights the benefits of a more “empathetic, supportive style of leadership ... that considers the wellbeing of the athlete beyond their performing lives”. In saying this she refers to a number of female athletes who have reported bullying from aggressive coaches whose attitude has been to win at all costs.

Murray, Lord and Lorimer's (2020) study found that female sport coaches were more likely to utilise this caring approach with their athletes, the authors going on to stress that the emergence of caring coaching philosophies – for both genders – should be capitalised on for the benefit of sport, rather than being looked upon as inferior. However, they also warn that a caring philosophy should not be misinterpreted, with the continued perception of femininity as being disadvantageous in sport, and thus likely to inhibit women's progression. Similarly, Anstiss (2021, p213) warns of the danger of assuming all women are “soft, caring and maternal”. She stresses that not all women are feminine in their approach, just as not all men are aggressive; further supporting theory of multiple masculinities (Carrigan, Connell and Lee, 1985), discussed earlier.

Communication is key to a positive coach-athlete relationship (Jowett, 2003) and in their interviews Fasting and Pfister (2000) found that women preferred a more feminine communication style, many believing that they were not taken seriously by male coaches. Merchant (2012) identified differences in the communication styles of men and women, with women being more “expressive, tentative and polite” and men more “assertive, and power

hungry” (p17). In exploring preferences of female footballers, Norman (2013) found the feminine style to be more popular. Furthermore, male athletes interviewed by Siegele, Smith and Hardin (2019) also commended their female coaches’ ability to communicate effectively and empathetically.

Jowett (2003) discusses the importance of ‘complementarity’ in a positive coach-athlete relationship and female athletes often find female coaches can relate better to them, although Frey and colleagues (2006) did point out that, although they had this greater complementarity, the women they interviewed did not show a preference for female coaches per se. In support of women as coaches, studies have shown that autocratic coaching is the style least preferred by both male and female athletes (Pensgaard & Roberts, 2002; Surujlal & Dhurup 2012); this autocratic style generally considered to be a masculine one (Frey et al., 2006; Eagly & Johannesen-Schmidt, 2007; Coakley & Pike, 2009; Merchant, 2012).

More specifically, there is some evidence that quality of coaching can be negatively impacted by a gender imbalance between a male coach and female athlete (MacKinnon, 2011; Norman & French, 2013; De Haan & Norman, 2020). To investigate both perspectives, De Haan and Norman (2020) interviewed elite female rowers, and their male coaches. Although the coaches stated explicitly that they did not approach coaching men and women differently, they all went on to discuss some differences; suggesting that they were not aware of their preconceptions.

As previous experiences of being coached are likely to impact upon the coaches’ behaviour (Jacobs, Claringbould & Knoppers, 2014), De Haan and Norman (2020) suggest that men coaching female athletes are likely to reproduce gendered discourses that were apparent during their careers as athletes. Furthermore, they concluded that the male coaches often communicated in a discriminatory fashion towards the capabilities of the female rowers whom they were tasked with helping to reach their potential. With the importance placed upon a positive coach athlete relationship, and possible influence of gender on this, it is worth examining further to confirm whether elite female players, and perhaps males, would benefit from working more with female coaches.

2.9 Elite Players as Coaches

An early study by Kerr and Banwell (2014) referred to women as an 'untapped resource' in the coaching workforce. The promotion of elite female players becoming coaches is an area that has not been widely studied, however it has been reported that former athletes are more likely to become coaches than any other population (Gilbert, Côté & Mallet, 2006; Koh, Mallett & Wang, 2011; Lara-Bercial & Mallett, 2016; Schull, 2017; Watts & Cushion, 2017), and is likely that current athletes are ideally placed to become coaches of the future (Everhart & Chelladurai, 1998). A recent study of elite football coaches (both genders) found that the majority saw the transition from player to coach as a natural progression that would allow them to remain in the sport (Ronkainen, Sleeman & Richardson, 2020), therefore as more women embark on a career as a footballer (through the increased opportunities in professional leagues that were hitherto absent) there is a chance this will increase the number progressing into coaching.

The reason elite players have been suggested as prime candidates for coaching high-level players is their accumulation of "sport capital" (Moret & Ohl, 2019, p1). Sisjord, Fasting and Sand's (2021) study supported an earlier one by Reade, Rodgers and Norman (2009) in finding that relatively more women than men who were coaching at a high level had previous national or international experience, suggesting that this sport capital has aided their progression. LaVoi, Wasend and Baeth (2019) also refer to 'athletic capital', highlighting that as participation rates of women in sport increase, this leads to an increase in the number who have the attributes to succeed as future coaches.

Competing at the highest level involves far more than simply performing in the sport itself (Norman, 2013), therefore it is possible that only those who have been in the position themselves are able to fully understand, and therefore support others in adapting to, the lifestyle involved. Jacobs, Claringbould and Knoppers (2014) explain how one of the most important sources of knowledge that a coach can tap into is their previous experience as an athlete. This ability to understand the mental and psychological challenges faced by elite athletes was also highlighted by female coaches with previous national experience in Sisjord, Fasting and Sand's (2021) exploratory study. These women felt that having experienced success at international level as athletes also helped them to gain respect from their athletes,

and other coaches. As a result, most felt their self-confidence was increased because of their past achievements, a trait that was not mentioned by any of the men. This again reinforces the value of the sport capital gained through playing, which may counteract the lack of respect often reported as a limiter to female coaches.

2.10 Rationale

Historically, research in relation to women's football has tended to focus on players (Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019), and has generally taken a more quantitative approach, rather than exploring personal experiences (Norman, 2010; Norman, 2014). Although the last few years have brought an increase in exploratory research about female coaches, these have tended to focus on the experiences of current, and usually successful, coaches (e.g. Clarkson, Cox & Thelwell, 2019; Knoppers et al., 2021), leaving the subject of coaching intentions largely understudied (Wasend & LaVoi, 2019).

Once recent study by Darvin, Taylor and Wells (2019) found that women were unlikely to consider coaching as a career from a young age, and had limited aspirations of pursuing the occupation. An earlier exploratory study involving an analysis of Physical Education (PE) students' coaching experiences and intentions (Fasting, Sand & Knorre, 2013), led the authors to highlight a need for more knowledge about factors that influence these intentions, however, since this study, the issue has not been addressed in any detail. More recently, Moustakas, Petry and Lara-Bercial (2021) – following an extensive literature review – concluded there remained a dearth of evidence related to motivators and barriers to women in coaching, recommending further research to improve understanding, allowing more, and better, programmes to be created to address this inequality.

A recent study that sought to explore the career paths of female athletes, is that by Wasend and LaVoi (2019). Although this study shows some interesting information, it provides only quantitative data. As it does not include any qualitative exploration of the women's career choices, and with only their current head coach's gender being considered (which may not be the only factor affecting an athlete's coaching intentions), I feel this has some limitations. As a result, my research aims to explore, in-depth, elite footballers' complete journey – including

their football career, and wider life experiences – to provide a greater insight into their future coaching intentions, and the possible influencers upon these.

The main motivation for this study is that women remain underrepresented in coaching across sports and levels (Lapchick, 2018; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019; Wasend & LaVoi, 2019), and despite female athletes potentially having “the most promise to increase women’s representation in leadership positions across all levels of sport” (Schull, 2017, p99), transitioning to coaching remains the choice of a minority (Knoppers et al, 2021). I feel that there is a need to add to existing literature to further increase understanding of the current situation, and make suggestions for how this may be improved. Although it will not be the correct path for all, Bruening et al. (2013) explain that many potential female coaches fail to enter the profession at all. It is therefore hoped that through exploring the experiences of elite players in this country, that this failure to capitalise on these individuals’ experiences and knowledge of the game begins to change.

Feminist research questions should be grounded in personal experiences of female researchers that are relevant to other women’s lives (Bierema & Cseh, 2003). I have an interest in this area following years of coaching at various levels of football (and with both genders). Although I have not been involved in organised football for over ten years, I am concerned that the situation remains largely unchanged, and that this is likely to continue to affect others who may consider becoming coaches in future. Throughout my coaching career I had a largely positive experience, however I did find myself isolated at times, and faced many of the barriers that I continue to read about in the current literature. For this reason, I hope to utilise the postmodern feminist framework to answer the following research question:

‘How likely are elite female footballers to consider entering into coaching as a career, and what are the underlying reasons for this?’

3.0 Methodology

This section will begin by outlining the theoretical underpinning of the chosen methodology. Following this, the specific methodological choices will be explained, before a critique of the pilot study illustrates subsequent alterations that led to the final methodology.

3.1 Theoretical Perspective

Fundamental to feminist research is the exploration of the experiences of women (Benschop & Verloo, 2016) – and the impact of these – therefore this study was conducted in the interpretivist paradigm, utilising a qualitative methodology. In line with postmodern thought, I understand that knowledge is constructed through discourse (Rumenapp, 2016; Angermuller, 2018), therefore providing female players with an opportunity to share their story was key. I was careful to remain cognisant of the language used by the players, as well as the unspoken word (i.e. gestures, body language), to help me truly understand their journeys. Framed in the feminist philosophy, this research sought to look at the world from a woman's perspective, allowing their voices to be heard and used in the knowledge-creation process (Bierema & Cseh, 2003).

The epistemological assumptions of this research are in line with interpretivism, in that society is shaped by the individuals within it, and that in many cases 'reality' is subject to interpretation (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2018). When considering the most appropriate methods for this study, a critical realist ontology was adopted; acknowledging that although an independent world exists, our understanding of it is shaped by our own perspectives (Maxwell, 2015). These multiple realities (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012) are evident in previous studies of female representation in sport coaching. Although there is a general agreement on the nature of barriers faced by female coaches, and the qualities that they can bring to the workforce, investigations into the journeys of elite female coaches (e.g. Norman, 2014; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019) suggest that these barriers may be time and culture dependent.

Through framing the research in the postmodern feminist framework, I have attempted to move beyond "the simplistic assumptions and solutions offered" by more traditional feminist theories (Ely & Meyerson, 2000, p8), to make a real contribution to women's football. As a

Professional Doctorate thesis, this piece of work cannot, nor does it intend to be, revolutionary (Fulton et al., 2013), but I hope it can provide a background that may start to change attitudes and practices; these changing attitudes then beginning to decrease the number, and size, of barriers that currently seem to limit women's progression in coaching.

According to Meyerson and Fletcher (1999, p127), feminist research strategies should be "based on small wins — incremental changes that have the power to transform organizations positively for both women and men". This was something at the front of my mind as I sought to make recommendations. Although these recommendations primarily relate to increasing female representation, for the benefit of women, this increase in representation is also likely to benefit the overall football landscape, without any negative impact upon men. As well as benefitting the football landscape, it is also hoped that these 'incremental changes' may in turn lead to small 'wins' for other minority groups in society as a whole.

3.2 Qualitative Research

To provide an extensive examination of the coaching intentions of elite female footballers a qualitative methodology was adopted. This methodology fits with interpretivist and feminist research as it allows 'stories' to be told from the perspective of the population of interest (i.e. current elite female footballers), and interpreted through discourse with the researcher. Qualitative research aims to allow access to individuals' "subjective worlds", especially those often marginalised – and therefore "invisible" in society (Braun & Clarke, 2019, p8). As feminist research aims to tell the stories of women who are often seen as invisible, or inferior, this paradigm is most fitting in the current football landscape. It was originally planned that the study would incorporate some quantitative findings, however the response rate, and quality of information gathered in early questionnaires, was of limited use and was therefore discarded. These questionnaires however did serve a function, as they provided an opportunity for players to indicate a willingness to be interviewed, to share contact details for arranging this, and they provided basic information that allowed me to tailor interview questions accordingly.

Qualitative research gained popularity in the 1980s (Braun & Clarke, 2019) as several theoretical approaches, including feminism (Crawford & Unger, 2004) and postmodernism

(Gergen, 1990), started to question the notion of a single reality, exempt from internal and external influence. Key to qualitative research is the understanding that the relationship between person and context is “reciprocal” (Braun & Clarke, 2019, p8), so through in-depth interviews I hoped to be able to work *with* the players to construct the knowledge that would be analysed and presented.

3.3 The Study Context

Participants who took part in this study will be detailed below, however it is also useful here to note the context within which they participate. The women’s football landscape in Scotland is fairly unique, therefore findings should be understood in this context. Nationally the women’s game is governed by the SFA, in line with the men’s game, having done so since 1998. Scottish Women’s Football is an affiliated national association of the SFA, taking charge of leagues and competitions at all levels, including the SWPL. Both the SWPL1 and SWPL2 are professional leagues, although for many of the players contracts are part-time. This means that for many – especially outside the top league – football is not their only career.

3.4 Participants

The sample used in this study were high-level Scottish players. For the purposes of the study ‘high-level’ was defined as playing for the national squad, or in one of the top two domestic leagues. The reason only top-level players were included is that they have been identified as having many attributes that could lead them to be successful in coaching other high-level players in future (Kerr & Banwell, 2014; Lara-Bercial & Mallett, 2016; Watts & Cushion, 2017), and that there seems a disparity between the progression from playing to coaching among elite male and female footballers. The national squad fluctuates, but at the time of writing there are 27 current players listed on the SFA website (SFA, 2021a). In addition, there are ten teams in the SWPL 1 and seven in SWPL 2. Especially in the top league, a number of these players also represent the national team, however by inviting the national squad separately it also opened up the possibility of including Scottish players who were playing in other domestic leagues. Of the eight players interviewed, five were in the current national set-up, while three had represented the country in the past. Seven of the players currently play in SWPL1, the other playing for a team in WSL1. Table 5, below, provides a summary of the

participants.

Table 5 Summary of participants

Pseudonym	Playing history / status	Education / employment	Coaching experience / intentions
Sharon	Started playing with boys before transitioning to girls' football aged 12. Currently playing in SWPL1 on a part-time contract. Has represented Scotland.	Studied a sport related degree on a scholarship while playing football. Currently working full-time alongside football (in a non-sport related job).	Coached various levels from beginners to Premier League reserves. Both genders at lower levels but only girls at higher levels. Time is restricting amount of coaching currently. Has C-licence and plans to work through the higher levels. Would love to be a full-time coach but is not sure if it is worth giving up her established, secure, career for.
Kyla	Started playing with boys before a girls' team started. She then played for both until age 12. Has played with a SWPL2 team (recently promoted to SWPL1) throughout career. Represented country at age group levels. Currently on part-time football contract.	Studied and worked towards a non-football related job. Currently works full-time alongside football.	Has C licence and has coached younger players at her own team. Enjoys coaching and would "probably love" it as a career but finds it hard to see herself giving up her current job.
Linsay	Started playing with boys (stopped for a while as she didn't like being the only girl but returned) before transitioning to girls' football aged 12. Currently on full-time contract with a SWPL1 club. Has played at full international level.	Studied a sport-related degree but has not worked elsewhere since gaining first full-time professional contract upon graduation.	Did some grassroots coaching – both genders – as a means of earning money through her studies, working through some basic qualifications. Has not ruled out coaching but thinks it is unlikely she will make it a career after playing.
Heather	Started playing with boys before joining a girls' team aged 10. Currently on a full-time contract with a SWPL1 club and is involved with the Scotland national team.	Studied a sport related degree on a football scholarship. Currently works in the fitness industry alongside football commitments.	Has done quite a lot of coaching, at various levels, and is currently working towards B licence. Unlikely to make this a full-time career but hasn't ruled it out. May continue current part-time job after retirement from playing, but is also considering a non-football career.

Lisa	Started playing with boys, joined a girls' team as well around age 11 before having to leave boys' team at 12. Currently playing in SWPL1 on a part-time contract and involved in the national squad.	Currently studying a sport related degree at university alongside playing football.	Has not really considered coaching to a great extent but does not expect to go into this as a career at the moment. No coaching experience or qualifications.
Nicola	Started playing with boys before moving to a girls' team aged 12. Currently playing in the SWPL1 full-time. Also involved in international set-up.	Studied a sport-related degree and did a bit of part-time coaching prior to gaining a full-time contract.	Coached grassroots and regional squad to earn money while on a part-time contract. Working towards B-licence but does not expect to coach full-time. Considering working in the fitness industry upon retirement.
Margaret	Started playing with boys before moving to a girls' team aged 12. Currently employed part-time by a SWPL1 club. Has represented Scotland at full international level.	Worked in various office jobs throughout football career, currently working for a football club on a part-time basis.	Has coached at various levels and is currently working towards A-licence. Unsure if she will remain in coaching but plans to stay involved in football in some capacity post-playing.
Elaine	Started playing boys football before moving to a girls' team aged 15. Currently plays in WSL1 on a full-time contract and represents Scotland at full international level.	Studied sport at university on a football scholarship. No other work just now except for sporadic coaching.	Has coached at various levels but has no qualifications yet. Unsure whether she will coach full-time upon retirement or "have nothing to do with football".

All participants were female professional, or semi-professional, footballers aged between 21 and 34. Due to the small pool of players I have chosen not to specify individuals' ages. Players were also all Scottish, white, and did not disclose any disabilities. This means the sample is very homogeneous, but largely reflective of the demographic, as the current (2022) Scottish national squad contains only one non-white player. To protect anonymity all players have been given a pseudonym and any identifying details (club, former coaches, teammates, jobs, etc.) have been changed/anonymised or deleted. Interviews lasted between 32 and 80 minutes, with a mean duration of 48 minutes (SD = 15).

3.4.1 Sampling

To ensure suitable data could be gathered, relevant to the research question, the initial sampling technique used for this study was purposeful (Patton, 2002; Lavrakas, 2008). Purposeful sampling is widely used in qualitative research as it generally results in the

selection of a study group that have an extensive knowledge and / or experience of the phenomenon of interest (Patton, 2002). This sampling technique is efficient in relation to time, resources and expertise (Suri, 2011), and through utilising it I did not 'waste' any time interviewing people whose experiences were not of benefit to the research question. Although time efficiency was an added bonus, the main reason that purposeful sampling was used was because the population of interest was very specific. Patton (2002, p130) explains how purposeful sampling results in the identification of "information-rich" subjects who can be analysed to gain real "in-depth understanding rather than empirical generalizations". Again, this is key to postmodern feminist research where a thorough, in-depth, understanding of the experiences of women is vital. As elite footballers, these women are statistically a minority group and therefore worthy of study as a demographic.

Purposeful sampling is a broad term, and the specific strategy I used was criterion-i (Patton, 2002). This strategy involves the identification of all individuals who meet the predetermined criterion (Palinkas et al., 2015); in this case female footballers who were currently playing at National level for Scotland and / or playing in the top divisions in Scotland (SWPL 1 or 2). The population selected for this research was determined in response to the suggestion that current elite athletes are an 'untapped resource' of high-level coaches (Kerr and Banwell, 2014).

Although the gender gap in participation in football is narrowing (Sleeman & Ronkainen, 2020), current statistics suggest that – although they possess many desirable characteristics – it is not as common for female players to move into coaching at the end of their career. This criterion-i method meant there was a limit to the quantity of potential data sources (compared with a more extensive sampling technique), however it did ensure that all of those who were interviewed were "information rich" (Palinkas et al., 2015, p533), and had experiences directly relevant to the research question. Although there is the obvious disadvantage of limited quantity, small samples are the norm in exploratory studies because "increases in sample size do not accomplish an adequate basis for generalization, but they most certainly compromise the opportunity to report in depth" (Wolcott, 2008, p.93).

In relation to sample size in qualitative research, there are "no rules", rather it will be affected by the purpose of the study, and the time and resources available to the researcher (Patton,

2002, p244). Braun and Clarke (2013) suggest that six to ten interviews are sufficient for a study exploring experiences, again highlighting the influence of the *type* of data gathered. It is common for researchers to report interviewing until 'data saturation' (Glaser & Strauss, 1967), however, as reported by Low (2019), this is arguably impossible as – due to the nature of qualitative research – there is always a chance that new information will be uncovered.

Braun and Clarke (2021b, p201) agree that the concept of data saturation is “not consistent with the values and assumptions of reflexive TA [thematic analysis]”, therefore, although I had an expectation of how many players I would interview, I did not set a definite number at the outset to avoid missing any useful new emerging data, or unnecessarily interviewing an excessive number of players. These two scenarios could be seen as being limiting to validity, and unethical, respectively (Francis et al., 2010). I therefore set out to achieve 'theoretical sufficiency' (Dey, 1999) or 'conceptual depth' (Nelson, 2016). Both of these terms suggest that data collection should stop when the researcher has developed an appropriate level of understanding of the phenomenon, indicating that it is more important to consider the quality of data, rather than quantity, when making a judgement about 'saturation'.

To recruit players for the study I used gatekeepers (Clark, 2011) who were able to provide access to the intended sample. Reeves (2010) explains how gatekeepers can both help and hinder research, depending on their perception of its value. For this reason, I thought carefully about who would be best placed for this, especially after my first choice of gatekeeper – the Scotland manager – had left her post only weeks before I was due to start. A colleague of mine works with the SFA, and he put me in touch with a Sport Scientist who worked closely with the women's national squad. I believe that the personal connection led him to genuinely promote the research, resulting in a good response rate. For the SWPL players I contacted the Scottish Women's Football (SWF) Senior Clubs and Competitions Officer, whose details were provided by a friend who works with her in his role at a Premier League club. The SWF Officer was extremely interested in the study and asked if SWF and the SFA would be able to access findings, something that I was happy to agree to, as sharing my research with bodies such as this the likelihood of it making a real impact is increased.

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, domestic football in Scotland had been cancelled when I initially distributed the questionnaires, therefore unfortunately it was not possible for

coaches to speak to players in person, which may have encouraged a better response. However, the SWF Officer distributed the link along with Participant Information Sheet (PIS) and covering letter to all club secretaries who forwarded them to individual players. A month was given for completion and within one week ten responses had been received, four of these providing an email address for interview. However, after this promising start, there were no further responses. The SWF Officer sent out a request to the secretaries to remind the players, but no further responses were received.

Although domestic football had been cancelled, international matches continued, and at a training camp the gatekeeper forwarded a message I had transcribed via WhatsApp, including a link to the questionnaire and PIS. Whatsapp was the medium used for players' communication, and one they were all familiar with, so the message could be sent to the full national squad electronically, allowing them to complete it safely at their convenience. The squad at this camp involved 23 players. Twelve of these completed the questionnaire, and five also provided an email address, stating a willingness to participate in an interview.

Following this initial purposeful sampling, which was not as successful as hoped, a new approach – 'snowball sampling' (Patton, 1990) – was adopted. This was not planned, however after a positive first interview where a good relationship was formed, it was apparent the player found the experience enjoyable, and was keen to do what she could to help. Because of this I asked her to encourage her team mates to get in touch with me if they were willing to participate, and in the next week eight more questionnaires had been completed, with two more email addresses. This snowball sampling continued with each interview, leading to eight in-depth interviews with players from across the league, and one who played in the WSL in England (recruited through the national squad). Most of the Scottish league players were also current and / or past representatives of the national team.

As similar types of studies have tended to include 10-12 participants, I did initially plan to interview this number myself, however the main factor in me stopping at eight was one of time and resources, often the case in this type of research (O'Reilly & Parker, 2012; Braun & Clarke, 2021). Although it could not be certain that no new data would emerge, I did start to see more and more duplication of codes, and fewer new ones, leading me to be satisfied I had uncovered enough to draw some useful conclusions. It should be noted that the pool of

available players for this study was small, therefore the number of participants represents a large proportion in comparison to similar studies.

3.5 Ethics

Prior to any data collection, including the pilot study, ethical approval was granted by the University of the West of Scotland. All players were over the age of 18, and in a position to provide consent themselves. To allow them to make an informed decision, all players were provided with a copy of the Participant Information Sheet (Appendix 1) that detailed the study in full, and given an opportunity to ask questions. The PIS detailed the procedure, and assurance that anonymity would be bestowed through the use of pseudonyms, and removal of any identifying details prior to any presentation of findings. The players were also informed that their participation was optional, and that they had the right to withdraw, without reason, at any time.

Questionnaires included a consent statement, and for those who indicated a willingness to participate in an interview, they were provided with an additional consent form (Appendix 2) to sign and return prior to meeting. This was all done electronically, minimising any inconvenience – or Covid-related risks – to the participants. Initially, ethical approval was granted for the study of the national team only, however following the pilot study (Section 3.8) – in which the response rate was very low – I decided to widen the proposed sample to maximise potential sources of data. As a result, an application for an amendment to the study was made to allow for a wider sample (including those playing in the top domestic leagues in the country), and this was granted prior to study commencement (Appendix 3).

3.6 Questionnaires

Although in the final analysis the questionnaire results were discarded, this section will briefly explain their format, and how they played a small part in the research process. Questionnaires included quantitative questions about playing experience (length of time, level achieved, etc.), coaching experience (how much, who with, etc.), qualifications, and intentions. It was initially planned that enough data would be gathered to draw wider conclusions about the population, but the number of responses received meant that this was

not possible. There were also qualitative questions about playing and coaching history, as well as a final section for the players to add their email address if they were willing to be interviewed. Although the data was not formally analysed and presented, the information gleaned allowed me to best prepare for the interview. As I had three different interview schedules (Appendix 4), depending on whether players had coached and / or intended to coach, the quantitative data allowed me to use the correct one, saving an additional question at the start of the interview. The questionnaires were also the primary method of recruiting for interviews, before snowball sampling commenced latterly.

3.7 Interviews

As an exploratory study, semi-structured interviews were chosen as the method of data collection. This type of interview is most common in qualitative research, especially that related to experiences (Braun & Clarke, 2014). Due to their nature, these interviews provide enough structure to encourage information related to the research question, while remaining flexible enough to account for any interesting divergences. Semi-structured interviews are also common in feminist research (e.g. Kitzinger & Wilmott, 2002) as they allow women to share their stories freely. In deciding upon the most appropriate method, it is sensible to consider the limitations of each; the main disadvantage of semi-structured interviews generally accepted as the time required to conduct and transcribe them (Brown, 2001). Although the interviews were expected to take around 40 minutes to conduct, and a few hours each to transcribe, with the intention of including 8-12 participants I decided this was feasible in the time I had available, and that the effort of the interview process was justified by the depth of information that could be gathered.

Although the questionnaire responses did not provide enough quality data to utilise in analysis, with their dependent design (Schoonenboom & Johnson, 2017) – in that the second component was influenced by the first – they did provide me with an overview of the players' experiences and intentions, allowing me to tailor my interview schedule accordingly. With the knowledge of which players had experienced coaching, to what extent, and who had considered coaching in future, I was able to ensure I asked only relevant questions, avoiding unnecessary time commitment for any party. Wilkinson and Birmingham (2003) recommend semi-structured interviews as a useful follow up to questionnaires which may focus on the

surface elements of the phenomenon, as the interviews can provide greater insight into the meaning and significance of this surface data.

Interviews have been described as, “a social, interpersonal encounter, not merely a data-collection exercise” (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2018, p 506); allowing knowledge to be constructed between participants. Again, this fits well with interpretative research, and the epistemological viewpoint of multiple realities (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2012). The social nature of interviews is also key to successfully using a feminist framework that seeks to use the voice of the women themselves to construct knowledge.

A key benefit of interviews, over written data collection methods, is that they allow for “multi-sensory channels”, that is “verbal, non-verbal, seen, spoken and heard” (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p506). As highlighted in Foucault’s (1972) work, language is key to meaning creation. Therefore, as well as using the explicit words spoken in my analysis, I also considered body language, movements and pauses that added to their meaning. Further benefits of interviews include the ability of the interviewer to explain and clarify any questions if required (Phellas, Bloch & Seale, 2011), minimising the risk of misunderstanding. Furthermore, through being able to ‘probe’ participants on interesting points (Phellas, Bloch and Seale, 2011) it was possible to gain a far greater depth of information, a necessity for sound qualitative research.

3.7.1 Procedure

At the start of the methodological decision-making process, I decided to conduct the interviews face-to-face, in-person, as evidence suggests this is the ‘gold standard’ (McCoyd & Kerson, 2006; Novick, 2008); likely to build a better rapport, put the interviewees at ease, and promote more honest, reflective disclosures. However, as a result of the coronavirus pandemic during 2020, and associated travel and meeting restrictions, face-to-face interviews were not an option – at least for the foreseeable future – and the decision was made to conduct the interviews through Microsoft (MS) teams. Although earlier research suggests asynchronous interviews (in relation to time and / or place) may hold lesser value (Gillham, 2005; Irvine, 2011; Rubin & Rubin, 2011), concerns tend to focus on limited non-verbal cues (Gillham, 2005; Fielding & Thomas, 2008; Cater, 2011; Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2018),

difficulty in building rapport (Adams-Hutcheson & Longhurst, 2016; Seitz, 2016), and technological issues (Hannah, 2012; Seitz, 2016; Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2018).

As the country was put into 'lockdown' to contain the virus, online platforms became the norm for many interactions that were hitherto in-person, such as education, business meetings and socialising (Richter, 2020), leading many to quickly adapt to this new way of working. With people becoming more familiar with online interactions many of the concerns highlighted above became obsolete (Rubinger et al., 2020), therefore this forced change arguably worked to my advantage as I was able to interview individuals across the country at a time suitable to them, without the need for either of us to travel. Furthermore, the ease of recording these interviews allowed me to focus on the conversation, with little need to write additional notes.

Through 'active listening' (Robertson, 2005), I could focus fully on the participant, taking in what they were saying, while also noting gestures, tones, etc. that added to the meaning of their story. Active listening generally involves three elements including showing interest in the speaker through nonverbal responses, refraining from judgement and paraphrasing the speaker's message to confirm understanding, and asking questions to allow the speaker to elaborate (Weger Jr et al, 2014). I used these techniques to ensure I gained thorough information, and also to help the participant feel at ease and valued. The recording of these interviews also allowed me to revisit them in their entirety, as many times as necessary, unlike in a standard face-to-face interview where only the verbal content would have been available afterwards.

The interview itself began by asking each player to discuss her 'journey' as a footballer. This opening question would serve two purposes; primarily putting the player at ease, while also providing some interesting information that would help me to understand the influences on her current career, and future intentions. Following this, questions focused on experiences of being coached, experiences of coaching others (where appropriate), and plans for a post-playing career (with probing questions asked where necessary to try to understand potential influences on these topics). The players all engaged well with the interview, providing some very interesting stories that will be discussed further in the findings and discussion section. From questionnaire responses I could ascertain if each player had any coaching experience

and / or whether they coached currently. This allowed me to tailor questions more appropriately, although the semi-structured nature of the interviews did allow for diversion from the guide where appropriate. Copies of all three interview guides can be found in Appendix 4.

3.7.2 Member Checking / Validity

Regardless of medium, in addition to the time factor, lack of complete anonymity and the potential for subconscious bias have also been cited as disadvantages to using interviews for data collection (Brown, 2001; Phellas, Bloch & Seale, 2011). By using MS Teams, with video enabled, it was impossible for the players to remain anonymous to me, however they were assured that in any written transcripts that they would be given pseudonyms, and any identifying characteristics, or experiences, would be removed to protect their identity.

The traditional method of controlling interviewer bias is through 'member checking' (Lincoln & Guba, 1985), however more recently Smith and McGannon (2018) have criticised this practice for its inability to 'prove' accuracy. The notion of member checking conflicts with the assumptions of qualitative research where it is understood that there is no single reality, therefore it does not make sense to expect one viewpoint to be accepted as correct. As both participants' and researchers' interpretations will be affected by their experiences and beliefs, it is important to remember that these are unlikely to fully correspond. Smith and McGannon (2018) therefore offer 'member reflections', not to confirm validity, but to help create "intellectually enriched understanding" (p15), through generating further dialogue. Having considered both member checking and member reflections, and the benefits of each, I decided to utilise aspects of both practices to ensure interpretations were consistent with the interviews themselves, and the experiences discussed.

The first stage of checking involved sending a transcription of the interview to each participant, asking them to confirm it was an accurate account of the conversation. The participants also had the opportunity at this stage to reconstruct their narrative if they felt it was no longer representative of their experience (Birt et al., 2016). Although all participants were emailed with these transcripts, only three replied (one initially and two more after a second email). Because of this I did not expect much engagement with the member

reflections, however I did want to allow the participants the opportunity to reflect upon my thematic analysis so, following its completion, I emailed each participant a copy and invited them to arrange a phone call if they wanted to discuss it further. As expected, none of the participants took up this offer, although two did respond to say that they were happy with the themes I had identified and discussed. This process of checking and reflecting, involving participants in the process, did not remove subjectivity – as it is not possible, nor perhaps desired in qualitative research (Smith & McGannon, 2018) – however it did aim to increase transparency for the participants, and for those reading the research.

With the limited input of participants in this aspect of ‘quality control’, I felt it was particularly important to triangulate my findings to an extent. For this triangulation I used "critical friends" (Arnold, 2012; Smith & McGannon, 2018) throughout the data analysis stage, to maximise the validity of my findings. Critical friends are individuals selected for their knowledge and experience of the subject area, and the research methods adopted. In this case the chosen individuals were my supervisors; both highly experienced in qualitative research, one also published widely in women’s sport and feminism. These critical friends had access to the transcripts and the themes that I had identified, challenging me to further reflect on my construction of knowledge (Patton, 2002) with each draft.

3.8 Positionality

The concept of positionality was originally introduced by Merton (1972) who discussed a dichotomy of insider and outsider doctrines of research; simply defining an insider as a member of a specified group, and an outsider as a non-member. However more recently researchers have discarded this simple dichotomy, arguing instead that positionality is better suited to a continuum (e.g. Christensen & Dahl, 1997). Mercer (2007) agrees that positionality exists on a continuum with multiple dimensions, adding that researchers constantly move back and forth along this continuum, depending on the nature of their research. Positionality “reflects the position that the researcher has chosen to adopt within a given research study” (Savin-Baden & Major, 2013, p71), and influences how research is conducted, and the results it obtains (Rowe, 2014). Holmes (2020, p2) explains how reflexivity “informs” positionality, requiring a self-assessment of the researcher and how views and positions may impact the research.

Through regular reflexion throughout the whole interview process – prior to, during, and after each interview – I made an effort to ‘step away’ from the information, looking from different angles, and continually questioning my understanding of findings. I took time to consider my interpretations and assess whether these were likely representative of the true feelings of the players, and not impacted disproportionately by my own experiences. Thinking of myself in this capacity, I acknowledged that my beliefs, political stance, and cultural background were likely to affect the research process, and findings. Although this subjective impact is inevitable, by remaining reflexive throughout the process (Burke-Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Ahmed, Hunt & Blackburn, 2011), the effect is considered and acknowledged.

Part of my commitment to reflexion included keeping a Reflexive Journal (Lincoln and Guba, 1985) in which I regularly recorded any methodological decisions made, with reasons, along with a personal reflection of how these were impacted by my own values, beliefs, and interests. Key to my values is my strive for equity, and I believe everyone should have the opportunity to be successful. I also believe in the value of hard work and do not expect to be simply ‘given’ opportunities, but in looking for them and taking them on that, regardless of gender, race, etc., one should be able to make the most of them. In relation to research, I believe stories from individuals provide rich data, therefore my methodological decisions were made to best allow the players to openly share their stories, without judgement, in a safe environment. I also added to my reflexive journal throughout the interview process, noting my thoughts and feelings at the end of each.

Where women discussed (often indirect) discrimination, and opportunities they had been offered and taken, I noted my own thoughts in my reflexive diary to ensure I could be transparent in my analysis of any themes that emerged from these discussions. This reflexion had to be in-depth and I thoroughly evaluated my role in relation to positionality, the potential impact of the information I shared, and the possible effect of my own experiences on my interpretation of those shared by the participant. In my self-assessment of positionality I considered my own coaching experiences, reflecting upon how these had shaped my beliefs about the role. I acknowledged that my experiences were individual to me, and that I could not presume these would be reflective of those of the interview sample.

This reflexion led me to conclude that my position on the continuum was in fact fluid, and

context dependent. Soerdigo and Glas (2020) propose the term 'active reflexivity' which relates to this fluidity of positionality. Mohammed (2001) explained how one could simultaneously be an insider and an outsider and I feel this was the case for me. Positionality cannot be defined simply by demographic characteristics, but also personal and professional experiences and values (Soedirgo & Glas, 2020), therefore, through 'actively reflecting', I began to understand that my (perceived) positionality was likely to alter as I engaged with different players.

As a white Scottish woman, I shared some significant 'fixed' characteristics with the study participants and, having played and coached football myself in the past, I also shared some key experiences that could lead me to be seen as an insider. However, although I did share some characteristics and experiences, there were factors that moved me along the continuum. For example, although I played football, I did not do so at national level, therefore I had not lived this specific experience; one which is key to the current research. Also, my football experiences – both playing and coaching – were typically 20 years before those of the current sample, at a time when the football landscape was very different; again, making it important for me not to generalise or assume.

Regardless of the different experiences that moved me away from being a true insider, I believe that my partial insider status did bring significant benefits to my research. It seemed apparent that the players viewed me as 'one of them' as the conversations were always easy and informal, indicating that they all felt comfortable in my presence. I feel this relationship was enhanced by me sharing some information about my own experiences, and this was something I considered carefully, and reflected upon in my reflexive diary, at the end of each interview.

Previous studies have indicated some clear benefits to insider status, some of which were apparent for me, including easier access to the culture being studied (Sanghera & Bjokert, 2008). At first I did not have great success in recruiting players, however after interviewing one player I found that my sample 'snowballed' (Patton, 1990), discussed above. This was not a sampling strategy I initially planned but I feel that having created such a good relationship, the players were keen to support me as it seemed they genuinely enjoyed their interview experience.

Another advantage that has been highlighted is the ability of an insider to ask more insightful questions (Holmes, 2020) and again, I believe this was the case as I understood what it felt like to be in some of the situations the players were describing, allowing me to probe further with relevant questions. Holmes (2020) also suggests that interviewees may provide more honest descriptions, and perhaps more detailed descriptions of their experiences, to an insider. Participants seemed keen to share their experiences with someone to whom they could relate. This willingness to more openly share has been highlighted as a key benefit to insider status as an interviewer, participants feeling more comfortable with someone who they understand to be sympathetic to their situation (Berger, 2015).

Although I used my insider status to encourage full, honest disclosures, I made sure that the participants were confident that I would not pre-judge, or assume, as a result of my previous experiences. I did this by being open myself at the start of the interviews, acknowledging my positionality, sharing my experiences (briefly), and explaining how I was open to their experiences, and would not presume theirs would draw parallels to mine.

There were some instances when the players touched upon what initially seemed personal and potentially sensitive topics, and I was unsure whether to probe further. However, I did carefully ask that they share if they felt comfortable doing so, and the players all went on to provide some very honest accounts of their emotions. Upon reflection, I feel this was a result of the relationship I had built, at least partially a result of my insider status. Finally, Holmes (2020) explains that an insider is better able to understand language and non-verbal clues better than an outsider. There were instances of the players using jargon and referring to coaches and other players by first name which I could relate to as I understand the arena in which they play. An outsider would likely have had to ask more questions which I believe would have taken away from the 'friendly' relationship that I had created; potentially detracting from the depth of information offered.

I did not find any disadvantage to my insider status although I cannot be sure my own experiences did not disproportionately influence my interpretation. To limit any influence – or at least to remain transparent about it – I spent time reflecting on each interview afterwards, as well as offering the opportunity for member reflections in case any wanted to discuss my interpretation further. Reflexion was key to all stages of the interview process,

from identifying questions which I would place greater emphasis on, being aware of my reactions to responses, and ensuring full engagement and analysis of the data, without 'unconscious editing' (Valentine, 2007, p20). Again, through noting in my reflexive journal at the end of each interview I was able to ensure I remained cognisant of my subjective input as I later analysed the data.

3.9 Data Analysis

To analyse the data from the interviews I used Braun and Clarke's (2019) Reflexive Thematic Analysis (TA). Thematic Analysis in general is popular among qualitative researchers as it is flexible, accessible, and relatively quick to learn (Braun & Clarke, 2013). The approach involves six steps – outlined below – however Braun and Clarke (2021a) are keen to point out that the process is not linear, and that the researcher moves back and forth between stages as required.

The original six-stage approach involves firstly becoming familiar with the data, which I did by transcribing and revisiting each interview, fully immersing myself in the transcripts. Next, I used NVivo to generate initial codes (stage 2) (see Appendix 5 for an example). For this coding process I used a predominately inductive approach (Braun & Clarke, 2013). Braun and Clarke (2013, 2019) argue that it is unlikely a researcher can exclusively use one technique, and I agree that I did have some ideas about what type of codes may emerge prior to analysis (deductive coding). For example, from previous reading – and my own experiences – I would have been surprised if the players did not begin by speaking of playing in boys teams, and being influenced by men at early stages. However, I was keen not to look for examples on the basis of assumptions, rather creating codes that – upon reading transcripts – I felt best illustrated the experiences as communicated by the players (inductive coding). I repeated this step on numerous occasions as, with each draft, I considered the different ways each story could be related to key points. As I became more immersed in the data, I also felt I could be more critical in my interpretation of spoken, and non-spoken language; key to inductive coding (Braun & Clarke, 2013).

As I coded, I utilised both semantic and latent approaches (Braun & Clarke, 2013). There were instances where codes were developed from the explicit language used, for example the

players all told of their early coaches being men, allowing me to easily code this as ‘experiences of coaches’ and ‘playing journey’. However, through using a more latent approach at times, I was able to interpret deeper levels of meaning, and meaningfulness, of the experiences being discussed (Braun & Clarke, 2006). An example of this is that, although players tended to talk fondly of their experiences of coach education, I could interpret from the language used, and hesitancy in some statements, that the courses were not necessarily suited equally to women and men. The players played down this male dominance, and lack of attention to the women’s game, but the implicit meaning induced from the interviews suggested this may have had a bigger impact than they realised; a common doubt coming through that they could be successful at the highest level. In my analysis I used verbal and non-verbal content as I felt this added to the data; this can be seen in the Results and Discussion section. Through using quotes with further explanation, I have been transparent in showing what the players actually said, along with how I felt gestures, tone of voice, etc., perhaps enhanced my analysis of this.

Coding is an “organic and evolving process” (Braun & Clarke, 2013, p211), therefore as I read and reread data items, as well as adding new codes I modified existing ones, and at times merged codes where I felt this was appropriate. For example, in an early version, I had a ‘general playing experience’ code, and a ‘football playing journey’ code which, upon reflection, I decided to merge into simply ‘playing journey’. Similarly, codes for ‘education’ and ‘non-football career’ were adapted to become ‘education/career journey’ to accommodate information about life choices that have led towards their current – or planned future - career. Table 6 (below) shows a worked example of how some codes evolved.

Table 6 Example of Coding Process

Data Item	Initial Codes	Adapted codes
Eh just a better opportunity I think like obviously at the time em (my team) took over a em, so (my team) didn’t actually have a youth academy until, well for the female side, until, that was the first year I think they took over and they became, they took over a club,	Football playing journey General support for women’s football General playing experience	Playing journey Opportunities in women’s football
it was just a good opportunity to go into that kind of like, it’s almost like the female version of pro-youth	Barriers / enablers to career (football)	Opportunities in women’s football

<p>obviously girls don't have pro-youth in this country it's not something that's eh, ever been, football's I don't think has been, invested in the women's game enough to have something like a pro-youth system like the men's or the boys have. Em so it was like the best equivalent I think in terms of like what the money and investment was put in and it was like some of the best coaching, em, at the time were kind of involved that were heavily going through their SFA badges at the time so even at like Under 13 you had like coaches that were doing their B-Licence em or doing their C-Licence which was a like quite accredited em, coaching affiliation for that kind of level. Em so yeah you had like some really good coaching</p>	<p>Football playing journey</p> <p>General support for women's football</p> <p>Barriers / enablers to career (football)</p> <p>Experience of coaches</p>	<p>Playing journey</p> <p>Opportunities in women's football</p> <p>Experience of coaches</p>
<p>I still believe that probably that was one of the best influences I had at the time was my coaches at that time which was like (male coach) and (female coach) that were great.</p>	<p>Influences on playing</p> <p>Experience of coaches</p> <p>Coach gender</p>	<p>Influences on football career</p> <p>Experience of coaches</p>
<p>it was just a better opportunity to go and play at a level where I wanted to kind of progress and, and actually, hopefully progress and play further up the game.</p>	<p>Barriers / enablers to career (football)</p> <p>Aspirations as player</p>	<p>Opportunities in women's football</p> <p>Playing aspirations</p>
<p>I always wanted to be a footballer because like, like I say my best pals all said they wanted to be footballers and, em my family's a, grew up quite big (Scottish team) fans, so em...</p>	<p>Influences on playing</p> <p>Aspirations as player</p>	<p>Influences on playing</p> <p>Aspirations as player</p>
<p>I think I always wanted to be but I don't think it was something that really, I thought was possible until a lot later on in my career like, like probably when I hit about 16, 17 when I got into the academy set-up</p>	<p>Aspirations as player</p> <p>Barriers / enablers to career (football)</p> <p>General support for women's football</p> <p>Aspirations as player</p>	<p>Aspirations as player</p> <p>Opportunities in women's football</p> <p>Aspirations as player</p>

<p>I think it wasn't until I got accepted onto that (scholarship) programme I was like, wow this is what it must be like to be full-time</p>	<p>General support for women's football</p> <p>Education</p> <p>Barriers / enablers to career (football)</p>	<p>Opportunities in women's football</p> <p>Career/education journey</p>
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Once I had finished the coding process I started to create 'candidate themes' (stage 3). Braun and Clarke (2013) refer to candidate themes – rather than simply, themes – as they stress that it is likely that they will emerge, develop, change, and be removed, as the process continues. Once the candidate themes were identified, these were reviewed in line with the data (stage 4), and I created a thematic map (Braun & Clarke, 2006) to check how they fitted; how well they presented an overall picture of the findings (see Figure 3 for thematic map).

Initially I had only two overarching themes ('I'd love to, but could I?' and 'I've not really considered it') which I felt were related to my research question about coaching intentions. However, upon reflecting on the data and the codes, I felt it was necessary to add a third theme ('we totally should!') as this allowed me to include interesting data about why the research question was relevant; showing the qualities the players could bring to the profession. Following this I worked with the codes again to generate sub-themes that would provide more specific information about each overarching one.

The penultimate stage of the process was to name the themes and sub-themes, using short statements that were reflective of the content, before finally writing up the Findings section, which I did combined with the Discussion. This merging of findings and discussion is common in qualitative research (Blignault & Ritchie, 2009) as it allows the experiences to be understood through the eyes of the researcher and participants, in conjunction with existing literature to build a fuller picture.

Figure 1 Thematic Map

I decided to use the more novel, Reflexive, TA (Braun & Clarke, 2019) as Braun and Clarke (2019) themselves critiqued its original form, moving forward to adapt it in line with their own reflections. One key aspect I have taken from the newer approach is that the authors now use the term ‘generating’ themes, rather than ‘searching’, to show that it is the role of the researcher, and their interpretation, to create themes, rather than assuming they preexist in the data waiting to be found. Braun and Clarke (2019) explain how there are various methods of TA and what makes Reflexive TA distinct is the importance placed on the researcher’s role in knowledge production. I found this fitted well with the postmodern feminist framework used, and with my own values as a researcher, so through “thoughtful engagement” (Braun & Clarke, 2019, p14) with the data, and the analytic process, I felt in a position to conduct a quality analysis and presentation of the data gathered.

3.10 The Pilot Study

As this was my first experience of qualitative research at this level, I felt it was necessary to do a pilot study with a similar demographic, in preparation for the study itself. As the clubs below the top division in Scotland remain semi-professional at best, I first decided to pilot my questionnaire with a team in the English League, just below the top tier. This meant that they were among the best players in the country, one of the top ranked in the world (FIFA, 2021). By using a similar demographic to the ones proposed for the final study, the responses to

questions were expected to be similar, allowing for improvements to be made to the schedule prior to study commencement. The pilot would also allow me to see any technological issues that may arise, again allowing me to prepare for potential issues.

Through making a contact with the manager at Brighton and Hove Albion during an online webinar, I first piloted the questionnaire with these players. The manager sent the questionnaire to another member of staff at the club who then forwarded it on to players. From the whole squad of almost 20 players, it was disappointing to receive only three responses. I believe this was partly due to the indirect link but did lead to the decision to widen the potential sample in case this happened in the final study; the first learning experience of this pilot study.

Although there were only three responses, it was encouraging that two players offered email addresses to allow me to pilot the interview. However, following some very promising email conversations, none of these ever transpired; another good learning experience (and a bit of a reality check) for me. While this early pilot study did provide me with some very valuable experiences, it did not allow me to test my interview schedule, and online interview skills, so I decided to try again with another group of high-level players. As a result of me deciding to use a wider sample for my final study I was restricted in terms of suitable teams that I could use; a team of a high enough level but not included in my final sample.

Because of this I took advantage of a relationship I have with Scottish Volleyball (SV), where the national team manager was willing to forward the questionnaire to the female squad. Although these women were not elite footballers, they were all playing their sport at the highest level, therefore it was expected that they would be a suitable sample for the purposes of this pilot study (namely testing the research tools). This sample also produced a poor response rate to the questionnaires (five were returned), but three of these respondents provided an email address. Again, although email exchanges followed, only one interview transpired. This player was currently coaching the national age-group team, and had an interesting journey from grassroots through to elite – including a period coaching men – so she was a very interesting candidate to interview.

From both groups of players completing the questionnaires, I was able to analyse the answers

provided and the presentation of responses, to assess the quality and quantity of data gathered. This led me to the overall conclusion that they were successful in gathering the type of information required, and would allow me to draw some good conclusions about the overall experiences and intentions of the players (although I later decided to discard this information from my final presentation of findings due to the quantity rather than quality gathered).

Following the return of the questionnaires I arranged an online interview (via MS Teams) with one player from Scottish Volleyball's 'A' squad. The arranging of this was simple, with a link sent direct via email and both parties accessing the interview with no problems. The interview was recorded (with consent of the participant) and saved to MS Stream where it could be viewed again in future, something that would be important for the final study. In this interview in addition to piloting the full interview schedule, I also discussed the player's experience of completing the questionnaire, to assess to what extent it was user friendly. She confirmed she had no trouble accessing the link, or completing any of the questions, so the questionnaire remained largely unchanged for the final study.

With reference to the interview schedule itself, again the participant had no issues in answering the questions, offering extensive answers without need for much prompting. The answers provided gave a good insight into the player's past experiences and her future intentions, therefore no real alterations were made to these original questions. However, towards the end of the interview I realised I had not actually asked about her journey as a coach. This must have been an oversight in my original planning as I believe this is key to understanding the influences on future intentions, therefore I did ask the question towards the end of the pilot interview, and subsequently added it as an earlier question in the final schedule. Not including a few minutes at the start where I detailed the format of the interview and reiterated general 'housekeeping' the pilot interview lasted just over 33 minutes. Upon reflection I felt I could perhaps have delved a bit further into some answers, to gain a deeper understanding, however this was close to the timings stated in the PIS so it was good to know that I could gain a good depth of information with these questions, with some minutes to spare if required.

Although it was not necessary, I decided to transcribe the interview in its entirety to allow me

practice (having never done this before), and to help me plan the time I would need to allocate for this aspect of my final study. As a competent typist I did feel comfortable doing this, but it was a new experience trying to make sense of some more hard to comprehend statements, and to be typing lots of 'um's and 'eh's, and grammatically incorrect, under-punctuated, statements; this took a bit of getting used to. I typed the interview up the same day I had conducted it and I think this helped me as I could work out some harder to hear parts from memory. I noted this and would strive to do the same in my final study. The transcription took a total of just under four hours which had to be taken into account in my overall plan.

3.11 Summary of methodology

The methodology described above was formulated through careful consideration of my own epistemological and ontological beliefs, in line with the postmodern feminist framework. The decisions made were based on evidence from research, and from trial and error throughout the pilot process. I believe that reading research literature, and reading others' use, and critique, of potential methodologies led me to use one which was appropriate, and likely to provide interesting findings for analysis.

4.0 Findings and Discussion

This section begins with an overview of the themes that were generated from the interview data. Initially it was apparent that there were two overarching themes related to the players' coaching intentions; generally seeing it as an enjoyable career, but that perhaps it was 'out of reach'. However, upon reading left-over codes I realised there was some very valuable information that did not directly relate to the research question, but that was useful in understanding the benefits the players could offer as coaches, therefore would be useful in suggesting recommendations. At this point I created a third theme that would discuss the benefits that the players could bring to the role. Within these three themes, five smaller sub-themes emerged; explained below through a critique of the interviews alongside previous literature.

4.1 Overview of Intentions

Following full transcription and coding it was apparent that, although it was far from a definite career path, none of the players had completely decided against coaching – at least in some capacity – in the future. In some cases, the thought of becoming a coach had simply not entered their mind. This may be related to the ingrained stereotypes in which they have been immersed from an early age. None of the players stated specifically that they saw coaching as a male domain, however previous evidence (e.g. Walker & Bopp, 2011) would suggest this is likely the case, having been involved in such a male dominated environment as they formed their identities.

Again, although not explicitly stated, through delving into the experiences of the players, it was clear that they lacked, and in some cases continue to lack, visible role models; this will be discussed later. One reason for limited consideration of coaching in future, explicitly stated by a number of players, was that – where their contracts allow – they have chosen to focus all of their time and attention on playing, due to the short-term nature of professional football. Players said things like, "I'm still very much in my playing mindset" (Heather) and, "I've not really got too many plans I'm just kind of, focused on football at the moment" (Nicola). However, when asked, the players were happy to give a coaching career some

consideration, often showing signs that they were starting to think of it as a possible career path.

The nature of women's football means most players – including some on full-time professional contracts – have second jobs to make up for the limited earnings available to them, therefore it is likely that this has impacted upon their free time, and therefore some exposure to coaching opportunities. This dual career is common, with 30% of European players combining football with another job, and 46% combining their football with study (FIFPro, 2017). The impact of a dual career in football was examined in Gledhill and Harwood's (2015) investigation of UK based female footballers who had left the sport prior to transitioning to elite status. These players reported a difficulty in juggling roles, citing this as a key reason for their eventual drop-out.

An example of this struggle can be seen here in Sharon, who works full-time while training and playing part-time for one of Scotland's top clubs (although her football schedule could easily be mistaken for that of a full-time player). She discussed her lack of free time, stating, "sometimes I'm literally in the door from work and I'm straight back out to training so, yeah it's, busy". Other players shared similar feelings, for example Heather, one of the players on a full-time contract explained, "now I'm full-time football but I still have another job on the side because ... I'm not in a position where I can say 'oh yeah my wage is enough to support me' ... I've got my own flat so, I've got bills to pay and I've got, you know, I drive a car...". Similar quotes can be found throughout the interviews so, although not explicitly stated as a reason for lack of coaching intentions, it could be interpreted from the more latent meaning that the players simply have not had time to fully consider options.

Added to the lack of time available to gain coaching experience, is the limited opportunity to gain qualifications. This could be seen as an 'informal practice' (Ely & Meyerson, 2000). Discussed in Section 2, these informal practices refer to ways of working that tend to suit the majority, but can indirectly discriminate against some. The players did not expose any direct discrimination, but they discussed how courses take place on a Sunday, which is match day for female players. Some players in this study explained how they found it difficult to fully attend courses between their work, training and matches. Looking at this from a feminist

perspective it could be argued that this is a result of male hegemony, and decisions made to suit the majority.

Margaret, a part-time player who works part-time in another job, explained how it took her far longer than her male counterparts to progress through her coaching awards. "It was always hard to kind of find a course that suited me, because a lot of the courses were either Sunday only, or fell over Saturday and Sunday, and of course with me my football's my priority". Sharon also highlighted the difficulty in juggling these as she said, "I had to use my own holidays for my C-licence that was like, I can't remember 5 days over, 2,3 months and that was taking my own time off work, so it's hard. It is hard." Sharon's experience is also evidence of the additional barriers women face, having to use their own time to take these courses where men on full-time contracts are more likely to be able to do them around their training and match commitments.

Although most players had not settled on a long-term, post-playing, career route, they did acknowledge the need to plan ahead, as they would not earn enough in their short careers in the women's game to allow them to retire when no longer fit enough to play. Although she is playing full-time football for one of the top teams in Scotland, Heather explained that "even females that are playing at the highest level, will have to think about, they're already thinking about retirement and like saving as much money as they possibly can in that window because ... [they don't know] what's coming after their career". Statements such as "I know it's not going to last forever ... [I need] something to, use, and fall back onto" (Elaine) and "I went to uni and stuff like, just for something to fall back on" (Nicola) were common when the players contemplated their future.

Although in many cases a definite decision in relation to a long-term career had not been made, it was evident that there were generally two main categories in relation to coaching intentions, leading to the formation of the initial two overarching themes: 'I'd love to ... but could I?' and 'I've not really considered it'. I have named these themes as I feel they really sum up the two main overriding feelings of the players in relation to their future careers, they are not direct quotations from any one player. It is notable that none of the players ruled out coaching for sure.

As these data were further analysed it became apparent that there were some very useful findings in relation to the benefits that these players could bring to the coaching arena. Although not directly related to the initial research question, these findings would be of use in drawing conclusions about the value of elite players entering coaching, therefore a third overarching theme – “we totally should!” – was added. Under these overarching themes are seven more themes, each with a central organising concept, in line with Braun and Clark’s (2006) model. These themes and subthemes are defined in Table 7.

Table 7 Overview of Themes

Overarching Theme	Sub Theme	Description
I’d love to ... but could I?	I’m not sure I’m up to it	Players show a lack of confidence in their ability as high-level coaches
	I’m not sure it’s worth it	The financial viability and the work-life balance as future coaches is considered
	It’s still a man’s game	Football remains dominated by men, and this has had an (often subconscious) impact on players’ past experiences and future career intentions
I’ve not really considered it	I’ve taken another path	Players tend to have another career alongside football that may influence their post-playing plans
	I’ve not really seen it	There remains a lack of female role models in coaching for players to aspire to. Players also have limited experiences of what being a high-level coach entails
We totally should!	We could be game changers	The players discuss the benefits of being female and playing at a high-level. They also start to wonder if maybe they could ‘make it’
	We just can’t live without football	The players discuss their love for the game and how they struggle to see a future without it

4.2 The Overarching Themes

4.2.1 I'd love to ... but could I?

This overarching theme covers the subthemes and codes related to the players' desire to coach, but the lack of confidence that seems to stifle their ambition. Many, when questioned, admitted that it would be their dream job, but it seems this remains a dream rather than a realistic ambition. The first subtheme here is 'I'm not sure I'm up to it', which focuses on a lack of self-confidence among the players when it comes to coaching, especially at higher levels. This is a frequently cited barrier to women's progression in coaching (e.g. Clarkson, Cox & Thelwell, 2019; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019), and became apparent through speaking to the players in this study.

Separate from any internal doubt, some players also questioned whether the cost-benefit ratio of elite level coaching would be worthwhile, leading to the creation of the subtheme, 'I'm not sure it's worth it'. Here, the players discussed the limited opportunities available to them; the low pay, long hours, etc. – that they feel is often due to their gender – making the 'risk' of choosing coaching over another career perhaps too high. Finally, 'It's still a man's game' is incorporated here as players ponder whether, as women, coaching is an appropriate career for them.

4.2.2 I've not really considered it

This overarching theme also incorporates the 'It's still a man's game' subtheme, as the male dominance of the sport has impacted on players' perceptions of coaching, and whether it is a career that is a realistic ambition for women. Male dominance, inferior treatment and masculine language are discussed in this theme; all highlighting the players' perceptions of coaching as a masculine domain.

In addition, this overarching theme covers 'I've not seen it', a more specific subtheme related to the paucity of role models, especially at earlier stages of their playing careers. Not seeing female coaches when they were forming early opinions, and taking the first step(s) on their own path, appears to have – perhaps subconsciously – reinforced the masculine stereotypes

that prevail at all levels of the game. This may serve to explain the lack of consideration given to a transition to coaching.

The final subtheme related to a hesitance for considering coaching as a career is, 'I've chosen another path'. This subtheme explores how some of the female players have already begun to focus on a non-football career, and how this has impacted upon their coaching ambitions. This scenario is generally a result of the low pay for female players, leading many to go to university for 'something to fall back on' and / or work another job alongside playing to have a reasonable standard of living.

4.2.3 We totally should!

This overarching theme was added after the others as it is not directly related to the coaching intentions of the players, but adds value to the study as it supports the notion that this particular demographic – elite female players – should be provided with opportunities to enter the coaching workforce. The first subtheme included here is 'we could be game changers'. This focuses on the skills, qualities, and experience that the players could bring to the coaching workforce. Secondly, the 'we just can't live without football' subtheme discusses how the players have 'lived' football for so long – often making some real sacrifices to do so – that they cannot see a future without it. One of the players summed up the feelings of the others when she said "It's always been my one true love ... I just love it ..." (Heather). Similarly, Margaret explicitly stated that, for her, "staying in the game in some capacity ... for me is a must it's a necessity I love the game..." Therefore, it is likely that many, if not all, will remain involved in the game in some capacity upon retirement.

4.3 The Sub-Themes

4.3.1 I'm not sure I'm up to it

In line with previous research (e.g. Clarkson, Cox & Thelwell, 2019; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019) self-confidence appears to be a key factor limiting female players when it comes to their career intentions. In the interviews, a general lack of confidence was apparent in relation to coaching and, more specifically, coaching at the highest level. Players said things like,

“I’ve not got the personality to be coaching a team like that ... I’d probably rather stick to, you know, youth national levels or a club team” (rather than aiming to coach the full national squad) (Nicola)

“I would need to get a lot of experience probably playing, younger age groups first and working your way up” (Heather)

“[The UEFA Pro Licence] seems so far away because (laugh) again I just think of, kind of older top coaches getting to that level ... maybe I’m not as good as maybe I thought I might have been (laugh)..” (Sharon)¹

This supports the findings of Cunningham, Sagas and Ashley (2003) who concluded that women were more likely to leave the profession, rather than aspire to reach the top. Similarly, Kentta (2020) found that Swedish high-performance coaches reported a lower perceived competence, especially in comparison to men. With the nature of football in this country, it is likely that where women do progress, that they will work alongside men, and this may be a factor in the limited confidence they seem to have in applying for high-level jobs.

Investigations into football coaching in this country and worldwide (MacInnes, 2017; Filho & Rettig, 2018; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019; Thompson, Whitaker & Bunyan, 2020) show the gender imbalance widening as the standard of coaching goes up which, although not explicitly stated by the players in this study, is likely to have reinforced the gendered stereotypes that prevail in sport (Burton & Lavoie, 2016) and leadership (Anderson, 2008; Koenig, 2011). In turn, these stereotypes may reinforce the notion that women are more suited to supporting roles when it comes to coaching, making it harder for them to feel confident enough to aim for high-level jobs.

Because many players simply had not considered coaching it is difficult to make any strong suppositions, however in analysing the conversations – and sometimes the latent meaning behind the spoken word – there was a change in their visible ego when the players were asked about whether they could be a future Premier League, or national team coach. When reacting to these questions it was common for the players to become more diffident. In hesitating in

¹ These types of comments I felt really resonated with me, evidenced in my reflexive diary. For this reason in my analysis I believe my own experiences helped me really understand how this lack of belief could impact.

their speech, and looking away from the camera, there were signs of awkwardness at the suggestion, again perhaps related to a lack of self-confidence in this environment.

It was encouraging to hear that there were some players in the sample that were striving to coach at higher levels, however low self-confidence remained apparent in statements like,

“I think I’d, like to slowly progress ... I think it’s dangerous jumping, even if I had my A Licence, to jump into something that is massive, dangerous maybe. Just to slowly work my way up, kind of, get past the A Li-, eh sorry B Licence, potentially go on the A Licence, further if that’s an option ... be an assistant for many years and kind of work my way up” (Elaine).

This statement clearly suggests that confidence is a factor in this player’s aspirations and expectations.

In critiquing the language used, words such as “dangerous”, “massive” jump, “potentially” move up the coaching levels really highlight the air of caution shown by female players in relation to their abilities. Similarly, Sharon felt the need to, “slowly progress”, get “a good 2, 3, 4 years’ experience before ... [even thinking of the] Pro Licence”, and “try to get involved if it’s with [a Premier League’s] first team, or with the younger teams to try and get some involvement with coaching” before thinking about applying for a more prestigious job. The use of the word ‘try’ repetitively here suggests the level of doubt over the player’s own coaching ability.

This cautious approach to coaching is in line with previous studies of female coaches. For example, national level female coaches interviewed by Norman (2014) all agreed that many developing coaches did not believe in their abilities enough to challenge the patriarchal control of the profession. One of the coaches said,

“I can think of a couple of players of mine who would make fantastic coaches and I have been astounded when they’ve turned around and said, ‘I am not good enough, I’m not able to do it’”.

This is just one example of the lack of self-belief the coaches in Norman’s study had experienced in potential future coaches, and it is hard not to draw comparisons to the sample here. Although not stated as explicitly, there was some evidence of a lack of self-belief. For

example, “I did question if I was ... right for it” (Linsay) and “I don’t know if I have, you know, the personality to do that [coach at a higher level]” (Nicola). With the capital they will have accrued throughout their playing careers, along with the qualifications many have already achieved, it seems there is a mismatch between this capital, and the apprehension they have about transitioning straight to coaching at the highest level.

This likelihood of women to downplay their qualities, “I can only manage 90% of this, so therefore I can’t do it” (Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019; p9), in contrast to men who are more likely to show over-confidence, “I can manage 10% of this, so therefore I can do it” (ibid) has been highlighted before. Norman’s (2014) study of coaches who had all succeeded in gaining positions as national head coaches, also highlighted an unwillingness of developing coaches to aim for elite positions. Although the coaches who were interviewed by Norman were working at the highest level themselves, they discussed how most women they knew were happy to coach at club level, rather than striving for national level jobs.

A perceived ‘ceiling’ in terms of coaching expectation is evidenced in the current study in statements such as, “no, definitely not the Scotland job but (laugh) I wouldn’t [want] ... as high as that” (Nicola). The reaction of the players to the suggestion that they could coach the Scotland team highlighted their feelings of unease about aiming for the most prestigious jobs, even when perhaps they have the necessary skills and experience. When analysing the underlying meaning of Nicola’s statement, it could be suggested that it is not that the player does not *want* to coach the national team, but that perhaps she feels she is not capable, or that she is capable but unsure if she would be accepted. Through analysing the language and non-verbal content of a number of the interviews, as well as the explicitly spoken word, there were hints throughout that an underlying lack of confidence, and fear of failure, may be inhibiting aspirations.

It is not uncommon for those who lack experience to be lower in confidence, however there are players in the current study who have experienced coaching, and these experiences have actually led to a feeling of incompetence. An example that illustrates this comes from Linsay – an experienced player at the highest level – who explained how she questioned the respect she was given by players she had coached in the past. As well as *what* she said, *how* she said it highlighted a lack of confidence, with lots of “um”s and nervous laughs,

“there was times where I did question if I was em, if I was right for it in terms of like (laugh) just em, what’s the word em, like I wasn’t sure I had enough authority and things like that, em so just little things like, like I wasn’t sure, em”.

This sign of unease contrasted with the way she spoke when discussing her playing career, suggested a real disparity between her confidence as a player and future coach.

Although this lack of confidence could be argued to be misplaced, previous literature suggests it can be more difficult for female coaches to gain the respect they deserve from their athletes and other coaches (Walker & Bopp, 2011; LaFontaine & Kamphoff, 2016). This is concerning as it is unlikely that players’ confidence will increase as long as they feel under-appreciated / disrespected in their early experiences, leading it to perhaps become a self-fulfilling prophecy.

Following earlier studies (e.g. LaFontaine & Kamphoff, 2016; Norman, Rankin-Wright and Allison, 2018) presenting female coaches who struggled to gain the respect they deserved, Kentta and colleagues (2020) also found examples of female coaches whose male colleagues continued to look upon them as inferior. This perception of inferiority was summed up by a coach in Sawiuk, Lewis and Taylor’s (2021) critique of English coach education courses. One coach explained her “biggest pet hate” is the use of phrases like, “you’re a good female coach, aren’t you” (p13); stressing the inclusion of this extra adjective was both unnecessary and demeaning.

Lack of respect is likely to impact any potential coach’s self-confidence and desire to continue. In their study of female grassroots coaches in the UK, Murray, Lord and Lorimer (2020) found examples of women in various sports experiencing a lack of respect. One example came from a football and basketball coach who stated, “yes you had to *gain* the respect instead of just walking on and instantly having the respect like guys would”. As these early experiences are likely to have a real impact upon future aspirations it could be argued that gendered early experiences may be at least part of the reason that the players in this study – the majority of whom started coaching at grassroots levels – had not considered aiming higher. Coaches in Murray, Lord and Lorimer’s (2020) study discussed their need to show competence as performers to gain the respect of their athletes and this is something that came through in the current study, for example Sharon explained how she joined in with the boys she coached, to show her playing ability.

Lack of confidence was apparent again in relation to coaching in the men's game, evidenced in statements such as, "I don't know if I've got the thick skin ... it's maybe a bit more, intimidating 'cause it's not the normal yet which is sad" (Kyla). Although it was uncommon, three of the players did say that they would consider coaching men's football, where more opportunities for full-time employment lie. However, here not only inherent lack of self-confidence was observable, but also confidence stemming from their predecessors. As well as their own self-doubt, the players felt that lack of success by women before them limited their chances of success. This was summed up by Heather when she stated, "I would quite like, enjoy working with guys but, I don't know if there's been enough success with other females coaching guys for us to allow those opportunities to keep happening".

This lack of challenging the norm was highlighted in Walker and Bopp's (2011) study of female coaches working with male athletes. Although the women interviewed had been successful in gaining these roles, they did highlight the challenges they faced in entering and progressing in the male dominated environment. Walker and Bopp's (2011) study was conducted in America, however, like many of the women in the current study, there seemed a general acceptance that their gender would at least hinder their progress. One of the coaches in Walker and Bopp's (2011) study stated,

"I just think that's the way that society is; it's just expected in men's sports that men coach men. It's just like that. That's just the way it is, and no one's tried to change it and do anything about it".

This is a concern as it seems now, ten years later, that women are still reluctant to challenge this norm, thus encouraging the self-perpetuating cycle.

4.3.2 I'm not sure it's worth it

Through speaking to the players, it was evident that although they did not dislike the idea of coaching as a career, they found it hard to see how it could provide them with a good enough wage to allow a reasonable work-life balance. Work-life balance is frequently cited as a barrier to coaching for women because of the long / irregular hours and travelling that it generally entails (Burton & LaVoi, 2016; Smith et al, 2019; Ronkainen, Sleeman & Richardson, 2020). This is not a gender specific barrier, but evidence suggests women who take on

coaching roles are more likely to have feelings of guilt (Ladda, 2015; Carson, McCormack & Walsh, 2018), possibly due to the traditional stereotype that a woman's role in a family is that of care giver (Hardin & Taylor, 2016; Stick, 2017). In their study of both male and female high-level coaches in Sweden, Kentta and colleagues (2020) found that many highlighted work-life balance as a struggle. Coaches discussed evening work and travel demands as a challenge to family life. These recent findings suggest having children are a key challenge to coaching and, although not a gender specific issue, it did appear from these interviews that men were less likely to face this challenge. Furthermore they appeared to the authors to be unlikely to be understanding of the women who did.

The players in the current study are generally young and independent, and family commitments were only mentioned by a few. However, it was clear that with their current schedules they often had little in the way of free time, as had been the case throughout their careers. From early adolescence, when they had to move away from boys' football, many of the players had to travel to train and play as there were few girls' teams that could provide the level of challenge that they sought for their development.

Sharon explained how, while at school, she made the three-and-a-half hour each-way journey to train with her club twice a week, as well as a similar journey for an elite training squad, and a game at the weekend. Similarly, while at university – studying towards a degree on a football scholarship – Heather's typical day involved 7am classes, a training session and afternoon classes, before leaving university at 4pm to travel to her club's training session; arriving home at 10pm ready to do it all again the next day. This juggle of studies and travel was common among the players, and it could be argued that this busy lifestyle prepared them for their life as professional footballers, as the majority – even those on full-time contracts – continue to have to manage training and playing alongside another job.

The information provided in the interviews suggested that in Scotland only three teams were in a position to offer (a very limited number of) full-time coaching contracts, with most team's coaches employed on a voluntary and / or part-time basis. These limited opportunities, coupled with the fact that becoming a coach in Scotland – even at the highest level – will need to be combined with a second income, has led the players to question the appeal of the job. The players see their own coaches juggling different jobs, evidenced in quotes such as,

“you know my own managers have their own jobs and they’re doing it part-time, they do get paid by [the club] but it’s not it’s not substantial enough is it?” (Kyla)

“we’ve got (assistant coach) that’s eh, em, he’s a volunteer” (Sharon)

The players in this study accept the sacrifice of leisure time as part of being a footballer:

“yeah [I] don’t have much life apart from my [second job] and em football” (Heather)

“I do ten-hour shifts ... we even train Saturday mornings ... I’m literally I the door from work and I’m straight back out to training” (Sharon)

“I’ve sacrificed so much ... not being able to spend time with my family ... more sacrifices you make every week ... they’re almost normal for you now” (Elaine)

“I can’t go out on Saturday to the shops or go do something ‘cause I’ve been training during the week and I need to spend more time on my work ... kind of comes down to sacrifices” (Lisa)

However, having sacrificed so much for their playing careers, they wondered if they wanted to continue this lifestyle into the future. A quote that illustrates this well again comes from Heather who pondered,

“is there enough opportunities for me to go and do coaching at the level that I want to coach at, and make a decent enough living off it without having to like run yourself into the ground, like, I don’t know. I’ve done that for my playing career so, do you really want to go and do that for your coaching career as well?”.

Similarly, Kyla stated, “I would probably love full-time coaching ... but ... you still want to have kind of same standard of living”.

Linked to the limited earning opportunities available to women in a coaching role, this study also supports the finding of others (e.g. MacInnes, 2017; Thompson, Whittaker & Bunyon, 2020) who explained how the cost of gaining the qualifications required to progress are barriers in themselves. Although the cost is the same for both genders, there appears to be a better cost-reward ratio for men who are likely to earn more upon entering the profession (MacInnes, 2017; Norman, Rankin-Wright & Allison, 2018), largely due to the greater earning potential in the male game. This cost-benefit ratio appeared to be a consideration for the players in the current sample.

Nicola explained, “I might do they coaching badges at some point again, I don’t know, I’m not really sure at the moment if that’s something I want to go down, again, as I say they’re quite expensive”. She went on to explain, “I don’t want to do it and then, maybe not use it ... you know get to the age when I retire and think, ‘oh I don’t actually really want to do that’ ‘cause they are thousands of pounds”.

This could be related to findings in Norman, Rankin-Wright and Allison’s (2018) study where female coach educators based in England discussed the limited opportunities to be in paid employment, affecting their choice to progress to higher levels of qualifications.

This outlay for coaching courses will have more financial implications for women, unlike their male counterparts who earn “probably, three nearly three times, four times five times the amount” (Heather) than they do, leading them to perhaps put it off until they are clearer about their future plans. The result of this, however, is that by the time the players have accrued enough money, or are at the latter stages of their careers, they may already have moved towards another career.

Throughout the interviews it was evident that the players struggle to see coaching as a financially rewarding career. They have seen a lack of gender equity in relation to finances throughout their playing careers, supporting recent FIFPro (2017) statistics which highlight the difference in funding between the male and female game across the world. An earlier study by Walker and Bopp (2011) concluded that women working in men’s sport were often appointed to less important roles, as did a more recent study by Clarkson, Cox and Thelwell (2019). Therefore, the current sample support the notion that as long as women see their role solely in female sport and / or lower positions, they are unlikely to turn down opportunities in other careers to focus on coaching.

4.3.3 It’s still a man’s game

At first glance the interviews do little to support the plethora of evidence that presents a negative picture of male dominance in football, as the players tend to speak very highly of the majority of men that they have encountered throughout their careers. However much of the information presented in this theme comes from a more analytical interpretation of the type

of language used, and non-spoken word, rather than overt verbal content. From the beginning the players discussed their early careers with much fondness, with only minimal suggestion of any feeling of awkwardness at being the only girl in a boys' team.

It was interesting to note that although they described positive experiences, as the interviews progressed it became apparent that the players were making a real effort to show that they felt privileged to be in the position that they are now; being paid to play a sport that they love. However, more implicitly, there was some suggestion that this feeling of privilege was one that they believed they *should* feel and / or a feeling that has been influenced by previous experiences; experiences which have led to an ingrained feeling of inferiority. This feeling of privilege does add to the notion that gender stereotypes have had an impact as there appears little evidence that professional male footballers – although likely grateful that they earn so much money for playing the sport – feel they earn more than they are entitled. Conversely, all of the women in this sample showed feelings of extreme gratitude that they are able to play professional football, even though despite being among the best female footballers in the country, many do not earn enough money to live on.

This feeling of gratitude for what men tend to accept as the norm has been criticised by Florence Williams, a Welsh rugby player. Quoted in Anstiss (2021; p251) she said, "I'm sick of female athletes having to be constantly grateful". Williams went on to say she was grateful for the progress to date, but was keen to state parity remains a vision. A vision that through "collective voices" perhaps may become a reality, reinforcing the importance of work such as this that allows female athletes' voices to be heard.

The players interviewed in this study all play in women's teams now, but they all began playing with boys, therefore key influencers in their formative years tended to be male:

"I started playing, mainly with my dad and my brother just in the garden" (Lisa)

"just kicking a ball about at school with the boys" (Sharon)

"a lot of my pals growing up at school were boys" (Heather)

"I've got four boy cousins they all played football and my uncle played Highland League, Dad's really big into football ..." (Kyla)

“it all stemmed from my dad who at that point played football” (Margaret)

These early experiences were similar across the board, and all tended to be positive. The experiences, however, serve as an early indication of the minority status the players could expect to face throughout their careers. Again, it seems that these women’s personalities, from a young age, put them at ease in male dominated environments, and there was very little mention of any feeling that they did not belong among the boys with whom they played.

Lynsey was the only player in the sample who discussed how she quit football for a short period as she “was the only girl and I think I didn’t really like that so I stopped for a bit ... well I just didn’t go back (laugh)”. She was not put off for too long though as she joined a boys’ team a few years later, only moving to a girls’ team when playing with boys was no longer allowed. Elaine also played boys’ football at the beginning and although she felt “lucky there because ... [she] always felt part of the team”. Her twin sister “didn’t enjoy it at all” and dropped out (restarting only when a girls’ team became available). Margaret summed up most of the girls’ early experiences when she said, “I never ever saw myself as a girl playing in a boys’ team, I just saw myself as a footballer.” This statement (and many others throughout the interviews) again reinforces the notion that this demographic (current high-level players), unlike many other women, feel comfortable in male dominated environments, having socially constructed their gender from their life experiences (namely those related, but not exclusive, to their sport).

The two examples of girls dropping out (Lynsey and Elaine’s sister) are more in line with previous literature (Casey et al., 2009; Lyu & Gill, 2011) and thus worthy of further study. However, as the research question here focuses on elite players’ coaching intentions, drop out at early stages of playing will not be a major focus of this discussion. It must be emphasised though, although these women felt comfortable playing with boys when they were younger, it does not necessarily mean they will feel at ease entering the male dominated environment of coaching where their self-confidence appears lower, adding support to the belief that personality traits can be context dependent.

The positive early experiences of playing football appear to be a real influencer on the way the players now reflect on the sport; feeling grateful for the experiences they have had, and

continue to have. Again, from the spoken word, and analysis of some implicit meaning, it was clear that the players downplay any notion that football is viewed as a 'man's game'. However, there was some evidence of an early indication that they were in fact 'different', in statements such as, "when a girl showed up it wasn't normal, for the opposition so I think I just wanted to prove them wrong. Just their perception of 'girls don't belong in football'" (Elaine). Elaine goes on to describe that she always felt very included in her team, but this quote shows that she did experience a level of gender discrimination, and suggestion of inferiority – from those out with her team – early in her career. ²

This need to prove oneself has been highlighted previously; coaches in Norman's (2010) study explaining how they had to show they had playing ability to be accepted as coaches. From the interviews it appeared that the main place this need to show their ability was felt was on coach education courses, a common finding in recent literature (e.g. Lewis, Roberts & Andrews, 2018; Stoney, 2019). Through interviewing UEFA A level female coaches, Sawiuk, Lewis and Taylor (2021) found that even at the highest level, women continue to feel the need to prove themselves upon starting a course. Related to coaching itself, the coaches in Kentta and colleagues (2020) study also discussed a need to overachieve in the role to be accepted as an equal.

The reason for this feeling of a need to overperform in coach education is perhaps twofold. Firstly, again as self-efficacy can be very much context specific (Bandura, 1994), the players – whose job status likely provided them external assurance of their ability – had less experience and thus confidence in their ability as coaches. Secondly, as they progressed as players, these women went on to play in girls'/women's teams and leagues, where they were no longer in a minority as players (although many continued to have male coaches). The reason for this move to women's football was almost always a result of the then SFA ruling that teams must be single gender from age 12 (this ruling has since changed to allow co-ed teams until age 15) (SFA, 2011).

² Again, my reflexive diary showed me how my own experiences helped me understand the subconscious impact. I too felt very included in my coaching roles, but in hindsight wonder if I truly was. These comments and my own reflection provided some very interesting data here.

Most of the players in the current study had been on at least one coach education course and, with the exception of the female-only course that was put on for the national level players (discussed later), all were in a minority; often the only woman in the group. This minority status as a female coach supports previous literature (e.g. Lewis, Roberts & Andrews, 2018; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019) which consistently shows women outnumbered by men on coach education courses, increasingly so as the level progresses. Even where the players had attended female-only courses the educators were male, doing little to break down stereotypes of the masculine nature of coaching and leadership. The impact of this was discussed by Norman, Rankin-Wright and Allison (2018) who found that lack of diversity among coach educators was a real influence on coaches' ability to relate to a tutor and perhaps see themselves progressing through the levels similarly.

The lack of female representation was not a concern for these players, most expressing a preference for the mixed-gender ones, illustrated in the following quotes:

“I found it enjoyable” (Sharon)

“I enjoyed it because you're hearing different people's stories, different backgrounds”
(Margaret)

“it's very nice learning from all these different players and coaches” (Heather)

The way the players spoke about the courses made it clear that they really did enjoy, and benefit from, them, however there was often a 'but' or a subconscious need to justify any inequality. For example, Margaret was very complimentary of the coach educators she had experienced when she said, “the content of the courses are all very kind of gender neutral”.

This contrasts with other recent investigations of women's experiences of coach education (Lewis, Roberts & Andrews, 2018; Fasting, Sand & Nordstrand, 2019; Knoppers et al., 2021; Sawiuk, Lewis & Taylor, 2021), where any references to the women's game were largely neglected. This may be due to the different culture between the countries, however, in analysing the language used by the current sample, words such as “kind of” suggests the players are not convinced there was parity. Margaret followed her statement with, “I mean there'll always be a slip of the tongue from the coaches and they'll say, 'right guys'”. This use of masculine language appears common, again highlighted in the aforementioned studies.

Looking at the language, when Margaret says, 'I mean' this again seems to suggest an acceptance of this as the norm, and that as a female player she has no right to question or challenge it.

Sawiuk, Lewis and Taylor (2021) found that the women they interviewed were unsure about how to deal with the masculine language, one asking, "do I alienate myself or do I become one of them, one of the lads?" (p8). Some of the coaches in Lewis, Roberts and Andrews' (2018) study also discussed their frustration at being referred to as 'lads'. One coach did continually remind the educator of the inappropriate use of language, but he took no notice, and the authors concluded that the language used by the coach educators played a key part in reinforcing gendered stereotypes.

There was no evidence of any of the players in the current study challenging the gendered language, further suggesting that they have accepted it as the norm in the football environment. Added to this acceptance that masculine language would be used by male coaches, it was interesting to note that some of the players themselves used masculine language, even when discussing their own experiences (e.g. Lisa talked about the importance of "man management"). This could be argued as a result of pressure to take on characteristics of the dominant group – in line with previous research (e.g. LaFontaine and Kamphoff 2016) – or simply an acceptance that this is the terminology associated with the sport and therefore accepted as the norm.

The final part of Margaret's quote – discussed above – is, "you're like 'well' but, again that doesn't offend me at all, but as I say it is certainly getting better", reaffirming a resignation that it is not worth the challenge, and confirming, although it may not be a problem now, there may well have been more of an issue in the past. It would be impossible to be sure whether the player is offended at all, but Margaret certainly appeared to be being honest about it not bothering her, her body language open and confident, no suggestion of trying to cover up any unease. Furthermore, there was no indication of any real offensive behaviour, such as the overt sexism encountered by females in previous studies (e.g. Sawiuk, Lewis & Taylor, 2021).

Another example of a player acknowledging that she feels that she is in a better position than her predecessors is Heather, who explains,

“mindsets are a lot different and, the males within the coaches [courses] that I’ve been on certainly, actually respect you and listen to you and want to, want to be close to you and want to, to hear from your experiences and, hear your stories of, of both playing and coaching so, that’s certainly been, been good because I know previously, that certainly wasn’t the case”.

Here she explicitly states that she knows there has been discrimination in the past and, although she never says she has faced any, a critical interpretation of her wording would perhaps suggest otherwise; her use of the word, “certainly”, followed by “actually”, showing a lack of certainty over the level and nature of respect granted to her.

A key reason the current sample of players gave for their positive experiences on the courses was that they felt that women’s football was included by the SFA, unlike in the experiences of those on FA courses described above. However, from looking at the nature of this I would posit that this *inclusion* is largely superficial. Kyla mentioned how Shelley Kerr (then the Scotland Women’s manager) had some input and, “yeah they spoke about it as well so obviously it’s something they want to encourage”. Sharon, although the only woman on her B-licence, “felt very comfortable on the course” because “they kind of knew about women’s football”.

This contrasts with the findings in Sawiuk, Lewis and Taylor’s (2021) study where the following quote is representative of many others,

“the lack of female content affected my motivation, I would like to link what I am learning to female sport, but there is no opportunity to. No references, no talk, no pictures, no audio, all-male content” (p9).³

Although the participants in Clarkson, Cox and Thelwell’s (2019) study highlighted some examples of discrimination, they too reported this was happening less than previously. Going back to the players in the current study, an analysis of the language used suggests (i.e. “spoke about it”, “kind of”) that the time spent on the women’s game was minimal, if apparent at all.

³ Again, when reflecting on this during my analysis I realised how male dominated my coach education courses tended to be, especially my UEFA B Licence.

It should be noted though that there was indeed an attempt by the SFA – on mixed courses attended by these players – to include the women’s game in their education structure, and this should be further developed.

Kyla added to the interesting contrast between the spoken word and more latent meaning of the players’ experience as she also said that she did not feel that there was any issue with gender discrimination, and that “everybody was really nice”. However, this acceptance did not seem to be given to the women automatically upon arrival, supporting findings of two recent studies of coach education experiences in England (Lewis, Roberts & Andrews, 2018; Clarkson, Cox & Thelwell, 2019). This goes back to the belief that female players need to prove themselves, showing that there are some similarities in experiences of coach education across the two countries.

Kyla summed this up when she said, “sometimes you’re like ‘oh there’s a girl on this course’ you know at the beginning but after a few days a[of] being there like everybody was eh really nice”. This was said as a compliment to the people on the course however it is clear that this ‘being nice’ was not without condition. Sharon also explained how she gained acceptance, only after showing her competence: “when they kind of see you joining in the exercises they might think, ‘oh you know what maybe girls are alright (laugh) at playing football’”. Kyla went on to tell how the male participants on the courses are

“always like, they don’t really know what to say to you at the start I always think they’re quite quiet and stand-offish but then once you’ve been there a few days and I think, you know sometimes it sounds stupid but like you have to like do the drills or take something and I think once they realise, ‘oh, oh she actually can understand football’ or ‘she knows what she’s talking about’ they then start, chatting to you..”

This mirrors the findings of Norman (2010) who found that female coaches felt they had to show their ability to gain the respect they deserved.

For this reason, Kyla chose to,

“always stick my hand up early ‘cause I’m just like no I want to like, not show off that I’m a good player but show off that like I am competent like I can control the ball and all that and I think that sets like, a good tone or respect for you early on”.

It is commendable that the players are willing and able to gain acceptance but the fact they have to do so provides further support to the argument that women continue to be looked upon as second class citizens when it comes to leadership in sport (Walker & Bopp, 2011; LaFontaine & Kamphoff, 2016; Norman & Rankin-Wright, 2018). It also shows that for this player – and others in the current study – their self-efficacy as players allows them to show their competence and thus gain acceptance. However previous literature often suggests that a lack of confidence (perhaps more so in less experienced players) can lead many women to be put off attending these courses. Again, this highlights the uniqueness of this particular demographic.

Although they did not explicitly disclose any feeling of lack of respect overall, the way the players talked did suggest that perhaps it was ‘brushed over’, or perhaps on occasion it went unnoticed. Kyla stated that,

“I didn’t feel that they were disrespecting or anything I think, em, yeah they were quite quite good once they understood you, you played a bit and knew a bit they they were quite comfortable with you”.

The wording of this quote shows just how the players’ perception of equity perhaps differs to the true meaning as a deeper analysis of this statement shows a level of disrespect was apparent; i.e. the repeated use of the word “quite” in describing the level of acceptance. As well as the language itself, it is interesting to note the stuttering, showing a hesitation and perhaps unease about what she was saying. Again, this could suggest that the players are simply so used to this inherent disrespect that they do not feel in a position to question it.

A feeling of intimidation – in relation to male domination – has been cited as a reason for many women failing to progress through coaching courses (Norman, Rankin-Wright and Allison, 2018), leading to a widening gender gap at higher levels of performance. Norman, Rankin-Wright and Allison’s (2018) study involved both coaches and coach educators in England, some whom had undertaken mixed courses, others female only. Data in these interviews showed women feeling a higher level of intimidation on mixed courses where they tended to be in a minority. It was encouraging to hear that the players in the current study have not felt this way, although it is likely this is almost completely a result of their playing

ability (something that many aspiring coaches do not have to the same degree), and perhaps ingrained tolerance of masculine culture and dominance.

The players in this sample hinted that they were aware that their experiences may have been different had they not been able to perform to a high standard. For example, Sharon pondered,

“on that coaching course although I was really impressed with, you know them taking an interest, like I say would it have been different if I didn’t play at such a high level? Em again not that they would have been nasty to me but there might not have been that interest in, again in women’s football.”

This feeling that their ability proved them worthy of their place, and subsequent enjoyment of the course, was apparent throughout the interviews. For example:

“they probably saw that we played at a decent level ... mutual respect” (Linsay)

“once they understood you, you played a bit and knew a bit they were quite comfortable with you” (Kyla)

Another interesting discussion point related to the subconscious perception that football remains, to an extent, a male domain, is shown through the players’ declaration of their feelings of comfort in the company of men. The players all discussed how they enjoy male company, having been involved in male dominated environments since their early football experiences. Heather went as far as to say, “I’m [sic] always been more comfortable around a guys’ environment”. She explained her friends at school were mainly boys and through playing boys’ football, like the others in the sample, this is likely to have almost inducted her into this masculine culture.

For those players with second jobs, these are often in male dominated environments, or certainly mixed ones (none of the players work in predominately female dominated roles), again perhaps ‘forcing’ them to be able to function in the masculine culture. Kyla explained how at work (a male dominated career) she is seen as “the girl that plays football” and that this is a useful “tool” in finding “common ground”, aiding her working relationships. Again, this finding emphasises how the current sample is quite distinct from many other groups of women who have not grown up immersed in such a male dominated environment. Although

only a small select sample, however, these experiences may make them ideal candidates as high-level coaches, as will be discussed in the 'we could be game changers' theme, thus reinforcing the need for further research and perhaps separate consideration to be made when planning for the future progression of this demographic.

Although this theme generally describes the negative impact of the 'man's world' in which football exists, there is some evidence to suggest that progress is being made. One example of this is the "bespoke B-licence" that the Scotland squad had been offered. This course, fully funded by the SFA, was "something that, I couldn't, I didn't feel like I could pass up" (Margaret). In addition, the goalkeepers were also given a similar opportunity for the goalkeeping licence. This is evidence that the national governing body are working to increase female representation in coaching, something that has been acknowledged by the players as they say, "they know that, what they're ... giving out and paying out now they'll, they'll certainly and hopefully reap the rewards, longer-term".

Some of the players also discussed how their clubs helped with funding courses and provided opportunities to gain experience. This investment by clubs and governing bodies shows that there is a real attempt to move away from the male-dominance that persists in the coaching of the sport. Although the female players acknowledge the opportunities available to them, it is clear they do not see them as an entitlement. Their comments suggest they feel privileged to have been offered these opportunities. One quote that illustrates this comes from Heather who said, "we see that [funded coaching courses] as such an amazing opportunity but maybe that's just because, we're now being drilled into us that that's the social norm, like you know". Similarly, Margaret said she would "have been foolish to ... pass up" the chance to do a B licence funded by the national team.

Although they speak highly of the opportunities they have been given, the players also told of how in the past they have felt secondary to their male counterparts. Heather, again, provided a good example of this. She told of how at her former club, her team (the women's first team) were put off the pitch if the under eight boys' team wanted to use it. This, she said, was when she really realised how women were regarded in relation to men. This experience of Heather's is in line with experiences of the elite coaches in Knoppers and

colleagues (2021) study, suggesting that if they were to go on to coach they would continue to feel inferior.

An example of the inferior status granted to women in Knoppers and colleagues' (2021) study is a woman who was unsuccessful in applying for a job of a men's team. Although she was more than suitably qualified and experienced, she was overlooked in favour of a man without even the requested licence. Of her experience Heather exclaimed, "I was like 'wow', that when I was first exposed to the fact that, women is so far off it". Heather is a player who seems at times to really try to over-compensate for the strive for equality. This was evident in statements such as, "I would say I'm quite a feminist but not in the sense where I do think that all women should get, I do think that sometimes we, pry [play] on that a little bit and some women get fast tracked when they aren't quite right for the job".

Sharon also explained,

"I find it hard sometimes when they try and, this might sound (laugh) quite bad but promote females and push females in, it's not just coaching it's in my [full-time job] as well they try and get you promoted 'cause you're female and again that just doesn't really sit well".

Again, this nervous laugh indicates an air of unease in discussing the subject and could be interpreted as an attempt to over-compensate for any feelings of unfair treatment.

It seemed that the players try to justify why they tend to have subordinate status, highlighted in another passage from Heather:

"I can understand why females don't get paid the same as male at the minute because we don't bring in the same revenue, however ... we've never had the same investment, so how do you know that the game couldn't have grown to that level if it had the same investment ... nobody's given it an opportunity to grow ... it does frustrate me ... but yeah there isn't the same revenue there so, if the game isn't bringing in the money you can't ... you wouldn't give a top sales person the same money as somebody who's only selling two or three cars ... but you need to also weigh up the fact that female hasn't had the same investment ..."

This statement really shows Heather being torn between frustration at the lesser status and investment, and what seems to be a feeling that she has to justify the situation, which from

previous reading, could be explained through this ingrained stereotype of sport as a masculine domain that women are not in a position to challenge. It is true that women's football brings less revenue, however Maggie Murphy, the General Manager of Lewes FC Women, echoes Sharon's thoughts as she said:

"We are not blind to the fact that women's football doesn't yet generate as much money from revenue and broadcasting, but then there hasn't been any *investment*. How can I generate bigger crowds, or how can I go on a marketing drive, if I have just won £2000 in my FA Cup? Imagine what I could do with £18,000." (Murphy, cited in Anstiss, 2021; p132),

It is becoming increasingly common for prize money to be equal for men and women (with football being a key exception), however this is only part of the story. Lewes FC is leading the way in not only paying the same wages for both women's and men's teams, but also providing the same marketing budgets and allowing both teams use of the same pitch and training facilities. It would be interesting to see if the women's game in general would bring in more revenue if other teams followed suit.

4.3.4 I've taken another path

Related to the above theme, the reason many players do not see coaching as a future ambition is that they have already embarked on, or at least studied towards, another (more financially secure) career before and / or while playing. Although participation numbers have been increasing, women's football remained amateur as these players were growing up. With very limited opportunities to earn money from playing, it was not until they reached higher levels that they started to see football as a potential career path. Without exception, the players all said that they did dream of being a professional footballer, but they did not really see it as a realistic ambition until later on, by which point they had already considered other possibilities. For example, Nicola explained, "I suppose it's been a long-term ambition but, at the same time growing up, it wasn't really a thing that you could do ... so I went to uni ... something to fall back on".

Related to this is the earning potential in women's professional football. Although the top leagues pay a 'full-time' wage, this wage is generally at the lower end of the scale, therefore women who choose to play football often have to sacrifice greater earnings and working

conditions that they would get in an alternative career (Thompson, cited in Anstiss, 2021). This perceived lack of opportunity was cited as a key reason that promising female players left the sport in Gledhill and Harwood's (2015) study. While showing promise in football, the girls they asked were reluctant to neglect other aspects of their life – including social life and education – for a career that seemed a distant dream. Gledhill and Harwood (2015) explained that this was a result of the interaction of various social agents, including parents, coaches and teachers. This lack of opportunity was summed up in a quote from a coach who said,

“the problem for our girls is ... [with a few exceptions] ... they can't make a living playing football. Trying to make a professional career as a coach is not much easier because of the culture in men's football” (p25).

Although the players in the current study did not drop out of the sport – and have gone on to play at a high level – they did explain how they did not see football as a career in the earlier stages of development, and were therefore reluctant to neglect other aspects of their lives. None of the players in the current study allowed themselves to expect that they could make a career out of playing. For example, Elaine “always wanted to become a footballer ... [but] it was more a distant dream”. Similarly, Nicola explained that being a footballer was “a long-term ambition but, at the same time growing up, it wasn't really a thing that you could, do in the female game, so it wasn't a realistic ambition, I didn't think at the time”.

There were similar quotes to these from all players, supporting the belief that girls and women often cannot see football as a realistic career choice, leading them to consider other paths alongside and / or after playing. These feelings of concern that they can rely on football as a career are in line with a study of female players across Europe, which found that only a small minority of players had a professional contract, and where contracts were apparent, they were on average less than two years in duration (FIFPro, 2017), another reason for hesitancy in choosing this over a more secure contract elsewhere.

This acceptance that football was likely to remain at most a part-time job, and more likely an unpaid pastime, was further demonstrated by the choice all but one of the players made to study towards a degree for “something to fall back on” (Elaine). This need for a backup came across in all interviews and, even though the players are all now earning a wage from football

– in some cases a full-time wage – this need to have an alternative source of income remains as the career of a footballer, regardless of gender, is not a long one.

One of the players in the sample – Margaret – did not go to university, ‘falling into’ various jobs. This is interesting as this was the eldest player who was developing in the era where professional football really was in its infancy. Regardless of this she maintained that “football was my priority”. It was clear that this player was willing to sacrifice the chance to potentially earn more money as, although she did not see herself as a professional player (due to the lack of opportunities, and her club remains fully part-time).

“I was that passionate and was that kind of focused and driven that if my job or employer turned round and said, ‘well you can’t, you can’t do that’ I was very much that headstrong that, well, ‘my football’s my priority’”.

In a short passage the player says “priority” on four occasions and the from listening to this her real passion for the game was palpable.

The player spoke of various jobs, all of which fitted around her football schedule and admitted

“of course it was hard at that time because the women’s game wasn’t as prominent as it is at the moment so ... [employers] maybe questioned why I was so adamant that was going to be a priority over money or anything like that so, yeah from a working perspective I made sure that football was kind of the priority”.

This player seemed to have a slightly different attitude to her career and ‘Plan B’ in that her Plan B was always going to be secondary to football. However, through choosing to go to university it seemed that the other players all had more of a focus on ensuring they had another primary career alongside, and / or after playing football.

This focus on education and career is likely due to the football landscape, and its inequalities. In Scotland the women’s game remains completely amateur until a player is old enough, and able to perform at the required level, to sign a professional contract, unlike men’s football where boys can be scouted from nine years old and signed on a ‘pro-youth’ contract (SFA, 2022). The signing for a professional team at such a young age often leads boys to identify completely as footballers (Mills et al., 2014), and therefore give less attention to education, career, and other lifestyle choices (Brown & Potrac, 2009).

In contrast, Gledhill and Harwood (2015) explained how girls are more likely to construct multiple identities during adolescence. Similarly, a more recent study of female handball players (Ekengren et al., 2020) found girls were more likely than their male counterparts to focus on school and social life, again due to the perception that a career solely in the sport was highly unlikely, if even possible. With the information provided here, the current study adds to the growing evidence of differing foci of male and female athletes; potentially beginning to explain why the transition to coaching remains more common for men (who are less likely to have an alternative).

The lack of alternative careers for retired male footballers could be explained in relation to 'identity foreclosure'. This occurs when an individual forms their identity early, before exploring other available roles (Marcia, 1996), and has been highlighted as common in young male footballers (Brown & Potrac, 2009; Mills et al., 2014). Identity foreclosure is considered a risk factor for mental health problems (Henriksen et al., 2020; Knowles et al., 2021) and more stressful transition out of sport upon retirement (Miller & Buttell, 2018; Payne & Driska, 2020), therefore it could be posited that although the lack of opportunities in professional football limits women's aspirations in the sport, this may decrease the chances of them facing the mental health issues that can accompany retirement from the game.

It was interesting to hear that, in my study, it was not uncommon for the players to make a point of explaining how they made a real effort to keep their football separate from other aspects of their lives. For example, Elaine explained how she had "always been big on having an identity outside of football", like Kyla who also likes to "keep it separate just eh enjoy football out the house and then come back and, switch off". In constructing these multiple identities through dual careers, studying, and other activities, the players have more varied experiences than their male counterparts; these experiences then providing them with more choice and opportunity upon retirement. Increased choice, coupled with the limited money available in coaching in the women's game, could be seen to be a key influencer on future career intentions of female players.

Where players had embarked on a non-footballing career they were faced with a dilemma between security and their love of the game. Kyla explained how she has worked up within her company to "a decent level". She said, "I want to go into coaching but I can't see me

stepping away from my [other] job to do football full-time”; a result of the likely drop in income and security. Another player who has an established, non-football, career is Sharon. She made it clear she loves football and that “it would be, be an ideal thing to (laugh) wake up in the morning and know that’s your only job”. The nervous laugh here again indicates just how self-confidence is playing a part, in that the player does not see how she could be a successful coach at the highest level, and the unease over the risk involved in moving away from another career where she has a “great pension all those kind of benefits”. Sharon seems to see a ‘glass ceiling’ in terms of possible income and therefore “couldn’t give up [my other job] straight away”.

This ‘glass ceiling’ effect (Williams, 1992) is regularly referred to in explaining women’s lack of progression in coaching. Norman, Rankin-Wright and Allison (2018) go a step further, suggesting the ceiling is, in fact, concrete. Because of this metaphoric glass (or concrete) ceiling, it is understandable that where women have opportunities to advance to higher levels in another career, they would not want to risk this for a coaching career where they are likely to continue to face barriers as they aim to progress. When probed further about her reluctance to leave her current career for full-time coaching, Sharon referred to the coaches at her current club. Only two are full-time, the rest volunteers, again highlighting the scarcity of opportunities to earn enough money to leave a secure, well-paid job for. She explained how her mum worries about her focusing solely on coaching, as managers “get sacked ... just to have nothing, anything to fall back on”; further adding to the pull towards the more secure career she has already established herself in.

From the discussions had with all players in this study, although all but one chose to focus on education alongside their football, it seems that Kyla is the one who has made the biggest sacrifice in relation to her football. Although she represented Scotland at age-group level she explained how she got to the stage where coaches could not understand her commitment to her academic work. This led to her taking a step back from football to focus more fully on her studies, to the extent that she turned down an opportunity of a scholarship in America because she was already “two or three years into this, very good apprenticeship” and “doing my degree”. As she did her degree while working full-time (and playing football), Kyla “used to be absolutely knackered at the weekend but ... didn’t want to give up football for my degree

either". This is an example of how much these players have sacrificed to stay in the game, and perhaps why they seek a better work-life balance in the future.

It was not only the players who had already chosen a full-time career over football, others were also concerned about the lack of security if they were to become full-time coaches in future. Although she currently works in the fitness industry on a casual basis (i.e. no salary, pension, etc.) alongside her full-time football contract, when thinking about the future Heather explained how she "would like to go into something like the [another job] ... because that's a career and it's something that's maybe a wee bit more stable". Unlike Kyla and Sharon, Heather would not be leaving an established career, but still considers other, 'more stable' professions before coaching. Heather also showed some implicit reservations about her future, almost expecting to face challenges, as she discusses how she has learned to "try not to have too many expectations" because "there's loads of things that could happen". She explained this uncertainty was "why I like to have so many things right now". This is another example of how female athletes tend to like to be prepared for all eventualities rather than focusing solely on sport.

It is perhaps not directly related to the research question, but an interesting finding was that although a long-term career in coaching was rarely a strong consideration, even where players had considered – or were currently working in – non-footballing careers, these tended to be in male dominated industries. This demonstrates the ease with which these women can 'fit' into male cultures – often showing a preference for this – and I would posit that this is a reason why they have remained in football for so long, rather than a result of it.

This finding does mean that this study is not transferrable to the female population as a whole, as male dominance is a reason so many women drop-out of sport, both as athletes and coaches (Smith et al, 2019; Murray, Lord & Lorimer, 2020). It does, however, make it a valuable addition to existing literature as these players – who seem unfazed by the masculine culture of football – are, although a minority, perhaps a real untapped resource (Kerr and Banwell, 2014); one which could reap significant rewards when it comes to developing high-level female players of the future. This finding also provides backing to the postmodern feminist notion that gender cannot be considered as predetermined and fixed, rather that it is socially constructed (Rubin, 1975; Ely & Meyerson, 2000; Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005),

with the players in this study feeling at ease in masculine environments, likely a result of their past experiences.

4.3.5 I've not really seen it

It is interesting to note here that the experiences of the players in this study conflict with much of the literature in that they were generally coached by men in the early stages, before encountering more female coaches as they progressed to higher levels. From the outside this would seem surprising as statistics tend to show the number of female coaches decreasing as level of performance increases (MacInnes, 2017). However, I would suggest this finding can be explained by the nature of the sport and the pathways these players took from the beginning. In common with the elite coaches involved in Knoppers and colleagues' (2021) study, they all started out playing in boys' teams, therefore it is not unexpected that they were coached by men in their formative years. It was not until the players reached higher levels of performance that they moved to girls' / women's teams where – although still in a minority – female coaches are more common.

It should also be noted that Scotland could be considered an anomaly, as the national team has been coached by a woman since 1998, only recently appointing the first male head coach since the SFA took over responsibility for the women's game (SFA, 2021b). This exposure to a female coach at the highest level is positive, providing a good role model for younger generations. However, in the club teams that the players have been involved in – from grassroots through to their current teams – they have experienced more male head coaches (more in line with previous literature).

Overall therefore, these experiences (and role models) will have shown the players that, although it can be done, it is not the norm for women to reach those heights. Furthermore, the lack of exposure to female coaches until later stages has perhaps resulted in gendered stereotypes being formed early in their careers, while they were forming their identities, and ideas about women and men in society.

Evidence of an early impact of lack of appropriate role models, in relation to playing, came as the women were asked who their role models were as they developed as players. They always

mentioned male footballers first and in interpreting this it would be reasonable to suggest that although they did not necessarily see football as a boys' game – evidenced by the fact that they continue to play – they were perhaps more likely to see it as a hobby rather than a career. The players did not seem to acknowledge the impact of this shortage of role models as they progressed – although Nicola stated “I would have loved to have a female role model when I was younger but it just wasn't a thing” – however the evidence available suggests that there was likely a subconscious effect.

Many previous studies (e.g. Whisenant, 2008; Lyle, 2013) discuss how good role models – who provide a realistic example of what can be achieved – can inspire young players to take up, and continue to progress, in football. This was also discussed by Fowlie, Eime and Griffiths (2021) who found that a paucity of role models limited the number of young girls taking up cricket, and progressing to higher levels. Therefore, although the young players looked up to the men they cite as role models, aspiring to be as good as them, they could not have seen themselves playing in the top leagues and earning enough money to realistically call it a career. This is not directly related to the phenomenon under study here – i.e. coaching intentions – however it does provide some evidence of the impact of early experiences on the women's overall understanding of their place in the game.

This shortage of role models has been identified previously as a key factor in women's lack of coaching ambition (e.g. Burton & LaVoi, 2016; Taylor & Hardin, 2016; Ekengren et al., 2020; Sisjord, Fasting & Sand, 2021). Based in America, Taylor and Hardin's (2016) study found female athletic directors explicitly said that lack of role models impacted their progression into the role. Although nine of these women had gone on to coach, they explained that a career in sport was not something they planned, one participant stating how she, “fell backward into it” (p18). Sisjord, Fasting and Sand (2021) discuss the importance of formal and informal learning, the former including coach education, the latter including role models. Therefore, although none of the players in this study admitted a lack of female role models had an effect on them, there was a real suggestion – often from the unspoken word – that their own experiences as players had indeed had an influence.

Early studies into role models in coaching found a positive link between female athletes' exposure to female coaches, and their interest and aspirations in the coaching profession

(Lirgg, Dibrezzo & Smith, 1994; Everhart & Chelladurai, 1998). More recently Fasting, Sand and Nordstrand (2019) discussed the masculine nature of football and how the social construction of gender may influence women's perceived competence, and resulting self-efficacy. In line with Norman's (2014) findings they suggest that scarcity of female coaches leads female athletes to lack the self-belief and motivation to pursue coaching. This previous research, and findings from the current study, offer support to the idea, "if you can't see it, you can't be it" (Murray, 2017).

Although the players' experiences of being coached by a woman at national level contrasts with much previous literature – which shows a widening gender gap as the level of coaching increases (UEFA, 2019a) – it will have started to show them that there are women who are capable of coaching at the highest level. However, this impact is limited because of the shortage of female coaches within youth football. Because the female players saw coaches as men throughout their formative years, it is possible that they had already started to associate masculinity with successful coaching before they encountered a female coach for the first time.

Although this was not explicitly stated in the interviews, there was some implicit evidence. When asked about high-level coaches, players generally used masculine language and male examples, such as Lisa's description of Jose Mourinho as an example of a successful manager, and Heather highlighting Frank Lampard in an example of a successful player transitioning into coaching. There are female coaches who could have been used as examples here, so it is a useful insight into their mindset that the players automatically thought of men; perhaps a reflection of the subconscious effect of the male domination of their early experiences, and / or the fact that these male coaches are more visible.

There certainly was no obvious preference in relation to coach gender, as players all spoke very highly of those they had experienced when they were younger. These early coaches were all men:

"it's always folk's dads isn't it?" (Kyla)

"many different teams there was dads" (Elaine)

“I never seen any [women] at all involved in the kind of boys’ teams when I was younger” (Lisa)

“primary school was ... one of the dads ... my youth career, it was all male coaches” (Nicola)

“it was dads that run [my early teams]” (Sharon)

Comments such as the following were common throughout all interviews, “like I say I’ve been really lucky” (Lindsay), [male coach] was “kind of like a father figure to me” (Heather), “I certainly was treated as an equal” (Margaret). This shows that the players saw no disadvantage to being coached by a man, and – in terms of their football development, and enjoyment – there likely was not. However, although nothing is explicitly stated – and therefore cannot be known for sure – a critical analysis of the comments offered about early coaches could serve to reinforce the suggestion these have played a part in the players’ perceptions of successful coaching as being a male domain.

4.3.6 We could be game changers

Although the players initially made a real effort to downplay the influence of coach gender on their own development, they did note some advantages of a single sex coaching dyad. Although they all stopped short of showing a preference for female coaches – some, in fact saying they preferred men – they did admit there was value to having a woman on the coaching team. Elaine was a player who felt this was a necessity because “men and women are very different” and “women get women”. This supports previous evidence (Longshore & Sachs, 2015; Norman, 2016; Stewart, 2016) which has found that female athletes need to be coached differently to male athletes.

In a longitudinal primary study, over 14 years, Stewart pointed to the importance of communicating with female athletes in an appropriate way. Furthermore, in an extensive literature review, Norman (2016) highlights three key areas where male and female athletes differ. She draws upon Hyde’s (2014) study to summarise memory of past experiences, communication in response to situations, and the building and maintaining of relationships that should be considered by a coach working with female athletes. Sharon elaborated on this as she discussed a female coach’s ability to “understand hormones in women”. More

specifically, Lisa referred to issues that only women experience, such as “menstrual cycle, injury and private matters”. She did say that she believed men could learn, but it was apparent that there was a feeling that only a woman could truly understand, due to shared experiences.

Lisa was the only player in this study to mention this, however previous research by the BBC showed that of 537 elite athletes surveyed, 40% did not feel comfortable discussing their period with their coach (BBC, 2020), an issue discussed by elite rugby players in a recent exploratory study by Findlay and colleagues (2020). Although it did not come through extensively, unlike in previous research (e.g. Fasting & Pfister, 2000; Pensgaard & Roberts, 2002), there was a suggestion from some that female coaches were “more approachable to an extent” (Kyla). In relation to approachability, Sharon brought up the subject of sexual orientation. Although it appears more common for female athletes to be openly gay (Hargreaves & Anderson, 2014; BBC, 2020; Anstiss, 2021) – this is backed up by findings from the interview where three players speak openly about their female partners – homophobia continues to be a problem in both men’s and women’s football (FIFPro, 2017). Because of this Sharon felt that, like herself, young players would likely feel more comfortable discussing her sexual orientation with a woman.

Considering previous evidence, it was interesting to hear how the majority of players were clear that the quality of their relationship with past coaches had been unrelated to gender, and a few actually had a preference for their male coaches. In looking beyond the explicit statements however, there may be some evidence that this is at least partly a result of their lack of exposure to female coaches, which has likely subconsciously reinforced traditional gendered stereotypes, in turn shaping their perceptions of quality coaching.

Both Margaret and Heather said that they preferred what they described as a masculine style of coaching although they admitted this may be largely because that is what they have “been used to, exposed to more” (Heather), finding it hard to draw any real conclusions due to the scarcity of female coaches throughout their careers. This description of a ‘masculine style’ is worthy of note and a further example of how traditional stereotypes influence what one believes is an ‘appropriate’ way for a particular individual to behave.

Because the players have experienced more male coaches, the likelihood of one of these being their 'favourite' is obviously increased. Heather does try to explain her reasoning however, as she says she likes how males "allow us to problem solve a little bit more, whereas I think females are quite over-thinkers". This is an interesting quote as it is an example of the players themselves genderising characteristics, where perhaps one would expect them to be more inclined to avoid this, as women in a male-dominated environment. This is concerning though as, if these players think women are 'over-thinkers', and over-thinking is a negative attribute in a coach, then this is likely to negatively impact their own belief in their ability to successfully perform the role. Again, this can be related back to the stereotypical view of male and female as a dichotomy, with biology determining characteristics; a notion long challenged by feminists (e.g. Morris & Bunjun, 2007).

Margaret said that she found the men she had worked with more approachable but, again, put this down to the fact that "80% of my playing career I've been coached by males, so I've had more experiences" to draw from. Aside from these two players, the others all insinuated that they did not find a coach's gender had any influence on their opinion of them. The overall consensus is summed up in the following statement from Nicola,

"I've had so many good coaches that were male, but I've also had so many good coaches that were female and as I say I think the common denominator's they just all have all they [sic] qualities that I think you need".

This disregarding of gender, more in line with postmodernist thought, is encouraging. It cannot be ruled out however, that past experiences could serve to inadvertently inhibit the players' progression, as what they see as 'qualities' in a coach have likely been influenced by their overwhelming experiences of men (largely being successful) in the position.

The importance placed on individual qualities and having the "right person" for the job (Sharon) could be argued to be a key reason that players such as these should become coaches, to show that women can be the 'right person'. Recent studies by De Haan and Knoppers (2020) and De Haan and Norman (2020) concluded that coaches are likely to reproduce the gendered discourses that they experienced throughout their careers as athletes, thus fulfilling the self-perpetuating cycle. Through encouraging more female

coaches throughout the game it may be possible to limit further reproduction of these gendered discourses in future.

Again, although none of the players seemed to think the lack of female role models influenced their coaching intentions, previous research makes it hard to argue that there has not been at least some implicit effect. Although she was discussing her ambitions as a player, Heather supported much previous research, and mirrored the thoughts of many minority groups, when she said, “it’s hard to visualise something that you’ve not seen”. Other players spoke of the importance of female coaches in inspiring future generations to follow in their footsteps as players. This is reason for this specific demographic, rather than simply women in general, to be encouraged to enter the coaching domain. Many felt that when they were coached by a woman who had been successful as a player, that this motivated them to work hard and progress.

A few of the players discussed an ex-Scotland international joining the coaching team for the national squad, all speaking very highly of her; a result of the respect she had earned as a player. Lisa was one of the few players who suggested that she did not expect to be involved in coaching at all in future, however she was the one who openly acknowledged the role model effect in relation to coaching. She said, “first and foremost it’s like a role model that then shows to other players that they can be coaches”. Lisa was the youngest player, growing up when women’s football was really increasing in popularity and status. It was therefore interesting that she was the only one that had not really shown any interest in coaching at all. However this may also be a result of her age as she said, “it’s just something I’ve not thought about too much”. Her interview painted a picture of a young player focused on making the most of her playing career, having not considered other career options particularly seriously either. The fact that she did acknowledge the importance of role models, and the scarcity of female coaches – “you don’t see any female coaches in the men’s game at a high level so, I think there’s no reason why at the highest-level women’s football why there shouldn’t be more female coaches” – does imply that these players could, in fact, be ‘game changers’.

Another unexpected, interesting finding that two players mentioned in their interviews – in relation to the effect of women as coaches – was that there could perhaps be a negative effect of a woman coaching a female team. Sharon alluded to this on a few occasions, highlighting

the issue of coaches potentially getting “too close” to players. She told how she had never experienced this but “there’s teams where you can get maybe too close and there is friendships there that can cause issues.” When describing a male coach she had got on well with, she said “he never got close, like too close to the players”, implicitly suggesting that it is perhaps a wider issue than she admitted. When discussing relationships with her female coaches, Sharon explained how they often took “a further step back to what the male ones to ‘cause they don’t want to get that friendship with the players”, suggesting perhaps this was something that could be problematic. Kyla also showed concern when she said that, as a coach “you don’t want to become too friendly with your team either ... you’ve got to pick the team and give your reasons ... you also want them to like you ... but you don’t want to be pally pally”. This is interesting as it is not something that has been discussed in relation to men’s football and I wonder if this is down to the ‘overthinking’ that Heather feels is characteristic of women, or something that is inherent to girls’ and women’s football. In hindsight I should perhaps have probed further about this, as it could have an indirect negative effect on the coach-athlete relationship.

To my knowledge this is an area that has not been studied and may be worth focusing on in further investigating factors that may put women off coaching. Perhaps related to this desire to keep a distance from players, Kyla explained how she was not keen to coach while playing as she did not want to be seen to be favoured over her teammates as a result of her position:

“I don’t want to do it too early ‘cause my teammates are my teammates ... I find it hard to then be able to like ‘oh, oh she’s a favourite ... ‘cause she’s coaching us’ or whatever just kinda want to remain a player...”.

It is not uncommon for men to act as ‘player-coaches’ towards the end of their careers, therefore again it may be worth investigating whether Kyla’s concern is more widespread, as this could further delay any move into coaching – and perhaps decrease the likelihood of it happening at all – when coaching their teammates does not seem a concern of male players.

This evidence, although tenuous, does start to add to the existing literature detailing the benefits that women can bring to coaching. More specifically related to the research question in the current study, is the suggestion that this demographic – female *and* high-level players – could really enhance the coaching workforce, especially in the women’s game. Related to

being female, as well as playing at a high-level, the players said how younger girls would “already know your career” (Margaret). This indicated she felt it may bring with it a level of respect, which previous literature has suggested is not commonly given to female coaches; a factor discussed earlier with regards to coach education.

This backs up findings in Sisjord, Fasting and Sand’s (2021) study in that women felt that their playing experiences helped them to gain respect among their fellow coaches and their players. Furthermore, in line with the ‘I’m not sure I’m up to it’ theme, the players agreed that having “been there done it” (Margaret) would make them more confident as they could use their own experiences to enhance the information they were giving to their squad. Kyla added to this when she explained how having played the game gives the advantage of “knowing women’s football”. Although the rules are the same, it is widely accepted that there are differences in terms of the female and male versions of the game (Alvaro & Barriopedro, 2009; Althoff et al., 2010; Hjelm, 2012; Gomez, Casal et al., 2019). It is uncommon for females to coach in men’s football, therefore it could be argued that women are better positioned to coach in the women’s game, having experienced it for themselves.

Regardless of gender, the players were all generally in agreement that their experience of playing at a high level would stand them in good stead if they were to go on to coach. Although none used female examples, they did talk of male coaches with whom they had connected well, as a result of their previous playing experience. For example, Margaret discussed a male coach she currently works with. She explained, “he was a player, and he played in the position that I now play in so I feel like ... it’s a relatable relationship we have”. The knowledge of the game was seen to be important to the players as they suggested that “you get that different perspective from someone who has been in the game” (Lindsay). And, away from the game itself Elaine explained how, having played, “you just know how it feels as a player ... it’s very difficult I think to know what players go through if you haven’t been there”.

These findings also support those by Sisjord, Fasting and Sand (2021) who found that coaches who had played at an elite level were better able to understand the psychological challenges involved, as being an elite athlete involves more than simply the sport performance (Norman, 2014). Similarly, the players also discussed the advantage of knowing what it is like to have

been coached themselves at this level. Related to gender, Slsjord, Fasting and Sand (2021) found that women were more likely to gain confidence as coaches from their playing experience. Although there was no mention of gender here, some of the players in the current study discussed bad experiences they had had with their coaches, and how they would use these to ensure other players did not experience the same.

Elaine provided a good example that she said may inspire her to coach, simply to ensure she could provide a more positive experience than she had. She referred to “reverse motivation”, explaining how one bad experience she had with a coach inspired her to “make a difference, and maybe make sure no one has to go through what I had to go through”. Sharon also explained how negative experiences she encountered served as a motivation for coaching in the future. She explained how her experience had shown that often “coaching at the highest level sometimes people can forget that you are a person as well”. Again, although this was not related to gender, there is a real suggestion that having been in the position these players are now, that they would be able to use their experiences to create a positive, more caring, coaching environment for the next generation of high-level players.

4.3.7 We just can’t live without football!

Throughout the interviews there was no doubt that the players lived and breathed football, further suggesting a transition to coaching could be an ideal future career path. Margaret pondered this as she said, “it’s not the same (laugh) feeling as what you would do in getting on a pitch ... [but coaching] has its rewards”. Margaret is the eldest of the players interviewed and one who seems to have spent most time thinking about her life after playing. She has no doubt that she will remain in the game in some capacity, stating, “for me it’s a must, it’s a necessity, I love the game, I love playing the game, I love watching the game, I love everything about the game”; a feeling that come across in all interviews.

Sharon, who works full-time in another profession, explained how her choice of (non-footballing) career was inspired by her parents as “they couldn’t imagine me sitting at a desk job, because I’ve always been quite active”. This is a common trait, evidence by the fact that none of those in the study with second careers outside of football work a typical nine to five, desk-based job. Similarly, Nicola – although still focused on playing full-time for a while yet

as a sole career – has already thought enough about her future to say, “I don’t, see myself going into an office and doing a nine to five job”.

Throughout the interviews the players all highlighted their love of the sport and how they found it hard to see a future without it completely, shown in the following quotes:

“It would be quite nice to still be involved in that football environment, with the players and stuff, and you know part of a team, like I have been my whole life”
(Nicola)

“I don’t really know what I want my role to be when I finish football, but I want to stay in football” (Kyla)

“I want to stay in football (Lisa)

Again, it seems that the players are generally keeping their options open – focusing on their playing careers for now – but the way they discussed both their love of football, and their thoughts on the future, there is a real argument for encouraging them to consider being involved in coaching to “stay part of the game” (Lisa) that they love. These comments are very much in line with previous literature with similar demographics. For example, in Ronkainen, Sleeman and Richardson’s (2020) study of ten high-level football coaches in England (two were women, all coached female players), one of the vignettes constructed to show the coaches’ journeys was named, ‘for the love of the game’. This vignette discussed how becoming a coach was a natural progression.

4.4 Summary of Findings

It was apparent from speaking to the players that there is an overall desire to help the women’s game evolve. When pondering her future Margaret stated her wish to “better it especially from a girls’ and women’s perspective, if I can drive the game forward on and off the pitch then that is something I certainly will do and strive to do”. From analysis of the explicit content, and the more latent meaning interpreted from the interview data, it appears that it is not so much that the current players do not want to coach, but that they have simply not considered it as a viable option. The deeper understanding of their past experiences as players, and coaches where applicable, certainly starts to provide some potential reasons for their future career intentions. I feel my own reflections aided my analysis of this as I started

to wonder myself how much the male dominance of my early experiences impacted upon my choice not to progress in my coaching career.

Furthermore, the interviews provided support to Kerr and Banwell's (2014) suggestion that high-level players are indeed an untapped resource, and that this demographic can bring sporting capital that would be a real asset to the workforce; a workforce arguably currently lacking in diversity. In LaVoi's (2016) book, she emphasised the benefits of a diverse workforce, including wider perspectives leading to better decision making, and less likelihood of discrimination and harassment. With the wider benefits to diversity in any workplace, this is a key reason relevant parties should work to increase diversity in football, partly through promoting current players' progression as coaches.

Upon pondering their position, the players in this study agreed that they were in a position to improve the game for future generations:

“I like the idea of giving back to sport, em and giving back to, like what I've come from and hopefully, encouraging more people to get involved in it, and to share my experiences and hopefully, you know, maybe give them that opportunity” (Heather).

This desire to 'give back' has been highlighted in previous studies (e.g. Ronkainen, Sleeman & Richardson, 2020; Thompson, Whittaker & Bunyon, 2020) and is therefore something that could be capitalised on in promoting options to current players. This, coupled with the investment from clubs and governing bodies, may serve to increase the representation of ex-high-level female players in women's football.

4.5 Impact of Personal Experiences

At this stage, in light of the epistemological assumptions of the postmodern feminist theory in which this research has been framed, I feel it is important to further discuss my own experiences and how these may have shaped my interpretation of the experiences of the women I interviewed. In addition to the continual reflective cycle that accompanied my research, I feel at this stage a sharing of my own experiences will allow the reader to make their own judgement on how these may have affected conclusions. It was important for me

to reflect back upon my own coaching experiences and how these may have influenced my perception of the role, and how they may have the potential to lead to incorrect assumptions.

Throughout my coaching career I generally felt that I was accepted, but I can draw parallels between my experiences and those I have since read about, where female coaches report a need to prove themselves. From my very first experience as a novice coach, through all of my coaching roles, I seemed to fit in well, despite often being the only female in the coaching team. I can honestly say – like the players I interviewed – that I enjoyed the banter, although in hindsight I think at times it was probably inappropriate.

I think that because when I was growing up football was very much a male pursuit (more so than now), that I considered myself a bit of a tomboy, and from a young age spent a lot of time with male friends. As I got older and entered the work environment, again – because of my passion for sport and resulting career choices – I continued to find I was more likely to be surrounded by men. Through spending so much time with male colleagues, I can now see that I had been socialised into the masculine culture, taking on ‘the banter’. I know some of my friends would have struggled in this environment and I can see how it can be off-putting to some women, but I think to an extent I actually quite liked being the ‘token’ female as the men I worked with were always very good to me; I think because they felt that I was ‘one of the boys’.

As I progressed through coaching qualifications, in line with current literature, I found myself becoming more and more of a minority until most recently I did my UEFA B coaching licence, and I was the only female participant. This was not unexpected and upon arrival everyone was very welcoming, but I did feel a real need to prove myself to be worthy of my place. This feeling was not new, but I think this was the level where I really felt quite self-conscious because, although I was equally as qualified as the men – and had more coaching experience than many of them – because they played semi-professional football, I felt out of my depth when it came to joining in games. In previous courses there were always some less able players, and many of the practical sessions were drill based where I felt my technical skills were adequate, however on this course it was more game-based and there were some very good players that I would have to play alongside. I felt that I managed to ‘hold my own’ in

the games and my coaching experience showed through, but I do remember constantly feeling under pressure not to show myself to be inferior.

From reading previous studies I can see that my experiences support much of the evidence related to other female coaches, especially at higher levels, thus it would not be wrong to assume that the players I was interviewing may feel the same. However, there are key differences – namely the elite status that the current players hold – that meant that I had to avoid making tenuous assumptions. These previous experiences I could draw upon to help me understand, also had potential to bias my opinions, therefore I was careful in the wording of my questions, and waited to hear the responses of the players before I shared my own experiences, to avoid making suggestions that may influence their responses. However, upon reflecting on the interviews it did become apparent that many of my experiences bore similarities to those players I was interviewing.

Thinking about this I felt I could use my experiences of self-consciousness and isolation to help me understand the current players' stories while continuing to look from other viewpoints to ensure a balanced view. It is impossible to say that my sharing of information did not encourage players to share similar stories, however I believe it is more likely that they felt comfortable enough to share honest accounts, rather than feeling they should say what I expected them to. This was evident in some cases where the players were keen to almost contradict me, explaining how they felt particularly comfortable in the male environment, and that they were accepted. However, my insider status did allow me to delve beyond the spoken word where I could see more hidden evidence that reminded me of my own feelings in similar situations.

5.0 Conclusion

This work has sought to examine the influences on current elite female footballers' coaching intentions, in an effort to understand the current lack of progression into the role by this demographic. Through primary research I have sought to answer the following research question: 'How likely are elite female footballers to consider entering into coaching as a career, and what are the underlying reasons for this?'. Through exploring the experiences of elite players in Scotland, and analysing these experiences alongside previous literature, I would conclude that coaching intentions are limited; a result of both past and current experiences primarily as players (and in some cases also as coaches). This chapter will bring together key findings, draw conclusions and provide recommendations for future policy, research and practice.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The current research supports much previous literature in that the women have presented experiences which have been heavily male dominated, although contrary to much of the previous literature, these women generally downplay any negative impact that this may have had. As an interpretative piece of work, I have used my own experiences to allow me to begin to understand these players' journeys, and feel there has been some subconscious effect of the lack of female role models – notably in relation to coaching – especially at early stages of the players' careers. It also came across in the interviews that, although they argued that a coach's gender was unimportant, the players highlighted many key qualities, or 'coaching capital', that they – as a unique demographic – could bring to the profession.

It was clear throughout the interview process that many of the women had not considered coaching, often a result of their focus on playing, and the fact that often this was accompanied by another job, leading to little free time. Furthermore, all had a degree, and / or a second job, alongside their playing career. This is likely a result of their perception of football in all capacities (including playing) to be an unlikely profession for them as they contemplated the future. With research showing the negative impact of identity foreclosure (DeFreese & Shannon, 2021) this focus away from football should not be discouraged, but should be

considered as those in policy making roles consider the creation of opportunities that may allow coaching to sit alongside other career options.

5.2 Strengths and Limitations

This study is limited in the small homogenous sample size, meaning it cannot be generalised across wider populations, such as female sports coaches in general. Generalisability is a term that historically has not been associated with qualitative research, however Smith (2018) suggests that although 'statistical generalisability' cannot be assumed in qualitative research, the lack of it should not be viewed as a limitation. Nevertheless, he does stress the importance of being cognisant of the issue, to avoid journal editors "demean[ing]" (p139) this type of research. Therefore, although it cannot be stated in the more traditional, statistical, sense of the word, I would argue that the findings of this study have both naturalistic (Stake, 1995) – in that readers are likely to be able to relate these to their own experiences – and analytical (Polit & Beck, 2010) – likely to hold significance to other populations – generalisability.

With the sample all white female players, mainly based in Scotland, the issue of intersectionality remains unaddressed. This homogeneity of sample is not ideal for this reason, however it is generally representative of the landscape within which it sits. With only one non-white player currently in the national squad, the sample is representative of the general demographic. This lack of diversity within the squad is a wider issue that should be addressed in other research. In order to generalise more widely it would be required to conduct further research within the other home nations, and beyond.

It could also be argued that the limited sample here is a strength of the research, due to the uniqueness of the demographic which – although a minority – has the potential to improve the women's football landscape, the football landscape in general, and wider society in Scotland and beyond. Other key strengths of the research include a thorough qualitative study of a unique demographic, and one which – to date – has been understudied. The study of this sample has the potential to improve understanding of the low number of female players who transition to coaching. As mentioned previously, much of the current literature in this field focuses on those who have already embarked on the career (e.g. Clarkson, Cox &

Thelwell, 2019), thus missing the potential to understand the reasons that so many decide against it.

Although the sample size could be viewed as a strength, or at least not a great limitation, the nature of the interviews – in that they were fairly short one-off discussions – is more likely a limitation to the study. It is possible that with less time to build rapport that players would be less open, maybe less likely to share personal stories. I would argue that this limitation is partially countered by my insider status, as I certainly got a real feeling of ease from all participants within a short time of the interviews starting. On occasions where I asked for more information about experiences of a personal nature, the players were all more than happy to share. Nonetheless this limitation should be noted, and it cannot be assumed that more information would not have been gleaned from follow-up interviews. This limitation could be addressed in future work – perhaps of a more longitudinal nature – that follows players' journeys as they near the end of their playing careers.

A further strength of the study is in the thoroughness in which it has explored, not simply what players said explicitly, but the way in what they said what they did, and even sometimes what they did not say. Through analysing the use of language itself, body language, tone, hesitation, etc., alongside explicit verbal content, I used my own experience and previous literature to draw my conclusions. For this analysis, the use of a reflexive journal was extremely useful. It seems from this study that players are generally unaware of the impact of some of their gendered experiences, therefore through a more thorough critique it is possible to make more valid conclusions and useful recommendations for future practice.

5.3 Recommendations

This section will provide recommendations for further research, and future practice in both football, and academia.

5.3.1 Recommendations for Research

As a result of the limited scope of this study, the first recommendation I would make for research, is for similar studies to be conducted across Britain, and worldwide. This would allow more thorough conclusions to be drawn, and comparisons to be made in reference to

the differing environments in which the game takes place. I posit that the findings of this study are quite unique due to the early stages of professionalisation in which women's football finds itself, therefore it is important to consider experiences of players in different contexts to draw wider conclusions and make recommendations in different countries and / or at different times.

5.3.2 Recommendations for Practice (Football)

My overall recommendation for policy and practice in Scotland and is to continue to strive to increase female representation at all levels of football, to ensure that not only are women coached by women at elite levels, but that they see women in leadership positions from the onset to avoid gendered stereotypes affecting their perception of the role at early stages of development. This is not a new recommendation, and it is encouraging to hear that some Scottish clubs, and the national governing body, currently provide funding to allow players to achieve coaching awards. Also, as discussed above, funding and mentoring programmes are available throughout Britain and Europe, but current figures shown in Chapter 1 (i.e., only 22% of Scottish top level club teams coached by women) show that these programmes are having limited success.

I believe these initiatives should be applauded, and encouraged to continue and expand, as evidence suggests mentoring programmes (especially single-gender ones) can help increase women's self-confidence (Avery, Tonidandel & Philips, 2008), and allow them to see themselves in the role. When I did my UEFA B licence, I was lucky to be offered a mentor. The reason for this was that I had signed up to a women's only course, but due to low uptake the course was cancelled. I was offered a place on a mixed-gender course (and was the only female coach on it), but given a mentor to support me, as the FA were trying to encourage more women into the profession.

My mentor was a very experienced coach, and coach educator, and I found spending time with him very insightful. It also built my confidence as he praised my coaching and provided constructive feedback throughout the course, especially in the lead up to my assessment. I would definitely credit this mentor with playing a huge part in my development, and eventual success on the course. However I cannot help but think that had I had a female mentor, that

perhaps I would have been able to relate better, and maybe even strive to coach at a higher level. With my male mentor I saw an opportunity to learn from an expert, and develop my coaching skills, but I did not see a realistic role model to whom I could truly relate.

For this reason I would like to see more female mentors recruited to support more novice coaches. This will take time as it will require suitably qualified women to take on the roles, however it would be something to work towards. In addition, wider peer support groups could be formed where horizontal support (Norman, Rankin-Wright & Allison, 2018) is provided. This would give women a sense of community and a network to share problems, successes and other experiences with others going through the same experience. I understand this choosing of gender is against the postmodernist philosophy of dissolving dualisms, however I believe with the plethora of evidence pointing towards the benefits of realistic, relatable, role models – including my own experiences – that this is a valid recommendation. It is not intended to create a new hierarchy where women are more valued than men, rather to support women to allow them to break through the traditional glass ceiling.

Although I can confirm – both from my own experience and from my literature review – that funding and mentoring can make accessing and succeeding in coach education more appealing and more likely, I would argue that the findings from my primary research suggest that the issue of lack of women in coaching needs to be addressed far earlier, when identities are being formed. For those who are keen to coach, funding and support through courses does indeed remove, or at least reduce, common barriers. However, where the women in my study showed little interest in coaching, this was rarely a result of the cost of courses. Although cost was mentioned, it seemed to me that by the time they had reached elite level as players, that they had already taken steps towards another career path (either taking on a dual role, or getting a qualification to ‘fall back on’ or use at the end of their playing careers). I would posit that for many of these women, free coach education courses are of limited value while they seem to have the perception (I believe often subconsciously) that elite level coaching is a male domain.

I do feel this strive to increase representation is a bit of a ‘chicken and egg’ situation as, while young girls are creating their identities, and forming opinions about what is ‘normal’, they are

most often playing football in teams coached by men. The only way to normalise female coaches is for them to be more visible, but that means more coaches need to be qualified and experienced, and so the cycle goes on. The media can play a role in this by showing more women's games on mainstream television, and other media outlets. Although there is still a disparity, more and more women are coaching at the highest level in Scotland and England and, with short weekly highlights shows, football fans of both genders are starting to see successful female coaches.

Social media tends to be the medium of choice for the promotion of women's sport (Anstiss, 2021), with a real growth in podcasts and apps (e.g. Talksport's Women's Football Weekly, The Offside Rule: WSL Edition, Two Girls Talk Balls) providing more opportunities for the consumption of women's sport. I would agree with Anstiss (2021) that this is a real opportunity for growth, however I would also argue that many of these media outlets remain 'niche', found by those looking for them specifically. Conversely, through a more diverse approach to mainstream media and advertising, a greater step could be taken towards the normalisation of women in sport; rather than further isolating them as a different, inferior, entity. One way to take this a step further than the current offering, would be to report scores and show highlights of key women's games at the end of the mainstream news – as happens with top level men's games – again, to promote both male and female players and coaches as being on the same level.

As well as simply showing more women's sport, it would be beneficial to more actively raise the profile of female coaches, through celebrating their success. In line with previous role model research, Anstiss (2021) suggests raising the profile of successful female coaches is key to showing others there is a pathway for them. Women in Sport (2015) agree it is important to highlight women who have succeeded, but they stress that to be effective this should be done honestly, clearly showing the challenges faced along the way, and support required for coaches to overcome these. With so many women's sport bodies (e.g. Women in Sport, Women's Sport Foundation, etc.) it would be good to see more events organised where aspiring coaches can learn, develop and network. Many sports organisations organise conferences, but these tend to be more widely attended by academics and those in higher leadership positions. By offering development sessions to those at early stages of their

careers (and perhaps those yet to embark on them) this could perhaps reduce the number of women who fail to progress beyond early levels.

Although increased visibility at the highest levels is likely to start to change perceptions, it is important that by the time women have progressed as players, that they have not already closed off the idea of becoming a full-time coach upon retirement. One of the players spoke about her experience in a different country where the senior professional players were expected to help coach the younger teams; a link that brought benefits on many levels. For the younger girls, in being coached by the more senior players, they had good realistic role models that they could aspire to emulate. These relatable role models can increase 'vicarious confidence' (Anstiss, 2021); something that a plethora of literature has highlighted as key to long-term participation and progression (Lyle, 2013; Meier, 2015; Dunn, 2016; Ronkainen, Ryba & Selanne, 2019). The benefits were far wider though, as this link with youth and senior teams meant that the professional players were able to gain quality coaching experiences that would allow them to assess whether it was a profession they enjoyed and, if so, to allow them to start building their 'coaching toolkit'.

This player went on to tell me that at one of her clubs in Britain her coach would not support her to coach, as she was required to focus solely on playing. This player, however, explained that although she was totally committed to her playing career, that the nature of professional football meant that she did have time on her hands between sessions, and felt that coaching was a productive way to spend it without any negative impact on her playing performance. Hearing this player's story did concern me and it may be that this was an isolated situation, but I would recommend that all senior teams in Britain look to create a similar set-up to that described above, as that is likely to benefit players throughout the club.

Although it will not be a career choice for all, the chance to experience coaching for themselves would provide women with a real-life experience, allowing them to make a more educated career choice in future, whether that involves coaching or not. Therefore, I would recommend that players are given as many opportunities to experience coaching as they are interested in. This would increase their self-efficacy and, in turn, their likelihood of considering aiming for high level jobs that would allow them to coach as a full-time profession. If players could be provided with paid opportunities to coach, alongside their professional

playing contracts, this may allow more to focus more fully on football where currently they have to work it around their unrelated 'day job'. I feel that a good way to do this, with mutual benefit to clubs, would be for coaches to be involved in some of their club's community programmes and youth teams. Through employing current players in these roles, not only will the players develop their coaching skills, but younger players will have realistic role models to inspire them. The issue around identity foreclosure cannot be ignored however, and it should be carefully considered as to how young players can gain experience of playing and coaching, without neglecting their holistic development.

A further means of increasing opportunities, and making women more aware of the opportunities they have available in Scotland, would be for the SFA to replicate the FA's Coach Index (The FA, 2021b). By simply allowing women (and other minority groups) to sign up to a database they could be directly contacted with appropriate qualifications, other learning opportunities, paid and voluntary employment, and support networks, to allow them to progress to the level they desire.

If women are provided with opportunities to coach earlier in their careers, those who choose to continue will be required to progress through the coach education ladder. Recent literature shows a masculine environment that rarely prepares coaches (of any gender) to work in the women's game (e.g. Sawiuk, Lewis & Taylor, 2021). Related to UEFA's target of increasing the number of female coaches across Europe (UEFA, 2019a), in September 2021 a Women's Football Competence Framework Working Group was formed. Made up of a range of professionals they are tasked with ensuring all UEFA diploma courses include sufficient women's football content. Planned to be finalised by April 2022 these courses will prepare all coaches to coach both genders at all levels (UEFA, 2021).

This is a bold move, addressing a long-standing flaw in the current programmes, and one that I feel should be replicated more widely. UEFA courses are relevant across Europe, with National Governing Bodies creating and running their own programmes at lower levels (as prerequisites to UEFA licences). I would therefore recommend that NGBs (i.e the SFA in Scotland) should work with current and potential coaches to co-create appropriate content that avoids any unconscious bias towards the male game, showing from the outset that women are welcome and valuable assets at all levels. Related to one of the recommendations

for academia (below) key academics could also be involved in this, drawing on evidence to create courses that truly address the current issues.

Cultural change is key to equity in sport (Women in Sport, 2015; Farrer & Co., 2019). “Subconscious bias” (Farrer & Co., 2019, p 20) is likely to impact upon recruitment decisions as those in hiring positions tend to select those they feel most comfortable with, those most like themselves (Farrer & Co., 2019). Through changing the culture of football clubs, the benefits are likely to be widespread, as a diverse workforce is one of the “fundamental building blocks” of a well governed organisation, more able to see both the risks and opportunities (Farrer, & Co., 2019, p23). Valls Martinez and Cruz Rambaud (2019) suggest that diversity on boards is linked with higher financial performance therefore this change of culture in all leadership roles could be key to the overall growth of the game (for men and women).

Recruitment strategies are key to this cultural change, and I would agree with Women in Sport (2015, p13) in saying that football teams and governing bodies must be “pro-active but not biased”. Interviewees in the Women in Sport (2015) study generally showed concern over about the hiring of ‘token’ women, whose reputation could be undermined as a result, but some did admit that the use of quotas could serve a purpose; forcing NGBs to “work harder to find the right people in the first place” (ibid., p12). It seems that in football where quotas have been introduced, these are generally at board level, but I agree with Petra Einarsson, quoted in Women in Sport (2015, p14) in that these quotas should be introduced from the bottom. This would minimise the feelings of tokenism, rather allowing women to work their way up in organisations, gaining valuable knowledge and experiences along the way (Farrer & Co. 2019).

5.3.3 Recommendations for Practice (Academia)

In relation to my role as an academic I feel that something that is not new, but should continue to be reinforced, is a drive to ensure all teaching materials are diverse, not just in relation to gender. By including all demographics, including women, people with disabilities, non-white individuals, etc., this may avoid any subconscious reinforcing of sport as a white, non-disabled, masculine domain. This is something I have been cognisant of for a long time but

believe there is always room for improvement in promoting equality and diversity. UWS is very proactive in this and provides many CPD opportunities for staff to educate about unconscious bias, and the importance of diversity in teaching materials. I would recommend that these types of modules should be written into teaching qualifications and that all universities regularly provide updates / refresher courses to ensure new materials are always diverse.

I would suggest academics avoid omitting white, non-disabled men from their materials (as I feel is sometimes done as an extreme measure to make up for previous lack of parity), but that they use an appropriate diversity of images, proportionate to the population. This is likely to impact upon students' perceptions of what a coach is in the current day; this may be a stereotypical man, but can equally be a woman, an individual with a disability, someone of an ethnic minority, or any combination of these.

The final recommendation I would make is for policy makers to link more closely with academics. There seems a plethora of good research and it would make sense for this to be used – especially the more exploratory studies – to allow future policies to be driven by current evidence. This is done to an extent, at my university and I expect others, but I would encourage the creation of a greater number of more formal links with academics and governing bodies, to ensure the needs of wider demographics (not only girls and women) are considered when new policies are created, and targets set.

Universities such as mine have many female students coming through Sports Coaching courses with the aim of working in the sports industry, and these students are required to conduct research as part of their fourth-year dissertation. With established links between the university and numerous sports clubs – including football – it would make sense for some students to focus their research on women in leadership positions. Through exploring experiences of women from partner clubs, recommendations could be made, and interventions employed and evaluated, before future students move forward with further recommendations from these. At a higher level, it would be beneficial for more experienced researchers (namely academic staff) to play a more key part in the creation of national sports policies, and government priorities.

Key to all of these recommendations is the input from women themselves. As with any minority group, only they can truly understand the barriers they face, therefore current policy makers are often not best placed to make recommendations alone. Anstiss (2021) highlights a US study that shows just how troublesome assumptions by men can be. When male athletic directors were asked what they thought prevented more women being head coaches, the top three responses were; time constraints due to family, failure of women to apply, and lack of qualified women. However, when female athletic directors were asked, they answered, 'old boys' networks', discrimination during the hiring process, and time constraints due to family. Time constraints is obviously a factor limiting some women's progression and therefore this must be addressed, but it is notable that this was listed below more obvious discrimination by the women questioned.

By employing a diverse range of women (considering intersectionality), to input into key decisions, policies are likely to have more impact and perhaps in future equity will be less than simply a vision, in football, sport, and the wider society. Table 8 (below) provides a succinct overview of my recommendations for practice.

Table 8 Summary of Recommendations for Practice (academia and coaching)

Recommendations for academia	Recommendations for coaching
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strive to truly represent sport and society in course content including teaching and marketing materials • Continue to create and develop links to clubs and organisations to add to the quality and quantity of research undertaken in this area • Work with NGBs and policy makers to influence policy and practice, through evidence-based recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue to promote funding and mentoring for female players to gain qualifications alongside their playing career • Celebrate successful female coaches, and increase the visibility of them in the mainstream media • Provide opportunities for senior players to coach younger teams within their club • Continue to develop content of NGB and UEFA coaching qualifications to reflect the women’s game • Proactively recruit women when their qualifications and experience are appropriate (not simply to achieve a quota)

6.0 Personal and Professional Reflections

A key difference between a traditional PhD and a Professional Doctorate is the emphasis on the reflective element (Cunningham, 2018). Fulton and colleagues (2013) explain how, by taking on the Professional Doctorate, one is aiming to become a *researching professional*; one who looks at challenges from different angles and offers new solutions to issues in their profession. This is something I aspire to do, as I aim to balance publishing and presenting research with teaching students; the reason I entered the profession in the first place.

I hope that teaching continues to be the main focus of my career, but that through research not only will I be teaching from my own experience, but also that I may bring more credibility to my lectures. I agree with Fulton and colleagues (2013) when they say this type of reflection does not come naturally, and the act of a more structured type of reflecting is something that I have had to develop throughout the course. Although I have always informally – often superficially – reflected upon my lectures and coaching sessions, these reflections have tended to be very much about what went well, what did not, and reasons why; from which I would seek to improve future sessions. Fulton and colleagues (2013), however, suggest that the ability to understand others' viewpoints is central to reflective practice, and is key to being able to make a real impact on a profession and this is an aspect of reflection that I have worked hard to develop throughout the course.

To become a “true researching professional” Fulton and colleagues (2013, p25) suggest that seeking opportunities to present ideas, although daunting, are fundamental, and that reflecting on these opportunities are key to one's development. I took this advice and at a very early stage I seized the opportunity to share my research proposal at the Football Collective Conference in Sheffield in November 2019. Although I was still far from being ready to start my data collection – and thus have meaningful findings to present – I was keen to gain experience of presenting, and to obtain feedback from experienced academics, and other football professionals.

This proved to be an extremely valuable experience. From the first stages of putting together the short presentation, the process led me to really reflect upon my proposal, considering the validity of my methods, and potential to gather meaningful findings. Furthermore, the

presentation itself provided me with valuable feedback from others who were looking on from different viewpoints, resulting in some very useful suggestions. This presentation, and associated feedback, formed one of my earliest real reflexion sessions. Through reflecting back on my planned research methods, the presentation itself, and the feedback provided, I was able to thoroughly critique my proposal, making changes that would strengthen it prior to commencing data collection.

Another reason I have placed such importance on developing my reflective practice throughout the course is that as well as being common in modern professional life (Sanders, 2010) it is particularly relevant in qualitative research (Braun & Clark, 2013). The research element of my profession is one that is fairly new to me, and through the Professional Doctorate course I feel that I have truly started to understand my position on the paradigmatic continuum. In the past I have used a range of methodologies in my limited research outputs, however from really taking time to reflect upon my values, I feel I can now define myself as a qualitative researcher. Through the learning I have undertaken during the course, and continue to undertake through reading and attending workshops, I feel I now have a sound understanding of the assumptions that underpin qualitative research, how these fit with my own beliefs, and how they will continue to impact upon my research; I hope this is clear from my positionality statement.

In relation to qualitative research, it is common to hear the term 'reflexion' which, according to Fulton and Colleagues (2013, p37), is much *deeper*, and requires one to be more self-aware; "truly understanding yourself as a professional, being aware of your values, prejudices and limits and ensuring that you act in full knowledge of why you are doing something". This is key to 'quality control' in qualitative research (Braun & Clarke, 2013), and one of the main areas I feel I have developed throughout the Professional Doctorate experience. Only through conducting my interviews, and critiquing them using Braun and Clarke's (2013) Framework of Reflexive Thematic Analysis, did I truly understand how my own experiences could really impact upon the way language can be interpreted and impact upon research findings. Through this I also learned the importance of transparency for the reader; being open about assumptions and the ways in which knowledge has been constructed.

This notion of 'quality control' in qualitative research is something I believe I have developed a greater understanding of. Through reading works by experts (e.g Varpio et al., 2017) I have become more critical of what I had previously understood as 'gold standard' benchmarks. For example, when putting together my ethics application, without a second thought I explained how I would use 'member checking'. Only after my supervisor pointed me in the direction of more recent research, I began to critique these 'member checks' in line with the epistemological assumptions of qualitative research, realising there was in fact an uneasiness between them.

Another thing I critiqued, again after a conversation with my supervisor, was the reliance on data saturation as a benchmark for ceasing data collection. Previous reading had led me to believe that this was 'gold standard' and something I should achieve for my research to be credible. Upon reading works by Braun and Clarke (2021b), Saunders and colleagues (2018) and Varpio and colleagues, (2017), among others, I realised that, although many authors claim to have reached saturation, none have really been able to clearly define what this actually means. Again, through becoming a more experienced researcher, I started to be more critical myself, and I agree with Low (2019, p131) when she states that data saturation is impossible as "there are always new insights to be made". I therefore thought more about the quality of my data, rather than the quantity, making a judgement that there was enough to present a good understanding of the phenomenon.

The final area I feel I have developed through undertaking the Professional Doctorate is my understanding of theoretical underpinning. In my limited research experience, I have hitherto paid little attention to this, never having been fully aware of its importance. Again, through the taught element of the course, and through working with my supervisors, I have begun to realise the importance of sound theoretical underpinning. I have read abundantly and critically about feminism for this study, and feel that I am now much more knowledgeable about its background, how it has evolved, and how it can be used to frame many types of research. I have really enjoyed learning this aspect of research, and expect I will utilise a feminist framework – and continue to develop my understanding of it – as my research experience continues.

Overall, reflecting upon this whole process, I believe I have developed greatly as a researcher and have learned valuable lessons that will help me in my future research, and within my teaching and coaching. I have also begun to build a good community of practice, including my peers from the course, my supervisory team, football professionals (both from networking at conferences and through my primary research), and other academics. This Community of Practice has been a great support to me throughout the process and one which I aim to continue to use, and to further develop, as my career progresses.

Going back to my experiences as a coach, I feel that – although I maybe did not realise it at the time – I did try to exert almost over-confidence as a way of covering up my insecurity when coaching. This was also the case when I was coaching high level players as there were times that I was coaching players who were of a higher ability than me. The players I have studied are less likely to have self-confidence issues in relation to their playing ability (although it is not impossible), but I believe I can empathise with their emotions as they approach coaching, especially at the earlier stages when their experience is not enough to provide them with the competence, and confidence, they need to succeed. Again, I made no assumptions about this, and cannot draw definite conclusions, but I feel my own experiences, and my coping mechanisms, allowed me to make a judgement about what the stories I was hearing were really telling me.

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8.0 Appendices

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8.1 Appendix 1 – Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Research Title:

“How likely are elite female footballers to consider entering into coaching as a career, and what are the underlying reasons for this?”

Purpose of the study: The purpose of this study is to investigate the experiences of elite female footballers and how these experiences have influenced future coaching intentions. Increasing female representation at all levels of the game, and in all roles, is currently a priority of the home nations’ Football Associations and UEFA, therefore to inspire more girls to be involved it is of interest to find out how past experiences have shaped current players’ perceptions of coaching; with the aim of increasing the number of females working at grassroots, club and elite level.

Why have I been approached to take part?

Elite players have been identified as potential high-level coaches of the future, therefore as a player in the top levels of the Scottish league and / or the national team your experiences are of real interest. All players in the top divisions in Scotland, as well as the Scottish national squad, have been invited to participate, regardless of their playing and coaching background to date.

Do I have to take part?

Participation in this study is entirely optional, if you do decide to take part you will be asked to provide consent. Even after you have decided to take part you are able to withdraw at any time and without giving a specified reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to complete a questionnaire which will ask some questions about your playing and coaching experience, and where you see yourself in the future. This should take no longer than 20 minutes to complete. Some players will then be invited to participate in an interview where findings can be discussed in more detail – this is completely optional, and you will indicate on the questionnaire whether you are willing to do this. If so, a time and location that is convenient to you will be arranged and this is expected to last around 40 minutes.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

The investigator does not see any possible disadvantages of taking part in this study.

The potential benefits of taking part:

By taking part you will add to the limited literature that is available about women's role in football in Britain, thus providing key information that may help to address the current gender imbalance in relation to coaching; and participation.

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

The study will be entirely confidential as the data collected from the research will only be available to the investigator and the academic supervisor from the University of the West of Scotland. No exceptions will be made. No identifying information will be asked for on the questionnaires and for those who take part in interviews pseudonyms will be provided for use in the write-up of the findings.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of the study will be published within my Professional Doctorate thesis, and a copy will be offered to all participants. A condensed version of the thesis is also likely to be sent to relevant journals for publication to help add to the currently growing literature on this topic.

8.2 Appendix 2 – Consent Form

An Exploration of the Experiences and Coaching Intentions of Female Elite Scottish Footballers

I _____ (insert name) agree to the use of any information from this interview being used in the thesis, and any associated publications, of the above research. I understand any identifying information will be removed to protect my anonymity. I acknowledge that I am participating in this interview voluntarily and if, at any stage prior to publication, I wish to withdraw my consent I can do so.

Signed: _____ Date: _____

8.3 Appendix 3 – Ethical Approval

03/06/2021

Dear Ms Laura Wallace,

Your application 8722: Elite Female Players' Coaching Intentions, submission 13729, has been approved by the Health and Life Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Gary Boyd

Page 1 of 1

8.4 Appendix 4 – Interview Guides

8.4.1 Current Coaches

Interview Schedule - Current Coaches

1. General introductions, housekeeping, etc.
2. Full name, age, current occupation, current team
3. Tell me a brief history of your career, how you got to where you are now.
4. Tell me about your experiences in relation to being coached as a player.
 - a. Did you experience mainly female or male coaches?
 - i. Did the gender of your coach change as you progressed through the levels?
 - b. Tell me about the relationship you had with your coaches throughout your playing career.
 - c. Tell me about any ways (if there are any) in which any previous coaches influenced your choice to become a coach yourself.
 - d. Tell me about any ways (if any) that previous coaches influenced your participation / progression in football.
5. Tell me about your coaching journey to date (e.g when did you start, what level(s) did / do you coach, what qualifications do you have, etc.)
 - a. Have you experienced any barriers to your progress? If so, explain.
6. Tell me a bit about your future coaching plans.
 - a. Detail your plans in relation to qualifications and experience to reach your goals.
 - b. Discuss the key influences on your choices.
 - c. Tell me if you expect to face any barriers in progressing in coaching.
 - i. Explain
7. Tell me about any experiences you have of coach education in relation to football.
8. Tell me your thoughts about how players perceive ex-high-level players as coaches?
 - a. Did you perceive coaches differently as a result of their playing experience?
 - b. (if appropriate) what do you feel ex-elite players can bring to their coaching that those who haven't played to that level can?
9. Do you think there is any benefit to being a female when coaching women's teams?

a. Or men's?

10. Is there anything else you think I may be interested to hear in relation to perceptions of coaching by elite players? And / or female coaches?

11. Thanks / close

8.4.2 – Past Coaches

Interview Schedule – Past-Coaches

1. General introductions, housekeeping, etc.
2. Full name, age, current occupation, current team
3. Tell me a brief history of your career, how you got to where you are now.
4. Tell me about your experiences in relation to being coached as a player.
 - a. Have you experienced mainly female or male coaches?
 - i. Has the gender of your coach changed as you've progressed through the levels?
 - b. Tell me about the relationship you've had with your coaches throughout your playing career.
 - c. Tell me about any ways (if there are any) in which any previous coaches have influenced your choice to become a coach yourself.
 - d. Tell me about any ways (if any) that previous coaches influenced your participation / progression in football.
5. Tell me a bit about your future career plans.
 - a. What have been the key influences on your choices? Explain.
 - b. Tell me if you expect to face any barriers in entering / progressing in your future career.
 - i. Explain
6. Have you considered the option of becoming a full-time coach at the end of your playing career?
 - a. Why do you think this is?
7. Tell me about your coaching journey (e.g when did you start, what level(s) did / do you coach, what qualifications do you have, etc.)
 - a. What prompted you to try coaching?
 - b. Did you experience any barriers to your progress? If so, explain.
 - c. What made you decide to stop coaching when you did?
8. Tell me a bit about your future coaching plans, if you have any.
 - a. Detail your plans in relation to qualifications and experience to reach your goals.
 - b. Discuss the key influences on your choices.
 - c. Tell me if you expect to face any barriers in re-entering / progressing in coaching.
 - i. Explain

9. Tell me about any experiences you have of coach education in relation to football.
10. Is there anything else you think I may be interested to hear in relation to perceptions of coaching by elite players?
 - a. How do you think players perceive former elite players as coaches?
 - b. Do you see any benefits to having played at an elite level for high-level coaches?
11. Thanks / close

8.4.3 No Coaching Experience

Interview Schedule – Non-coaches

1. General introductions, housekeeping, etc.
2. Full name, age, current occupation, current team
3. Tell me a brief history of your career, how you got to where you are now.
4. Tell me about your experiences in relation to being coached as a player.
 - a. Have you experienced mainly female or male coaches?
 - i. Has the gender of your coach changed as you've progressed through the levels?
 - b. Tell me about the relationship you've had with your coaches throughout your playing career.
 - c. Tell me about any ways (if there are any) in which any previous coaches have influenced your choice not to become a coach yourself.
 - d. Tell me about any ways (if any) that previous coaches influenced your participation / progression in football.
5. Tell me a bit about your future career plans.
 - a. What have been the key influences on your choices? Explain.
 - b. Tell me if you expect to face any barriers in entering / progressing in your future career.
 - i. Explain
6. Have you considered the option of becoming a full-time coach at the end of your playing career?
 - a. Why do you think this is?
7. Is there anything else you think I may be interested to hear in relation to perceptions of coaching by elite players?
 - a. How do you think players perceive former elite players as coaches?
 - b. Do you see any benefits to having played at an elite level for high-level coaches?
8. Thanks / close

8.5 Appendix 5 – Nvivo Examples

8.5.1 Example of codes

The screenshot shows the NVivo 12 Pro interface with a list of nodes. The 'Nodes' pane is active, displaying a table of nodes with columns for Name, Files, References, Created On, Created By, Modified On, and Modified By.

Name	Files	References	Created On	Created By	Modified On	Modified By
Barriers and enablers to future career (coaching)	7	48	20/05/2021 19:4	LW	24/05/2021 10:55	LW
Barriers and enablers to future career (not coaching)		4	20/05/2021 19:4	LW	24/05/2021 10:36	LW
Characteristics of a good coach		2	23/05/2021 13:4	LW	24/05/2021 10:59	LW
Coach education	7	43	20/05/2021 19:4	LW	24/05/2021 10:57	LW
Coaching experience	6	31	20/05/2021 19:4	LW	24/05/2021 10:55	LW
Coaching intentions		8	22/05/2021 15:5	LW	24/05/2021 10:56	LW
Education-career journey and influences		8	20/05/2021 19:5	LW	24/05/2021 10:49	LW
Experience of coaches		8	20/05/2021 19:4	LW	24/05/2021 10:48	LW
Football playing journey		8	22/05/2021 15:4	LW	24/05/2021 10:41	LW
Future career intentions		7	24/05/2021 19:4	LW	24/05/2021 10:50	LW
General playing experiences		4	8/20/05/2021 19:4	LW	24/05/2021 10:51	LW
General support for women's football	7	29	22/05/2021 16:0	LW	24/05/2021 10:45	LW
Influences on coaching		8	20/05/2021 19:4	LW	24/05/2021 10:54	LW
Influences on playing		8	20/05/2021 19:4	LW	24/05/2021 10:51	LW
Sacrifices	3	6	22/05/2021 15:5	LW	24/05/2021 10:51	LW
Thoughts on ex-players as coaches		8	20/05/2021 19:5	LW	24/05/2021 10:57	LW
Thoughts on females as coaches	7	24	20/05/2021 19:5	LW	24/05/2021 10:58	LW
Work-study-football-life balance	6	20	20/05/2021 19:4	LW	24/05/2021 10:41	LW

8.5.2 Example of quotes for codes

The screenshot shows the NVivo 12 Pro interface with a detailed view of a node. The 'Node Tools' pane is active, displaying a list of nodes and a detailed view of a selected node. The detailed view shows the node name, a list of files, and a list of references with their coverage percentages.

Node: Barriers and enablers to future c

It's so hard to try and fit it in, em just with my schedule but, yeah I need, I need to, that's something I need to try and do

Reference 8 - 0.90% Coverage

Yeah, time, em, yeah for me it's just time it's, again it's not just getting time off football 'cause obviously we're off-season it'll be in June it's getting that time off work (laugh). (LW: yeah) To try to do that to do that coaching so, 'cause I had to use my own holidays for my C-licence that was like, I can't remember 5 days over, 2,3 months and that was taking my, my own time off, work so it, it's hard. It is hard.

Reference 9 - 0.73% Coverage

I always have that in the back of my head thinking you know what just keep pushing, keep pushing and opportunities will hopefully come along so. It's kind of having that, that drive yourself I think, em, wanting to achieve that but yeah, just it's amazing in Scotland now they're putting money into it and hopefully we'll get up to the level of England.

Reference 10 - 0.95% Coverage